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Sujet de la thèse

Innovative approaches for high precision monitoring of snow
cover, Mount Lebanon

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Dedication

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Abstract

Global climate change induces transformations in rainfall and hydrological regimes in the Mediterranean regions. Lebanon is one of the richest countries in the Middle East for water resources thanks to its mountain ranges that trigger precipitation from the moist air masses coming from the Mediterranean Sea. Snowpack acts as natural water storage in winter and supplies fresh water during spring and summer. Yet, Lebanon is facing a serious water scarcity problem due to: i) the decreasing amount of snow precipitation and climate change; ii) the major growth of the original resident population and the large number of refugees that fled to the country during regional wars. Thus, continuous and systematic monitoring of the Lebanese water resources is becoming crucial. It is therefore very important to investigate low-cost methodologies in terms of both human resources and equipment.

The Mount Lebanon is characterized by karstic geological formations. Its highest tops are modeled and break out by sinkhole depressions of karstic depressions named “sinkholes.” It is important to monitor the snowmelt process inside these sinkholes because of their key role as “containers” for seasonal snow. In fact, by isolating the snowpack from sun radiation and wind, they slow down the natural melting process and sublimation, thus, delaying the low water flow period.

For the last 19 years, few studies have been conducted regarding the Lebanese snow cover. They were mainly focusing on estimating snow density and snow cover surface using remote sensing and terrestrial measurements on some zones. In 2010, AWS¹ has been

¹ Automatic Weather Station

installed in the convention of (USA, IRD²-CESBIO³, and CNRS⁴). In 2012 and 2013, the snow cover melting in a pilot sinkhole (2300m a.s.l) has been observed with the total station instruments.

This research aims to set up an observatory of snow evolution in the pilot sinkhole (2300m a.s.l.) and other sinkholes area (2000m a.s.l) located in Mount Lebanon. Measurements were done using terrestrial (just for a pilot sinkhole) and aerial photogrammetry. Those measurements led to the generation of DEMs, which are validated with total station instruments. Firstly, terrestrial photogrammetry was based on a system that uses three time-lapse cameras and structure-from-motion principles to reconstruct the snow DEMs evolution within the sinkhole. Secondly, aerial photogrammetry missions were done by Phantom DJI⁵. It serves to monitor the pilot sinkhole, extends the study area and monitors other sinkholes area. Thirdly, a total station instrument also serves to fill the gap of observation when terrestrial cameras and drones face any logistical problem.

Regarding the observations, more than 40 sites visits were driven. This provides a series of annual and inter-annual snow DEMs that were built, serving to estimate HS, surface, and volume. It was then possible to understand the snowmelt behavior during each year. In addition, those DEMs and volumes provide important information about the trend of the snow cover decrease from year to another. Moreover, they may lead to the approximate prediction of total snowmelt.

² Institut de recherché pour le développement
³ Centre d'Etudes Spatial de la Biosphere
⁴ Centre National de la recherche scientifique
⁵ Dà-Jiāng Innovations (DJI company)

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List of abbreviations

ASP	Ames Stereo Pipeline
AWS	Automatic weather station
CESBIO	Centre d'Etudes Spatiales de la Biosphere
CMVS	Clustering View for Multi-view Stereo
CNRS\NCRS	National Council for Scientific Research
CREEN	Centre Régional de l'Eau et de l'Environnement
DGGA	Direction des Affaires Géographiques
DSM	Digital Surface Model
EDM	Electronic Distance Measuring
GCP	Ground Control Points
GIS	Geographical Information Systems
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global position system
GSD	Ground Sample Distance
HS	Height of Snow
ICP	Iterative Closet Point
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IRD	Institut de Recherche pour le Développement
LCD	Liquid Crystal Display
NSO	network for snow observation
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
RTK	Real Time Kinematic
SCA	Snow covered Area
SIFT	Scale Invariant Feature Transformation
SWE	Snow Water Equivalent
TLS	Terrestrial laser scanner
TM5	Thematic Mapper 5
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
USJ	Université Saint Joseph
OLIFE	Observatoire Franco-Libanais de l'Environnement
MVS	Multi-View Stereo
WASH	Water Sanitation and Hygiene

General Introduction

At an international scale, climate changes have a significant impact on water resources due to the cumulative effect of the rising temperature and the decreasing snowfall (Somma et al., 2006; Drapeau et al., 2013; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Fayad et al., 2017). Middle Eastern countries suffer from these changes, as the majority of the region's area is arid (Mhaweij et al., 2014; Abou Chakra, 2013). Lebanon is drastically affected by climate change although it is one of the richest snow covers in the Middle East (Shaban, 2011; Shaban et al., 2004; Telesca et al., 2014).

In addition to water resources decreasing, Lebanon is facing an important population growth rate due specifically to regional wars, having hosted large number of refugees. Water supply is crucial for the majority of Lebanese people, especially during the dry summer season because of the previously mentioned reason and due to the lack of water resources legal control (El-Fadel et al., 2000; Fawaz, 2009; Shaban et al., 2011; Telesca et al., 2014). Subsequently, within the framework of the current climate change, continuous and systematic water supply observation is required for water management planning (Somma et al., 2014).

Indeed the distribution of snowfall and rainfall precipitations is driven by the major role of the highest Lebanese mountains as mountains role in the entire world (Viviroli et al., 2007; Jonas et al., 2009; Shaban, 2011; Dettinger, 2014; Telesca et al. 2014; Mhaweij et al., 2014; Fayad et al., 2017). Furthermore, about 30% of water resources as well as about 31% of rivers and spring discharges are linked to the Lebanese snow covers (Telesca et al., 2014; Mhaweij et al., 2014; Fayad et al., 2017). Moreover, snow covers around 25% of the total Lebanese territory (Shaban et al., 2004; Telesca et al., 2014; Mhaweij et al., 2014; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Fayad et al., 2017). Based on the above, one of the most imperative components of water resources investigation is the constant monitoring of snow covers, in order to elaborate prediction plan for the future hydrological regimes (Somma et al., 2014; Fayad, 2017).

Numerous karstic depressions “sinkholes” punctuate Mount Lebanon high plateaus and play the role of “containers” for the seasonal snow (Somma et al., 2014; Elali, 2014; Abou Chakra et al., 2016). They seem to contribute to the deceleration of the melting rate as they protect the snowpack from the wind and sun radiation. Thus, this process delay the low water flow period (Shaban, 2011; Somma et al., 2014). Therefore, it is also important to monitor the snow melting processes and speed inside those depressions. This could allow predicting dates of total snow melting, which could be useful for hydrologists to predict the beginning of low flow water season.

Snow is not just a national issue. It is important to mention that a significant number of nationals and internationals organizations consider its high priority (Fayad et al., 2017). At a local level, Lebanon is considered as snow observatory for this project (CESBIO, CNRS-L, USJ⁶). In this context, also three automatic weather stations have been installed and were integrated in newly founded observatory on biodiversity (OLIFE⁷). In that perspective, our thesis research aims to compare different approaches for snowpack volume estimation and the understanding of snowmelt dynamic behavior on the high plateaus of Ouyoun el Simane. Combining different innovative approaches, it will explore and identify the best solution for each used approach and ultimately the basement of a low cost snow cover monitoring approach.

⁶ Université Saint Joseph

⁷ Observatoire Franco-Libanais de l'Environnement

Problematic / Rationale

Global changes and climatic variations are one of the main concerns nowadays due to their negative impacts on several levels. Among them we can note the trend of temperature augmentation (Gao et al., 2017; Abhayapala et al., 2018), the acceleration of glaciers and snow cover melting, changes in hydrological regimes, floods, seal level rise (El Hage et al., 2011), drought (Asadi Zarch et al., 2017) ... affecting the natural and human environment biodiversity.

Snow cover plays a major role as fresh water reserve of planet earth. Due to climate change, the average global temperature has an increasing trend that was estimate about 1.8°C between 1963 and 2009 (Shaban et al., 2014). This issue affects decreasing trend of snow cover area (SCA⁸) from year to year. That is why in the last decades, snow cover thematic became highlighted for many researchers. Wide thematic review done by Fayad et al. (2017) shows that the majority of all articles (90.5%) about snow were published between 2000 and 2016 (Figure 1) what is very significant.

Figure 1: Cumulative yearly number of publications per journal (based on 561 articles published between 2000 and 2016) (Fayad et al., 2017)

⁸ Snow Covered Area

Mediterranean regions has been considered as climate change hot spot (Milly et al., 2005; Giorgi, 2006; Nohara et al., 2006; Nogues-Bravo et al., 2007; Giorgi and Lionello, 2008; Loarie et al., 2009; Kysely et al., 2012; Kapnick and Delworth, 2013; Moran-Tejeda et al., 2014; Prudhomme et al., 2014; Harpold and Molotch, 2015; Vano et al., 2015; Kumar et al., 2016; Fayad et al., 2017). The main indicators of this change is the trend shifting in hydrological regime from snowfall to rainfall (Berghuijs et al., 2014; Goulden and Bales, 2014; Fayad et al., 2017).

Geographically, Lebanon is part of the Mediterranean basin. Although this country have a small surface area of 10452 km² (Gears et al., 2010), it is highly considered for regional climatic assessment models because it is the only region in the Middle East where snow remain for several months and cover an important part of its territory (Corbane et al., 2005; Telesca et al., 2014; Shaban and Houhou, 2015).

Mountains have an essential role in leading the distribution of solid or liquid precipitation (McCab et al., 2007; Surfleet and Tullos, 2013; Mhaweij et al., 2014; Telesca et al., 2014; Guan et al., 2016). Indeed, Lebanon has high mountain peaks that act as a barrier to the prevailing southwest winds carrying moisture from the Mediterranean Sea. Their high altitudes favor snowfalls precipitations and the persistence of snow patches along many months (Somma et al., 2001; Somma et al., 2014). In addition, snow cover is a primary recharge source for groundwater systems across Lebanese summits.

The geological configuration of these highlands is karstic that is translated in the landscape as a very wavy relief. In fact, these high plateaus are picketed by a large number of karst depressions (sinkholes), which in turn play a fundamental role as natural reservoirs since they keep the snow inside the hollows protecting it from the winds and the sun radiations. Thus, snow melt slowly and as the melt water cannot runoff according to the dolines's shape, it can infiltrate the ground and feed groundwater reserves. The slowness caused by the sinkholes is one of the most important factors that contribute to delay the periods of Low Flow Water (Somma et al., 2014).

In such a wavy land due to the depressions, snow cover is a dynamic and irregular surface over space and time (López-Moreno 2005; Dèry & Brown, 2007; Svoma, 2011; Mizukami and Smith, 2012; Bormann et al., 2013; Somma, et al., 2014; Luce et al., 2014; Scipion, et al., 2013; Cimoli et al., 2017). From a hydrological perspective, an important parameter of the snow cover is Snow Water Equivalent (SWE⁹) which calculation is closely linked to the HS¹⁰ (Molotch et al., 2005; Lopez-Moreno and Noghés-Bravo, 2006; Lopez-Moreno et al., 2010; Pimentel et al., 2015; Dozier et al., 2016; Fayad et al., 2017; Cimoli et al., 2017). An accurate estimation of the HS, variability spatial distribution, volume and their dynamic behavior over days and years can improve the understanding of climate, and hydrological regime (Barnett et al., 2005; Lopez-Moreno and Noghés-Bravo, 2006; Che et al., 2011; Abou Chakra, 2013; Elali, 2014 ; Somma et al., 2014; Cimoli, 2015; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Fayad et al., 2017).

Snow cover plays an important role in the water cycle at both global (Che et al., 2011) and national scale (Shaban et al., 2014) and constitute an important water reserve. (Shaban and Darwich, 2013) estimate that about 58% of Lebanese water resources comes from snowmelt. If the temperatures trend continue toward up, snow mantle that was covering around 25% of national territory (Shaban et al., 2004; Telesca et al., 2014; Mhaweij et al., 2014), will decrease proportionally to the temperature rise (Fayad et al., 2017). Lebanon without snow could be without rivers with very few springs attending that snowmelt contributes to feed 31% of hydrological system for 15 River basins and more than 2000 springs (Telesca et al., 2014; Mhaweij et al., 2014).

Modifications in hydrological regime is an essential issue since Lebanon is having a warming trouble in water management (El-Fadel et al., 2000; Fawaz, 2009; Shaban et al., 2014; Telesca et al., 2014) especially in managing irrigation timing. It is known also that

⁹ Snow Water Equivalence

¹⁰ Height of Snow

Lebanese residents go through water-rationing problems during summer season (Somma et al., 2014). In addition, Lebanon is facing a serious problem due to the increasing of population and receiving a big number of regional refugees (Figure 2) (Abou Chakra et al., 2016; <https://knoema.com/atlas/Lebanon/Population>). This accentuates the water resources question and an important alert appears about the future sustainability of water reserve in Lebanon (Geara et al., 2010).

Figure 2 Lebanese and refugees population counted 6.08 million people in 2017. It is important to note that from 1968 to 2017, the population increased from 2.21 million to 6.08 million, which means it grows by an annual average of 2.10%. (<https://knoema.com/atlas/Lebanon/Population>).

The good managing of the water resources is then crucial. Thus, the early prediction of low flow water, in addition of well understanding the snow cover in term of quantity and dynamic behavior became a priority for Lebanese sustainable future (Abou Chakra et al., 2018). In this framework, it seems important to register annual and inter annual snow mantle fluctuations (Bernier et al., 2003; Aouad-Rizk et al., 2005; Corbane et al., 2005; Shaban et al., 2013; Telesca et al., 2014; Somma et al., 2014; Mhaweij et al., 2014; Shaban et al., 2014; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Fayad et al., 2017).

In relation to this thematic what were the previous researches on the Lebanese snow cover?

The first snow thematic studies in Lebanon were carried out under the initiative of two laboratories at Saint Joseph University: the Remote Sensing Laboratory and the Regional Center for Water and Environment (CREEN) in 2000. CREEN¹¹ installed few meteorological stations distributed at different altitudes (Khalil, 2002) and master degree students such as Touma (2002), Khalil (2002), and Bitar (2002), were respectively interested in the “calculation of the snow covered areas of Mount Lebanon, the “Modeling of snow melt in Mount Lebanon” and the “Equivalence in Water”. However, as Touma (2002) pointed out that it was difficult at the time to conduct accurate surveys or observations with basic cartography documents or tools (Touma, 2002; Mhawej et al., 2014; Telesca et al., 2014). CREEN with Aouad-Rizk et al (2005), realized a preliminary study of snow cover over Mount Lebanon and a simple snowmelt model. This study covered Nahr el Kalb bassin using DEM, TM5¹² and meteorological data for year 2001.

Besides, an approach using RADAR satellite imagery to measure the thickness of the snow cover and its density in order to calculate the water equivalent (SWE) was successfully done at Quebec and French Pyrenees (Bernier et al., 2003; Corbane et al., 2004; Abou Chakra, 2013; Telesca et al., 2014). The advantage of the method lies in the ability of the radar wave to penetrate the snowpack as long as it is dry. It was applied to the Lebanese territory (Bernier et al., 2003; Corbane et al., 2004). Unfortunately, this has not produced convincing results due to the excessive humidity of the snow and the sensitivity of the radar to it (Shaban et al., 2004; Aouad et al., 2004; Aouad et al., 2005; Abou Chakra, 2013; Telesca et al., 2014).

At the CNRS-L, Shaban et al., (2004) used low-resolution SPOT-VEGETATION images with 10-day intervals in order to monitor the spatial evolution of the snow cover over Mount Lebanon; this resolution did not allows to extract indications about snow cover thicknesses

¹¹ Centre Régional de l’eau et de l’environnement

¹² Thematic Mapper 5

along the melting season, nor even to observe the sinkholes or the karst reliefs (Shaban, 2011).

Two years later Somma and Luxey (2006) picked up, using an Ikonos Satellite Image and a Digital Elevation Model, the altitudes of discontinuous peripheries firms that were trapped in few sinkholes. With the Earth Vision (DGI) modeler, they modeled the snow patch in 3D by interpolating these altitudes, applying them on bare land model and then the volume could be calculated. However, to be accurate this method requires field data about névé's surface, which may be concave, convex, plane or oblique.

In 2010, a program was established in collaboration between the 'Institut de Recherche pour le Développement' (IRD) (France), the 'Centre d'Etudes Spatiales de la Biosphere' (CESBIO) (France), the National Council for Scientific Research – Remote Sensing Center (CNRS\NCRS) (Lebanon), and Saint Joseph University (USJ) (Lebanon). Three meteorological stations are operationnal under a joint-program for establishing a network for snow observation (NSO¹³) on : i) Mzaar plateau at 2300m ; ii) Cedars heights at 2900 m and ; iii) Laqlouq at 1840 m (Telesca et al., 2014 ; Fayad el a., 2017). In this context, it is important to note that AWS include accurate meteorological data such snow height, temperature, relative humidity, incoming and reflected solar radiation, wind speed and direction, and atmospheric pressure (Fayad et al., 2017). However, it remains a challenge to have accurate estimation of snow drift due to wind (Goodison et al., 1998; Nitu et al., 2010; Qui, 2012).

In 2014, a monitoring was done with MODIS images, with a resolution of either 250m or 1000m (Mhaweij et al., 2014, Telesca et al., 2014, Fayad, 2017). The Telesca study in (2014) driven a monthly surveying of the snow covers developments from the year 2000 to year 2012 by combining Modis and Landsat satellite images. For the same time interval, Mhaweij (2014) carried out a study in order to see the distribution of the snow covers between 2000

¹³ Network for snow observation

and 2012 and to calculate their equivalence in water. [Fayad \(2017\)](#) measured snow density and tried to measure HS, in addition of using Modis for surface estimation. He used also satellite data and meteorological station to realize a hydrological model.

An annex work touched the maximum capacity of snow retention of a summit area by modelling its depressions and calculating the volume of void between an initial virtual surface and the current wavy land which have been worked by dissolution, erosion, and corrosion ([Somma et al., 2014](#)). This study does not touch directly the snow cover, however, it highlight the importance of Lebanese high plateaus as natural tanks and the possibility to evaluate the reserve stored in its depression.

Based on terrestrial approaches, other studies aimed to define the speed of snow volume decreasing and the way in which it decreases using most accurate topographic methods for a pilot sinkhole ([Abou Chakra, 2013](#); [Somma et al., 2014](#); [Elali, 2014](#); [Abou Chakra et al., 2016](#)). Those studies were accomplished by a surveying measurement technique using Total Station machine (see: 2.1.1 Total Station). This instrument is one of the most precise tools for accurate measurements. The survey were done by [Abou Chakra \(2013\)](#) and [Elali \(2014\)](#) during a master degree at Saint Joseph University for snowmelt monitoring in a pilot sinkhole on the Lebanese high plateau during years 2012 and 2013. These studies had very high spatial resolution and a monthly temporal resolution but low points density measurement comparing to dense cloud. Metric measurements are very precise (1 mm to 2 cm) in term of point's measurement accuracy. However, they have a weakness due the low density of measured points comparing to Lidar or Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS¹⁴). Although Total station measurement is considered as low cost approach for small areas, it takes a lot of time (hours for a small area). On the other hand, snow cover is very dynamic in term of melting and accumulation ([Abou Chakra, 2013](#); [Elali, 2014](#); [Somma](#)

¹⁴ Terrestrial Laser Scanner

et al., 2014). Consequently, it becomes almost impossible to apply this procedure on a large territory because of i) the numerous teams needed; ii) necessity to carry a lot of equipment iii) due to the difficult accessibility to the whole plateau which make this approach hard and too expensive or even impossible on national scale.

Photogrammetric approach using aircraft has never been applied for snow cover monitoring in Lebanon. Photogrammetry required authorization, ground control points and is very expensive. In addition, classic photogrammetry on snow cover could face problems of finding homologous points to construct accurate DEM (Smith et al., 1967; Buhler et al., 2015).

By reviewing the previous studies that relied on remote sensing, it is noticeable that:

- Radar remain imperfect for the acquisition of precise measurement of snow cover thickness over a large area, either because the sensibility of Radar to wet snow layer, or due to low-resolution, or because the lack of field measurements;

- Observations done by Modis, Landsat and spot vegetation has a high temporal resolution but a very low spatial resolution according to our need. The pixel size was about 500m for Modis and 15-30m for Landsat. However, the Lebanese sinkholes vary in size from 2 to 40 m deep and about 10 to 300 m in diameter. Therefore, those spatial resolutions remain very low and cannot meet our need since the whole study area is contained in one or very few pixels.

Since few years, it was possible to have almost daily satellite imagery with an acceptable spatial resolution up to 3 m. This imagery is very helpful to easily calculate the snow cover surface variation. However, due to heterogeneity of the HS, we have to get the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) (Cimoli et al., 2015; Cimoli et al., 2017) of the snow patches inside these sinkholes (Abou Chakra, 2013; Elali, 2014, Somma et al., 2014; Abou Chakra et al, 2016). However, this imagery does not allow us to build DEMs and so to calculate the snow cover evolution in terms of volume.

We could use then spatial images PLEIADES by requesting consecutive and continuous acquisition of this very high-resolution imagery (50 cm). As example, PLEIADES has another advantage: the stereoscopic and even tri-stereoscopic imaging acquisition that allows DEMs production. Unfortunately Pleiades operator is since few years occupied by the military survey of Syria. In addition, of its high cost, it could be sometimes difficult to program a mission with Pleiades operator due to meteorological uncertainties.

In regard of the high cost of a massive terrain mission with an important and expansive need in team, instrumentation and transports, we ask ourselves if observations and monitoring on a single experimental pilot site could inform about a more wide area even on the whole plateau?

Ultimately, we are particularly interested by the aspect of thickness, surface and volume accumulated inside sinkholes. We aim to find the optimal methods of volumes estimation, in terms of cost and human resources. According to our knowledge, systematic and continuous (annual and interannual) monitoring for Lebanese snow cover at high spatial and temporal resolution has never been accomplished yet.

The rationale behind this study is the proceeding by innovative approaches in order to achieve easy monitoring system for snow cover like steady cameras and drone. Therefore, following questions arise:

a) Relying on low-cost observation approaches, is it possible to monitor accurately and automatically the snow cover volume decreasing during the melting season, in a pilot sinkhole, with a high spatio-temporal resolution ?

b) based on the pilot sinkhole observations, is it possible to:

1) understand snow melt behavior inside sinkholes ?

2) and to have precise information about the snow cover decreasing or increasing from year to year ?

Objectives

To answer to the above rationale, we will continue the studies of [Abou chakra \(2013\)](#), [Elali \(2014\)](#) and [Abou Chakra et al., \(2016\)](#). Thus, we can make a systematic and continuous observation of snow cover dynamism with high spatial and temporal resolution using three different approaches:

- continuing of the same procedure done by [Abou Chakra \(2013\)](#) and [Elali \(2014\)](#) in the same pilot site (witness sinkhole as topographic measurement, but in increasing the temporal resolution to weekly observation of the snow cover diminution (volume, surface, perimeter and HS) for the years 2015 and 2016 to understand the melting process in this area. This will be realized with high accuracy topographic instruments: total station for year 2015 - 2016 and UAV¹⁵ for year 2016;
- making automatic daily observation using steady cameras. This will be an innovative approach because although there is many studies based on time-lapse photography no one used it for 3D observation on snow cover. Therefore, this approach will be based on terrestrial time-lapse photogrammetry and will be validated by a total station instrument;
- finding the best solution for making snow cover observation using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV DJI Phantom) by testing many parameters like speed, different flight heights and processing resolution in the perspective to enlarge the study area;
- validating this procedure on another area (Bou Mechleh) after understanding the volume decreasing process in Jabal el Dib (witness sinkhole);
- Estimate approximate prediction date of total snowmelt in the study area.

¹⁵ Unmanned Aerial Vehicle

Objectives

The focus of this study is to test the advantages and disadvantages of the above-mentioned approaches and instruments that will be very helpful to make continuous observations for snow cover dynamics.

Study area

- Generality about Lebanon

The country of study area is part of the Mediterranean basin. Lebanon is nearly rectangular of about 10452 km² area. It is located on the east of Mediterranean Sea (figure 3) Lebanon has local population of about four millions inhabitants in addition of two millions refugees. The country had a quick rise of population rate on the last decade, especially after receiving a big number of refugees due to regional wars.

Figure 3: Localization map

Affected by the Mediterranean climate, the Lebanese summer is hot, long and dry. The winter is temperate and snow covers the majority of its high summits (Kinab et Elkhoury, 2012; www.climatetemp.info/lebanon; 2011). Lebanon have four seasons and sixths months of precipitation distributed as rainfalls and snowfalls (Fayad, 2007), depending on the temperature and the altitude of the area (Fayad et al., 2017). Winter precipitations (December - March) are estimated for 84% of total annual precipitation. Most precipitations above 1600 m.a.s.l. are snowfalls thanks to the Lebanese high mountains (Fayad, 2017). This makes Lebanon one of the richest among Middle Eastern countries in fresh water and snow covers. Snow may cover the quarter of the total territory (Shaban et al., 2004).

The majority of the Lebanese high mountains is karstic and presents a big number of ellipsoidal dolines and conical funnel shaped that favors snow accumulation. At the

beginning of the snow melting, we observe that these dolines keep important volume of snow because of their geometry; which means that melting water can penetrate the first layers to the ground aquifer.

This study is focusing on an area located in Jabal El Dib and another in Chiaab Bou Mechleh in the upper mountains of Ouyoun al-Siman (Figure 5): respectively 2,300 meters high and 2,000 meters above sea level. We chose them because of their proximity to Beirut, around 40 km, which makes them easy to reach and get the measurements without losing too much time on the road and because snow covers them for about several months per year. It means that the snow can remain until the end of July or August in Jabal El Dib area and until June in Bou Mechleh considering its altitude (depending on years). These highlands constitute areas of high importance, as they can be used as water reserves.

The study of Chiaab Abu Mechleh region was only done in 2017. We have used it as a validation area for the results obtained in Jabal El Dib.

Selected study area

As mentioned the work was done on an experimental site and a validation site (Figure 4):

- **The experimental site** is a sinkhole next to the arrival of the Jabal el Dib chairlift. This sinkhole (which we will name "JD sinkhole") is interesting from several points of view:
- It is at 2300 m above sea level, at an elevation where snow persists almost till the end of the melt season;
- It is easily accessible (chairlift, dirt road outside the snow period, possibility of using all-terrain vehicles or snowmobiles for equipment transportation);
- A meteorological station has been installed (thanks to the partnership with IRD-CESBIO) on one of its crests (NE);
- A geodetic point is located on the opposite ridge (SW) which facilitates topographic measurements;

Study area

- It is about fifteen meters deep, oval shaped with 75 m wide and 120m long. Its bottom is double and its most important part is 36 m long and 30 m wide. A crack in the ground allows the meltwater to infiltrate it with big noise. This infiltration could be measured.
- **A validation site (Bou Mechleh)** is 300m lower, on a larger observation area with several sinkholes, larger than the JD sinkhole ();

Figure 4: Selected Study areas locations

It is interesting to note that for elongated sinkholes and undulations, the elongation is perpendicular to the direction of prevailing winds from the southwest. Snow is driven by the wind on the ridges of the depressions and accumulates at their bottom favoring their filling, hence the interest of evaluation of trapped volumes because their contribution to groundwater recharge will be important. It will be correlated with the snow accumulated quantity. In addition, these sinkholes snows are somehow protected from solar radiation and winds. Their snowfields melt slowly than the steep slopes ones that are very exposed to sun and winds, hence a groundwater recharge quite slow during the melt season (Abou Chakra et al., 2018).

The above mentioned phenomena, cause high heterogeneity distribution in snow high. Indeed, this distribution make sensor of snow depth installed at AWS unable to well present the snow height that require particular distributed measurements (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Snow heterogeneity HS accumulation at Jabal El Dib sinkhole on March 19th 2016;

Thesis structure

General introduction, rational, objective, study area and three chapters present the core research of this thesis.

General introduction paragraph introduce global and Lebanese climate situation and negative impact of climate change on water resources. This paragraph highlights the importance of Lebanese mountains chains by favoring snowfall during winter, in addition of its geomorphological characteristics acting as natural water reservoirs in Lebanon. Moreover, this part presents the strategic importance of Lebanon, because it is considered as regional climate change indicator.

Rational section starts by announcing briefly the influence of climate change on water resources at worldwide, Mediterranean and Lebanese scale Level. Water problem management and increasing of Lebanese population are noted. In this context, general literature overview on hydrological studies in Lebanon is presented. Positive and negative reviews for each studies has been prepared according to questions of this thesis that were about: i) annual and inter-annual snow melt behavior and ii) suitable low cost and efficient techniques for snow cover monitoring.

On one hand, objectives paragraph declares the necessary steps to answer to rational in term of technical approaches, used instruments and hydrological goal. On the other hand, study area part provides general summary about Lebanese climate, geographic and geomorphological characteristics. More deeper, study area paragraph describe in details the pilot site located at Jabal el Dib and the validation site located at Bou Mechleh.

In order to define scientific materials needed in the research, chapter 1 introduces possible snow cover measurement techniques. Besides, it describes different approaches that allow Digital Elevation Model (DEM) creation like interpolation and Structure from Motion (SfM). In addition, chapter 1 explain the concept of automatic relocation of DEM

based on Iterative closest points (ICP¹⁶). Snow cover surface, thickness and volume are defined.

To achieve objectives of this research thesis, corresponding instruments and approaches are clearly explained in chapter 2. Firstly, used instruments (Total Station, GNSS¹⁷ device, steady cameras, UAV, geodetic points) have been presented. Secondly, methodology using each instrument has been demonstrated.

Results are presented in chapter 3, which is divided into two parts. Part 1 shows technical results by assessing the powerful of instruments and approaches. This part is mainly focusing on validation of DEMs accuracy extracted from each used approached. Part 2 concentrates on understanding snow melt behavior in the pilot sinkhole that was observed from 2012 to 2018. Snowmelt behavior between Jabal El Dib and Bou Mechleh area is then highlighted. The common behavior allows the perspective of results extrapolation on larger area for further studies.

Core of this thesis, is finalized by conclusion and perspectives. In this part, we will prove that the questions of this study were answered. Moreover, major limitations will be highlighted and future perspectives will be opened.

¹⁶ Iterative Closest Points

¹⁷ Global Navigation Satellite system

Chapter 1: Theoretical approaches

1.1 Introduction to snow cover measurement

This study aims at better estimates and monitors the snow cover (snow surface, height of snow and snow volume) on Lebanese high plateaus that are known by their wavy land. Due to the nature of such land and the wind drift the spatial variability on snow distribution is very high (Aouad-Rizk et al., 2005; Shaban and Darwich, 2011; Somma et al., 2014; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Fayad et al., 2017). To solve the issue we will use some of geomatics tools in order calculate snow surfaces (Shaban et al., 2014; Telesca et al., 2014) and snow volume (Abou chakra, 2013; Prokop et al., 2014; El ali, 2014; Cimoli, 2015; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Cimoli et al., 2017; Mertes et al., 2017). To calculate snow cover volumes, we need to create a Digital Elevation Model (DEM) for both of snow cover and Bare Land. It is important to note that the quality of DEM plays an important role to accurately estimate volume (Reuter et al., 2008; El Hage et al., 2012). Geomatics plays a key role in the approach. Its tools (surveying, terrestrial and aerial photogrammetry) were main tools approaches for snow cover measurements with our fieldwork.

1.2 Mapping and Digital Elevation Model (DEM)

Mapping surveys indicates locations of natural features on Earth, including vegetation, rivers, lakes, oceans, among others, and draw the relief including hills, valleys, and snow cover. In order to describe features that appear on the map, lines and symbols are used and names and legends are added to recognize some of the objects shown. For our purpose, we are interested to sense the snowmelt dynamic. For that goal, two types of DEMs are needed: i) first DEM represents the bare land and; ii) second DEM present the snow cover at day of survey.

The generation and quality of Maps and DEMs are divided into two different types of survey (Schneider, 2001; El hage et al., 2012): i) planimetry, which are objects shown in the

2D plan (X-Y) views only that allow to observe the top view of snow cover and ii) altimetry or topography, which represent the height of natural and artificial features (Brabant, 2003). For our case, the measurements will focus on estimating the HS and surface. These both part of the monitoring procedure allow us to obtain the geometric shape of the snow cover. It is important to mention that the two types (planimetry and altimetry) have also various applications that are used by engineers, geologists, forecasters, architects, archaeologists, geographers, and scientists.

Relief is expressed in maps through colors, hatching and shading. While for topographic maps, it is obvious that surveyors and engineers prefer to use contours lines or raster DEM also in colors. On the other hand, new computer methods are used to illustrate relief, such as Digital Elevation Models (DEMs), 3D volumetric models that could be shown on Earth Vision software for example.

In the coming paragraphs we will talk about the mapping “point by points” or “by dense cloud”, which were chosen for this study, in addition of explaining the fundamental of Iterative closest points (ICP).

1.2.1 Constructing DEM with manual random points

Generally, this approach could be done with total station (see: 2.1.1 total station) or GPS¹⁸ device (see: 2.1.2 GPS receiver) for fieldwork (Brabant 2003; Ghilani, 2012), however in our study, we did not use GPS device for snow cover mapping, we just use it for GCPs¹⁹ measurements coordinates. Total station is efficient because it collect data accurately and get the accuracy of 3D points (X, Y, and Z). With Total station, we measure the snow cover

¹⁸ Global Positioning System

¹⁹ Ground Control Points

point by point, thus we have to observe group of points (Figure 6). In fact, we create fictive representative grid on each slope changing in order to obtain reliable representation of terrain (Figure 6).

Figure 6: 3D model of an area with the distributed random points

The data required X (Easting), Y (Northing), and Z (Elevation) measurements can be obtained from the total station if the instrument is located within a referenced geo-system. This referenced geo-system could whether be arbitrary or coordinate reference systems because all surveyed points are located relatively to the instrument and/or the reference object (Lavine et al., 2003). Within the defined coordinate system, instrument setups are applied on a reference point or object (Brabant, 2003). For the Lebanese territory, the stereographic projection is used as coordinate system. The total station is positioned at a location with best overview of the area (Lavine et al., 2003).

Total station generates ID number, descriptor, and prism height for each point being surveyed. Point ID, code, prism height, horizontal and vertical angles, slope distance, northing, easting, elevation and all information are stored in memory. As for the point descriptors, they can be recorded either numerically or alphanumerically since they can describe the whole process, the topographic features, survey makers, roads, among others.

Once the field collection is done, the data will be downloaded from the total station to a computer; this is where reports are generated, together with the raw data and X, Y, and Z coordinates for each point, before being transferred into a GIS²⁰ and other 2D and 3D software packages (Milles et Lagofun, 1999). Thus, in order to instigate the structural interpretation, it is easy to make profiles through the surfaces at any orientation (Ghilani, 2012).

1.2.2 Constructing DEM with Photogrammetry and Dense cloud

In 1839, photography was discovered and the first aerial photograph was taken in 1858. Later, they tried to integrate photogrammetry in the elaboration of a topographic map. Nowadays, this new method has become the primordial tool used in topographic mapping and in compiling other forms of spatial data (Ghilani, 2012). Any accurate photographs taken from anywhere on Earth (airplane or terrestrial) and taking into consideration photogrammetric rules, give us the ability of having accurate map and DEM (Milles et Lagofun, 1999).

This approach has many benefits: such as the speed of collecting spatial data in any area, it's relatively low cost, the easy access to topographic details particularly in inaccessible areas (aerial photogrammetry case) and the reduced risk of eliminating any required details in spatial data collection. This technique has passed through many stages and improvements throughout the years. The latest is the Structure from Motion approaches (SfM).

SfM is a photogrammetric technique, which automatically resolves the scene's geometry, the camera's position and orientation (Vasuki et al., 2014; Aguera-Vega et al.,

²⁰ Geographical Information System

2016; Snavely et al., 2017); SfM includes Multi-View Stereo (MVS²¹) techniques (Furukawa et al., 2007 ; Aguera-Vega et al., 2016), which originates 3D structure from overlapping photography taken from multiple angles (Brunier et al., 2016; Li et al., 2016).

SfM methodology rebuilds 3D models of objects or scenes through various overlapping images taken from a normal digital camera (Cimoli, 2015; Cimoli et al., 2017). In fact, it is considerably different from traditional methods because scene's geometry as well as positions and orientations of cameras are automatically solved without recurring to any targets network with known 3D positions (Figure 7). SfM technique interprets issues directly, with its iterative set of adjustments based on features database instantly extracted from various overlapping images (Snavely, 2008; Cimoli, 2015; Morgan et al., 2016; James et al., 2016; Mertes et al., 2017; Cimoli et al., 2017).

The SfM process uses various images processing algorithms. At first, a tracking algorithm detector, the Scale Invariant Feature Transformation (SIFT²²), that identify patterns through the overall pictures (Lowe, 2004). Reconstruction of surfaces less textured like snow or sand is blocked with difficulties (Furukaw et al., 2004; Westboy et al., 2012; Fonstad et al., 2013). Then, both external and internal parameters of the camera are solved with an adjustments algorithm (Triggs, et al., 1999) that generates a sparse point cloud representing the scene. We note then an augmentation of the point cloud especially when Clustering View for Multi-view Stereo (CMVS²³) and Patch-Based Multi-view Stereo (PMVS) are implemented (Furukawa & Ponce, 2007; Furukawa, et al., 2010). Consequently, a fitted 3D mesh result of the dense point cloud that was possible thanks to the traditional interpolation methods used triangulation in particular. Here, the amount and distribution of matched and cloud points indicate how well the object is being reconstructed.

²¹ Multi-View Stereo

²² Scale Invariant Feature Transformation

²³ Clustering View for Multi-View Stereo

Figure 7: Point-cloud reconstruction: Image projection of reconstructed patches in their visible images are used to perform fundamental tasks such as accessing neighboring patches, enforcing regularization, etc (https://ags.cs.uni-kl.de/fileadmin/inf_ags/3dcv-ws14-15/3DCV_lec11_Dense3DReconstructionII.pdf).

SfM is considered nowadays an efficient, accurate and low-cost tool used in geoscience applications because it can generate high-precision DEMs in comparison with other established methods like terrestrial or airborne LiDAR and Interferometric Synthetic Aperture Radar (IFSAR) sensors (Westboy, et al., 2012; James & Robson, 2012; Cimoli & Marcer, 2014; Micheletti, et al., 2015; Cimoli, 2015). The DEMs are accessible through georeferencing the reconstructed 3D models by a set of Ground Control Points (see: 2.2.1.2 Ground Control Points GCP), whether artificial or natural features, because they are available in the topography and thus recognizable in the images. Therefore, the 3D models generated by SfM are set on a local reference system and the georeferencing process will be appointing the real world coordinates to these GCPs. Consequently, the entire model to real-world coordinates, which generates a DEM, will be addressed. The overall SfM workflow applied to earth surfaces reconstruction is clearly illustrated in the next section (1.2.3: DEM and Orthophoto generation)

1.2.3 DEM and orthophoto generation

Terrestrial and aerial Photogrammetry workflow rely on SfM technique using many software such as Agisoft Photoscan Professional, MicMac open-source from Institut Géographique National in France (IGN), SfM-PMVS open-source, ... (Morgan et al., 2016; Brunier et al., 2016). We have chosen Agisoft Photoscan Professional because it integrate

and automates the SfM protocol stages with a user-friendly interface and his price is affordable for academic version (500 \$), in addition of the results flexibility transfer into ArcMap (Brunier al., 2016).

As mentioned by Li et al., (2016):

“Agisoft PhotoScan is a 3D scanning software package developed by the Agisoft Company, Russia. It is an advanced 3D modelling package based on image data processing. It uses the latest 3D reconstruction technology from multiple views which can process any picture taken by a non-metric camera with data ranges from small sculpture to mass data captured from Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV). It can process a series of images to produce a high quality Digital Orthophoto Map (DOM) and Digital Elevation Model (DEM) from which a 3D model can then be built. 3D scenes have wide applications in many fields, such as the protection of cultural relics, industry, archaeology, biology, medicine and some military applications. The advantages and disadvantages of the software are as follows:

(1) Advantages of Agisoft PhotoScan: Agisoft PhotoScan can automatically construct 3D models throughout the whole course without setting initial values and control points and so it is very convenient for users. Photos can be taken at any position and at any angle with only one precondition, that there exist corresponding points between two adjacent pictures of the target. In comparison to constructing 3D models of surface features using a 3D Laser Scanner, this method is highly efficiency and has low cost.

(2) Disadvantages of Agisoft PhotoScan: it requires a high performance computer which is capable of graphics processing. The construction speed of the three-dimensional model depends on the number of photos and other corresponding parameters such as RAM. The larger the amount of processing data, the longer the time to build the three- dimensional model. The accuracy obtained from the above method is lower than that from a 3D Laser Scanner; therefore, a 3D Laser Scanner is still necessary for 3D measurements which require a high level of precision”.

It is important to note, that the workflow could be done with different resolutions (high, moderate, low) which will be tested later in terms of quality and require time. Below,

we briefly described the aspects of the workflow stages and the reconstruction of 3D models that are needed for our study (Agisoft 2015; Cimoli 2015; Brunier et al., 2016):

- Add (stereoscopic) Photos: we start sorting out the pictures (Figure 8) and synchronizing their coordinate's data (Easting, Northing, latitude and accuracy).

Figure 8: Series of captured images before processing

- Align photos is the most important step in the SfM protocol. Agisoft Photoscan algorithm identify match and monitor the movement of the unique object features (Verhoeven, 2011; Javernick et al., 2014; Agisoft, 2015; Brunier et al., 2016). This algorithm reconstruct the optimal picture positions (Figure 9) and improving them with a bundle-adjustment algorithm (Robertson and Cipolla, 2009; Westoby et al., 2012; Verhoeven, 2011; Javernick et al., 2014; Brunier et al., 2016). Here we note that SfM does not require 3D picture locations and orientations, contrary to traditional photogrammetry. However, in our study we have already the pictures coordinates for both of terrestrial and aerial photographs.

Figure 9: alignment photos under agisoft photoscan software

- Build dense cloud: Based on the estimated positions of the picture, the program calculate depth information from the correlation of each pair of images in order to converge later on in a single dense point cloud (Figure 10). The dense point cloud has almost the same density as LiDAR point clouds.

Figure 10: inclined view of obtained dense cloud under agisoft photoscan software

- Build mesh: Photoscan will reconstruct a 3D polygonal mesh that represents the surface of the object (Figure 11), taking into account the dense point cloud (Agisoft, 2015).

Figure 11: inclined view of obtained mesh under agisoft photoscan software

- Build texture: The step aim to provide better visual quality of the final model (Figure 12).

Figure 12: building texture

- Exploiting DEM and orthophoto: In this final stage, it is important to build the DEM and orthomosaic model and then to make the georeferencing basing on the GCPs and then to repeat the process from dense cloud till exporting DEM and Orthophoto.

Finally, SfM photogrammetry implementation, raw data and exported maps consumes a lot of disk space. For curiosity, our project will be consuming a total that exceeds 700 GB, including the pictures (terrestrial and aerial) set and the model generation.

1.3 DEM aligning by Iterative closet points (ICP)

This algorithm is a technique for medicine application (Hill et al., 2001; Nissen et al., 2012) and for computer graphic (Levoy et al., 2000; Nissen et al., 2012). Regarding earth sciences, ICP has been applied for landslide observation and tectonic mapping (Teza et al., 2007; Nissen et al., 2012). ICP algorithm functions, automatically, on subsets of the two corresponding sets (He et al., 2017). For our case, the subsets include only the bare land part. The ICP algorithm aims to minimize the difference between two raster DEMs (figure), for our case: i) reference bare land DEM and ii) slave DEM. The goal is to find a transformation matrix which converts the slave DEM to best match the reference (Pomerleau et al., 2013; Mizinski & Niedzielski 2017). To do this, we use the Ames Stereo Pipeline (ASP) software.

As mentioned by (Shean et al., 2016): “The NASA Ames Stereo Pipeline (ASP) (Broxton et al., 2009; Broxton and Edwards, 2008; Moratto et al., 2010; Shean et al., 2016) was developed by the Intelligent Robotics Group (IRG) at the NASA Ames Research Center with sensor models for NASA planetary missions available from the open source USGS Integrated Software for Imagers and Spectrometers (ISIS) (Anderson, 2008; Shean et al., 2016). The planetary community has used ASP24 for numerous mapping applications (Broxton et al., 2009; Shean et al., 2011; Re et al., 2012; Watters et al., 2015; Fassett, 2016; Shean et al., 2016)”.

When using easting and northing coordinates, both Master DEM and Slave DEM²⁵ are shaved to the common region. Running ICP on the raster at this stage allow us to obtain the matrix transformation. Thus, the transformation matrix convert the snow cover to the right location and orientation. Consequently, we obtain a superposition of Master DEM (Bare

²⁴ Ames Stereo Pipeline software

²⁵ Master DEM: is a reference DEM, based on it the slave DEM will be transformed

land) and slave DEM²⁶ (snow cover) (Figure 13 and Figure 14), which allow us to calculate the volume of the snow cover inside the study area.

Figure 13: ICP fundamental concepts (<https://www.pinterest.co.uk/pin/230246599677100053/>).

Figure 14: Difference between Master and Slave model, here it is illustrated using orthophotos under ArcScene software

²⁶ Slave DEM: is DEM that follow the Master DEM to be well relocated with minimum errors using ICP

1.4 Snow cover shape characteristics

1.4.1 Snow Surface

Snow surface is the area of snow cover (SCA) which represents the separation line between snow cover and the bare land (Figure 15). Sometime the snow cover is not naturally limited by a closed polygon inside the study area; we will make it situated inside a closed polygon (Figure 15). In this case, we close the polygon manually.

Figure 15: Snow cover surface / Orthophotos taken by drone and proceed by Agisoft Photoscan software. Three elements are seen: the bare land, the snow cover and the drawn red line representing the snow cover limit taken into consideration

1.4.2 Height of Snowpack

Height of Snowpack (HS^{27}) is the subtraction of snow cover top elevation value from the bare-land elevation value (Figure 16). This figure present a cross section of the snow cover and the bare land at Jabal El Dib during the day of 4 May 2012. From this figure, it is clear that we have a lot of variability on the HS value along the section. It start from zero

²⁷ Height of snowpack

thickness value and its maximum could be around 15 m in the middle of the sinkhole. It is noticeable that the variability of distribution of HS oblige us to measure the whole of the study area when we aim to estimate the volume (see: 1.4.3 Volume). That why the obtaining of accurate DEM and mapping become imperative.

Figure 16: Cross section at Jabal El Dib area at 4 May 2012 (Abou Chakra 2013)

1.4.3 Snow Volume

Volume represents the quantity of a three-dimensional space that is surrounded by a closed surface. It is quantified in cubic meter. The volume of a container is defined, in general, as its capacity of retention if we are talking about regular shape like cylinder, spheroid, ellipsoid, cone... in our case it is more difficult because we do not have regular forms despite we can note an approximate ellipsoidal form. In addition, the snowfall does not fill the whole of study area with a constant level and HS due to many meteorological and climatic factors (Figure 18).

Consequently, we do not have regular form neither on the bare land nor for the snow cover. Thus, we have to work carefully on field and office to well carry out to most precise and accurate volume for snow cover on each measurement date.

In the present case, two surfaces are needed to obtain volume of snow cover: i) bare land that is considered as fix reference; ii) snow cover, which will change according to meteorological situation. In fact, the DEMs of each surface will be prepared regardless on which approaches were used to obtain it such as total station or Structure from Motion based on terrestrial or aerial photogrammetry. On the calculation methodology, we note principal systems known as “unite area or borrow-pit (pixel by pixel)”.

This method was applied automatically under ArcMap software using “cut and fill” tool:

The Cut Fill tool allows to create a map that is based on two input surfaces before (with and without snow) and after displaying the areas and volumes of surface materials that have been modified by the removal or addition of surface material (Figure 17).

Both input raster surfaces must coincide. In other terms, they must have a common origin, the same number of rows and columns of the cells and the same cell size as well (ArcMap).

Figure 17: Volume calculation concept (ArcGIS Desktop 10.5 help)

To evaluate snow volume in the sinkhole it is necessary to measure the quantity of snow between the bare land and the snow top surface for a constrained area. The bare land Digital Elevation Model (DEM) is required. The snow top surface has to be measured and the difference provides the volume (Figure 18).

Figure 18: 3D Section in a volumetric model. Snow cover at Jabal El Dib, 4 May 2012 (EarthVision®: petroleum suite; software by Dynamic Graphics, Inc., Alameda, CA, USA).

1.5 Conclusion

All the theoretical approaches used in this study have been here defined and explained as the difficulty of HS determination due to the variability of snow distribution. Moreover, different techniques for constructing DEM by i) random points, ii) SfM and Iterative closest point algorithm have been identified. Besides, we explained the snow shape characteristics like Snow surface, HS, and snow volume. Thus, the required method has been introduced. Consequently, we will then move to the next chapters in order to explain the methodology used and the results obtained.

Chapter 2: Instrumentation and methodology

2.1 Instrumentations and tools

As mentioned in the objectives, this thesis aims at monitoring snow cover with high precision. Suitable equipment and methodology are required. Measurement will be based on Total Station, terrestrial and aerial and photogrammetry. Basic information about instruments and tools used in the study are provided in the coming paragraphs.

2.1.1 Total Station

Total stations have been until now one of the main tools used for high precision and accuracy surveying practice, including topography, hydrography, construction, geography, hydrology (Lavine et al., 2003; Ghilani, 2012).

Three main components contribute to the success of total station instruments: Electronic Distance Measuring (EDM²⁸) instrument, electronic horizontal and vertical angle (Figure 19) and computer or microprocessor for automatic immediate calculation (Wagner, 2015). Thus, horizontal and vertical distance components may arise and result in a Liquid Crystal Display (LCD²⁹). Data may be preserved consequently on board or in external data collectors (Milles et Lagofun, 1999; Lavine et al., 2003; Mills and Braber, 2004; Schofield et Breach, 2007; Ghilani, 2012; Abou chakra, 2013; Arango and Morales, 2015).

²⁸ Electronic Distance Measuring

²⁹ Liquid Crystal Display

Figure 19: Total Station (Abou Chakra, 2013)

Connected to a computer, the total station resulted efficient in many engineering and environment applications as mentioned above. However, the total station, with the numerous progresses in Geographical Information Systems (GIS), was considered one of the most recognizable environment applications (Lavine et al., 2003). In addition, it is important to note that total station have been used to validate the accuracy of United States Geological Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) (Webber, 1995, Lavine et al., 2003).

No doubt, 2D or 3D surveying and data collection are applicable with the total stations (Figure 20) (Milles et Lagofun, 1999; Lavine et al., 2003; Schofield et Breach, 2007; Ghilani, 2012; Abou chakra, 2013); In fact, the total station is positioned on a tripod, while it is first leveled with a bubble level. Then comes the accuracy with the electronic levelling in the instrument, contributing this way to the calibration of the level limits within a 360° circle. In our study, total station is indispensable to achieve snow cover and bare land accurate DEM. In addition, it is very useful for preparing the pilot site especially in measuring the geodetics network and Ground Controls Points (GCPs). Similarly, Total station will be the main instrument for validation Snow cover DEM obtained by terrestrial and aerial photogrammetry. Measurements were taken with many total stations (Figure 21); i) Leica TS06; ii) Ruide rts-862r; iii) Pentax R-1505N. The reason to test many Total Station is to assess its efficiency while using the reflector-less signal (laser) on the snow cover surface; because we do not have enough information about the performance of this signal on wet surface like snow cover.

Figure 20: Concept of 3D measurements (<https://www.slideshare.net/mirafhahira/sokkia-cx-seriesbrochuresok1008revbsm>)

Figure 21: The used Total station machine for this thesis

2.1.2 GPS receiver

Surveying and geomatics took another aspect since the Global Positioning System (GPS) saw the light on civil people hand. It is based on the signals that are transmitted from satellites and is used for global navigation and guidance (Figure 22). With this new technology operating day and night, rain or shine, precise timing and positioning information can be obtained from any accessible point on Earth, getting through reliable and low-cost results. It is really a revolutionary step in conventional surveying procedures (Ghilani, 2012).

For that purpose, we used differential GPS (i.e. base and rover) because single receiver cannot provide the required level of performance (Bento et al., 2017).

Figure 22: GPS Segment (<https://pdhonline.com/courses/l116/l116content.htm>).

Speed, low cost, productivity and enough accuracy are essential to success. In this field, we point on two mode of GPS measurement: a) static and kinematic mode. GPS Static mode is used for very high geodetic network measurement and known by his long time procedure and its high cost; b) Kinematic or Real Time Kinematic (RTK³⁰) GPS mode is the most productive surveying form in GPS, because it relies on relative positioning techniques and it is enough for our work in term of precision and accuracy (Guo et al., 2016; Capuano et al., 2017; Paraforos et al., 2017). Thus, instant values to the coordinates of points can be obtained whether the receiver is stationary or in motion because it is importantly accurate and adequate for many of the surveys like bench marks and snow cover measuring. It is

³⁰ Real Time Kinematic

applied in various surveying areas like mapping, construction, geography, hydrology, environment...

Accurate and immediate results are obtained with Real-time kinematic (RTK) mode; in fact, kinematic GPS has known a great success in positioning sounding containers during hydrographic surveys and aerial cameras during photogrammetric surveys, even though it was in motion (Figure 23).

Figure 23: GPS field of work (<https://www.indiamart.com/bsgeotech/global-positioning-system.html>).

Kinematic survey engages two receivers (Figure 24) in order to collect the required observations from two stations. The first one occupies a station of known position, while the second collects data on the points of interest.

Figure 24: Relative and RTK GPS system (<https://canadiangis.com/guidelines-for-real-time-kinematic-rtk-surveying.php>.
modified by Charbel Abou Chakra

We will be using GPS to verify benchmarks (see: 2.2.1.1 benchmarks network) points calculated by total station; hence, the measurement of ground control points GCPs (see: 2.2.1.2 Ground Control Points) in addition of the creation of benchmarks points far away from geodetic point in term of distance and visibility issues.

2.1.3 Digital cameras

Considered as fieldwork equipment, digital cameras have been extensively used in order to obtain digital elevation models and orthophotos. It is a revolution of making 3D model from taking pictures with stereoscopic overlap (Westoby et al., 2012; Morgan et al., 2016; Agisoft 2016; Balhuer-Puig et al., 2017; Mertes et al., 2017).

In our study, it is important to highlight the primordial role of digital cameras in obtaining orthophotos and DEMs. With time-lapse photography, digital cameras were the main tools used for automatic observation of the snow cover in the study area (Figure 25). We fixed 3 cameras (see: 2.2.1.3 Installing steady cameras) Canon PowerShot A1400 cameras, with a resolution of 4608x3456, a focal length of 5mm, and a pixel size that is equal to $1.34 \times 1.34 \mu\text{m}$. After programming, these cameras monitor automatically their field of view. They took pictures-automatically on a daily basis of the snow cover changes as the firm shrinkage, during the melting season in particular.

Figure 25: Three steady cameras with example of their field of view

2.1.4 Flying camera (UAV)

An unmanned aerial vehicle UAV, commonly called drone, is an aircraft without a human pilot aboard (Cimoli, 2015). Drones are relatively small flying vehicles that are controlled remotely via manual or automated mode. The flight of UAVs can be autonomous somehow because it is controlled either remotely by human operator or autonomously by onboard GPS computers (Brunier et al., 2016; Clark et al., 2017).

In comparison with manned aircraft, the initial use of UAVs was for "dull, dirty or dangerous" missions for humans. However, they were mostly used in military applications, and they were rapidly expanding to commercial, scientific, recreational, agricultural, and other applications, such as policing, and surveillance, product deliveries, agriculture, remote sensing, aerial photography and photogrammetry (Marzolff and Poesen, 2009; Marzolff et al., 2011; d'Oleire-Oltmanns et al., 2012; Eltner et al., 2015; James et al., 2016).

We are interested in photogrammetry approaches. In fact, photogrammetry-using UAV can deliver larger territory comparing to GPS and total station (Arango and Morales, 2015). In addition, they can give accurate datasets, while they are easy to obtain and low cost platforms (Cimoli 2015; James et al., 2016; Cimoli et al., 2017). It is important to remark that UAV has been extensively used in the last decades in order to get Digital Elevation Models earth topographic variations (Marzolff and Poesen, 2009; Delacourt et al., 2009; Marzolff et al., 2011; d'Oleire-Oltmanns et al., 2012; Harwin and Lucieer, 2012; Goncalves and Henriques, 2015; Eltner et al., 2015; James et al., 2016; Doumit, 2018), and to monitor snow cover in particular (Che et al., 2011; Whitehead et al., 2013; Immerzeel et al., 2014; Cimoli 2015; Nolan et al., 2015; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Mertes et al., 2017; Cimoli et al., 2017).

In our fieldwork by UAV, we used a "Phantom DJI" (Figure 26). Deeper information about the specification is provided in (Appendix 6). This aircraft is equipped with a built-in camera of 12 megapixels, with an autonomous 17-minutes fly for each fully charged battery.

Figure 26: Phantom III Advance picture during flight mission at Jabal El Dib on March 17th 2017. (Photograph by Elias Abou Chakra)

2.1.5 Geodetic points

Geodetic point is a point we use in order to make it a constant point of reference in any topographical work. In general, it compose with the benchmark network (see: 2.2.1.1 benchmark network), the link between the map and the earth. In Lebanon, the coordinates of the geodetic point are metric and three-dimensional. They also have a relation with latitude and longitude lines, which mean geographic coordinates (Brabant, 2003)

The geodetic points are created by triangulation of topographical operations. We can distinguish the geodetic points according to their accuracy and degree, from the first degree, which is the most accurate one, and to the fifth grade for the less accurate. The sets of these points represent the National Geodetic Network.

At a historical point in Lebanon, the establishment of the geodetic points start in 1920 with Colonel Perrier, head of the geographical division of the French army at that time. It was then agreed that Syria and Lebanon would be projected on one projection system because both countries were under the French Mandate and having an area and geography that permit it (Duraffourd 1930).

In this thesis, geodetic points were the principal elements to obtain benchmarks networks (Figure 27) (see: 2.2.1.1 benchmark network) and then obtain the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of bare land and the different snow cover stages. As source of the geodetic points, we rely on the geodetic network released by the Directorate of Geographic Affairs of the Lebanese Army” (DAG³¹) (Figure 28). The table below shows the used geodetic points in this study (Table 1).

Figure 27: a) GPS rover on GE3N; b) GPS base on CCQU; c) Total station on CCQU. (Photograph from left to right by Ralph KHOURY HANNA, Charbel ABOU CHAKRA and Janine SOMMA)

Points	Easting	North	Orthometric height	Ellipsoidal height
CCQU	-304211.25	-19386.18	2307.62	2334.4359
GD36	-302093.29	-15943.15	2080.15	2106.9660
GE3N	-300289.3	-15691.73	2076.65	2103.4660

Table 1: Geodetic points coordinates

³¹ Direction des affaires géographiques

مقدم الطلب:		لائحة إحداثيات نقاط جيودازية			الجمهورية اللبنانية وزارة الدفاع الوطني قيادة الجيش أركان الجيش للتجهيز مديرية الشؤون الجغرافية	
شماريل أو شفرة						
وحدة الاستخدام: أعمال مساحة						
منطقة: حيون السيمان العقارية						
		المسند: برقية رقم ١٤٤١٤/ت ج / (داري تاريخ ٢٠٠٧/٥/٢٨ إعصال مالي: رقم: ٢٧٦٣٧ تاريخ: ٨ / ١١ / ٢٠١٢			رقم: ٤٤٩٩ / ت ج / ح	
ملاحظات	الإرتفاع (Ellipsoid Height)	الإرتفاع (عن سطح البحر)	الإحداثيات المستويين جغرافية		الدرجة	إسم النقطة
			Y(m)	X(m)		
تستعمل في الأماكن التي تم كياها لل تاريخ ٢٠٠٢/٧/٨ مع التحفظ.	-----	2307.62	-19386.18	-304211.25	3	CCQU
تستعمل في الأماكن التي تم كياها قبل تاريخ ٢٠٠٢/٧/٨ مع التحفظ.	2334.4359	-----	-19386.18	-304211.25	3	CCQU
لا يجوز الاستفادة من هذه النقاط خارج وجهة الاستخدام المذكورة أعلاه. تستعمل الإفادة الأصلية فقط أو نسخة عنها مصادقة من مديرية الشؤون الجغرافية. يمنع نسخ أو طبع أو بيع هذه الإفادة. كل مخالفة تعرض مرتكبيها لأحكام القانون رقم ٦٥/٤٢ الصادر عام ١٩٦٥.						
عاريًا في ٢٠١٢/١١/٨ مدير الشؤون الجغرافية بالوكالة العميد والى حافظوم		رئيس قسم الحسابات الملازم الأول المهندس علي درويش		منظم لائحة الإحداثيات زياد البغدادي		

Figure 28: Sample of given Coordinate from DAG

2.2 Measurements methodology

It is vital to get real and true information on HS and its spatial distribution to estimate the snow cover volume (Abou Chakra et al., 2016). Evaluation of snow spatial distribution and HS at high resolution always presents a challenge. Latest investigations show that it is possible to find the accurate mapping of HS (Deems et al., 2013; Melvold and Skaugen, 2013). Nevertheless, covering larger zones are still extremely expensive (Bühler et al., 2012; Bühler et al., 2015). Today, it is easily possible to automatically monitor and estimate HS using AWS³² (Fayad et al., 2017). On the other hand, the weakness of this method is that the measurements are only taken on one specific location (Abou Chakra et al., 2018). Therefore, this methodology is limited to present flat sites and is not able to capture the high spatial variability of the HS distribution (Bründl et al., 2004; Egli, 2008; Bühler et al., 2015). Also, it is feasible to successfully perform constant and precise snow mapping by using laser scanning (Prokop, 2008; Grünewald et al., 2010), knowing that the accuracy of such measurements will be almost excellent. Nevertheless, this method has still a relatively high-cost and can only cover limited areas.

In the last decade, many experiments have been applied on snow cover using digital cameras. Very few studies have been relying on single digital use in order to detect the snow variation using time lapse photography like Revuelto et al., (2016). However, there is no study available that used this technique for 3D automatic monitoring for snow cover. Conversely, many studies have been relying on flying cameras (UAV) instrument (Bühler et al., 2015; Nolan et al., 2015; Mertes et al., 2017; Cimoli et al., 2017). In this context, SfM algorithm became very useful for DEM and orthophoto generation.

Giving overview about SfM studies, the accuracy of SfM point clouds has been analyzed and showed good concordance by using 3D data attained with TLS as benchmark (James and

³² Automatic Weather Station

Robson, 2012; Kaiser et al., 2014; Smith and Vericat, 2015; Balaguer-Puig et al., 2017). Moreover, Carrivick et al. (2016) published a detailed analysis of the SfM technology, advantages and disadvantages, and its application to geosciences. Fonstad et al. (2013) presented a specific description of the method and implemented it to get a 3D model of a river area from low-altitude aerial images with results that are comparable to Lidar surveys. Other studies used the SfM methodology in the laboratory (Nouwakpo et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2017), at different scales (James and Robson, 2012; Gómez-Gutiérrez et al., 2014; Doumit et al., 2018) to calculate terrain roughness parameters in small plots (Bretar et al., 2013; Snapir et al., 2014) and on snow cover (Cimoli, 2017; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Cimoli et al., 2017). Those efforts showed that it is of good benefit to use SfM photogrammetric with advantages of ease use, flexibility and low cost (Balaguer-Puig et al., 2017). In addition, it is functional at small scales (Balaguer-Puig et al., 2017) or large ones (Doumit, 2018).

However, while using this technique, the question about its validity and accuracy arise. For that purpose we will focus in our observation on using steady and flying cameras to capture the snow cover and to use total station in two ways: i) validating the measurement taken by terrestrial and aerial photogrammetry and ii) making systematic and continuous monitoring when circumstances dictate even for wind speed or breakdown of steady cameras. In addition, we will use ICP algorithm to relocate the DEM obtained from time-lapse photogrammetry system.

In the coming paragraphs we will be explaining the steps from preparing the study area till monitoring the snow cover using the three approaches used in this thesis i) Total Station; ii) Time lapse photogrammetry and; iii) aerial photogrammetry using UAV.

2.2.1 Study area preparation

As the purpose was snow cover volume estimation and so on, the evolution and variability of snow cover surface the preparation of the study areas was the fundamental part of the fieldwork. This preparation included equipment, steady cameras installation,

preparing the site for topographic monitoring to create a geodetic network, painting the ground control points (GCPs) on the ground and bare land modeling.

2.2.1.1 Benchmark network

Benchmark is composition of two words: bench and mark. In surveying, a benchmark is a reference point; based on it we can measure other points. It is a permanent mark established at a known position and elevation (X, Y and Z) used as the basis for measuring the elevation and location of other topographical features (<http://www.mckayassociatesllc.com>). The group of benchmark points make the benchmark network. In surveying, benchmark is generated by topographic operation and calculation that begin from geodetic points (see: 2.1.5 geodetic points). Actually, benchmark points are measured by total station or GPS device depending on logistic situation such as meteorological condition, attendance of buildings, visibility and distance between study area and the nearest geodetic points. In fact, benchmarks are the most accurate links between maps and ground and are very important for well orienting and locating the maps (Milles et Lagofun, 1999; Schofield et Breach, 2007; Ghilani, 2012; Abou Chakra, 2013).

The field work procedure change between GPS and total station. When using GPS, one geodetic point is enough to start measurement and obtain tridimensional coordinates (X, Y and Z) for new points. It is the case in the two areas of this research. While, using total station two known coordinates points are necessary to obtain planimetric coordinates (x and Y), but one point could be enough to obtain the Z value for any new point (Milles et Lagofun, 1999; Brabant, 2003; Ghilani, 2012; Abou Chakra, 2013). Thus, the basics are achievable for starting a survey, because the focal points are prepared along with their three-dimensional positions X, Y, and Z either by total station or by GPS device.

Benchmark network was prepared for each study area: a) Jabal el dib; b) Bou Mechleh.

a) Jabal el Dib: At the first stage, a total station and aerial imagery were used to extract the coordinates of the chairlift small buildings to use them as benchmarks. We proceeded like this way in order to do less costly operations, calculations and topographic measurements. However, when decided to enlarge the original study area (pilot sinkhole), it

was necessary to measure the coordinates more accurately. That is why a GPS receiver was used (see: 2.1.2 GPS receiver) to make sure that the maps were well located.

b) Chiaab bou mechleh: At Chiaab Bou Mechleh the situation was different, because some of the geodetic points are far away from the study area (more than 1 km), so we relied on GPS from the beginning to create the geodetic network.

Measurements done by GPS for both of the study areas were based on real time kinematic (RTK) mode. Actually, the base receiver was fixed on a geodetic point and then we move with the rover receiver to make the measurement on the other station marks that were painted on the ground. We have also been alerted to the use of both the ellipsoid and geoid elevation so that for the future, it will be possible to compare the elevations based on many datum.

2.2.1.2 Ground control points (GCPs)

GCPs are permanent or temporal marks putted on the ground, provided with their dimension visibility from sensor of observation. From satellite, GCP could be road or building and from terrestrial or flying camera, it is a mark (Milles et Lagofun, 1999; Schofield et Breach, 2007; Ghilani, 2012; Abou Chakra et al., 2016). GCPs are the fundamental element for success the georeferencing that is a main part of topographic surveys (Wang et al., 2012; James et al., 2016). In fact, GCPs adjust the distorted points cloud that related to the radial lens distortion (James and Robson, 2014; Balaguer-Puig et al., 2017).

GCPs were measured by total Station and GPS (Figure 29), and they are considered as benchmark network for the both of study area (Jabal El Dib and Bou Mechleh). Those GCPs were the main element for well orienting the orthophotos and DEMs obtained from UAV and steady cameras. For this study, the GCPs were painted on the ground and rocks to be able to calibrate the obtained 3D of models (DSM) models.

Figure 29: Measurement of GCPs coordinates by a) GPS device and; b) total station (Photographed by Ralph KHOURY HANNA and Charbel ABOU CHAKRA)

2.2.1.2.1 Ground control points for steady cameras

One of the important and innovative approach in this study is the daily and automatic snow cover monitoring a time-lapse photogrammetry system (i.e. steady camera). That experience was done just for the sinkhole located at Jabal El Dib. For this scope, we could not install the GCPs perfectly. This is due to geometry of the studied sinkhole, the snow accumulation and melting and because the observation was done by inclined images. We were obliged to proceed by inclined images because it was impossible to fix cameras horizontally and observe the whole study area. The elevation of cameras above the ground is 2 m, so we were obliged to give to the cameras an inclined orientation to capture a maximum of area. That is why, many tests were made to choose the best GCP's distribution (see: 2.2.3.3.2 a Test GCPs number and geometric distribution). The (Figure 30) show clearly the final distribution of GCPs (see more details are in 3.2.2.2 Permanent GCPs on the bare land).

Figure 30: GCPs distribution facing the time-lapse cameras system

2.2.1.2.2 Ground control points for UAV

The UAVs used were DJI Phantoms (see: Appendix 6). Those Drones are not equipped by sufficient quality GNSS in terms of accurate position. That is why the use of ground control points is highly recommended (Abdullah et al., 2013; James et al., 2016; Mizinski & Niedzielski 2017). GCPs must be measured accurately to obtain tridimensional coordinates and must be observed by total station or differential GPS to achieve a centimetric accuracy (Brunier et al., 2016; Aguera-Vega et al., 2016). The GCPs coordinates painted on Chiaab bou Mechleh (Figure 33) were surveyed by GNSS, while at Jabal el Dib (Figure 32) GCPs were measured using total station and GPS to make a test of compatibility between each of them. Each target of 70*70 cm was painted with different colors (Figure 31). GCPs are well distributed on the two-study area; they were painted on hard rock when it was possible.

Figure 31: Ground control points (GCPs) painted on Bou Mechleh and Jabal El Dib areas (Photograph by Charbel ABOU CHAKRA)

Jabal El Dib

Figure 32: The GCPs distribution at Jabal El Dib

Bou Mechleh

Figure 33: The GCPs distribution at Bou Mechleh

2.2.1.3 Steady camera installation

Monitoring of snowpack using time-lapse photogrammetry required the installation of steady cameras by providing sufficient stereoscopic overlap. For that, three issues have to be taken into consideration three issues: i) system's reinforcement structure; ii) position of camera (XYZ) and iii) electronics and configuration system. This system will be very useful in harsh conditions and it will require only minimal maintenance (Kepski et al., 2015).

- i) Because the study area was empty of vertical fixed features we were obliged to create a fix column with good reinforcement in order to be able to resist the harsh weather conditions, like speed winds and frozen snow during storm and low temperatures. The digital cameras were installed on fixed galvanized columns 2 m height (Figure 34 and Figure 35).

Figure 34: steps of cameras reinforcement installation system (Photograph by Janine SOMMA and Charbel ABOU CHAKRA)

Figure 35: Structure of the cameras installation and professional electronic engineer (Pascal Fanise) during the installation

- ii) In such area, we have to get a wild knowledge about snow cover accumulation behavior in this sinkhole. Indeed, the snow cover could vary between 0 to 15 meter of HS (see: 1.4.2 Height of Snowpack). This heterogeneity of snow distribution is due to the land shape (sinkhole) and the dominant wind direction, inducing the formation of a snow cornice (see: Study area). Consequently, the line of cameras has to be parallel to the major axe of the sinkhole, facing to the cornice and the snow patch.

Time-lapse photogrammetry is useful to obtain 3D model of snow cover. Therefore, it is not a simple photography. Consequently, the distance between each steady camera has to be taken into consideration to obtain sufficient overlap especially because working with inclined images. Thus, and after testing many different distances and after few Agisoft processing, it was decided that a 5m of approximate spacing between each pole with about 40 degrees angle for each camera toward the study area. With its concave shape terrain, this sinkhole offers excellent possibilities to install and cover the study area with the time lapse photogrammetry system because its exposed slope make easy to monitor the snow cover variation on this area (Figure 36).

Figure 36: The study area geometry and stereoscopic overlap

- iii) To favor lightning condition of the scene, it was decided and programmed to take photos three times per day at local time: 8:00, 10:00 and 12:00h; or 9:00, 11:00 and 1:00.

2.2.1.4 Bare land modeling, Master plan

The snow volume is calculated by comparing the DEM of bare land and the DEM of the snow cover for each monitoring day. In fact, the observation was done by comparing the snow height on each point or pixel of the study area. Consequently, providing the DEM of bare land reference surface for volume calculation became imperative. For Jabal el Dib (Figure 37), bare land DEM's data was surveyed by total station, steady cameras and UAV. The bare land of Chiaab bou Mechleh (Figure 38) was surveyed by UAV.

Jabal El Dib

Figure 37: Hillshade of Jabal El Dib site

Bou Mechleh

Figure 38: Hillshade of Bou Mechleh site

2.2.2 Snow cover monitoring by total station

We mentioned in the literature review (see: problematic/ rational) that the studies done by [Abou Chakra \(2013\)](#) and [Elali \(2014\)](#), were based on snowmelt monitoring during melting season using a total station. The target of this part is the continuation of those latest studies. However, we are looking forward to improve the technique and increase the temporal resolution. In fact, the basic difference between these two studies and the recent is the time interval between each dates of survey. Measurement was taken with an interval of 3 to 4 weeks in 2012 and 2013; while in the recent study, i.e. in 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018 the temporal resolution was between 7 and 15 days. It is important also to mention that during the fieldwork, i.e. in 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018 the total station was mainly used for validating coordinate measurements taken by other instruments (UAV and Steady cameras). In fact, while the generation the Snow DEMs based on UAV and steady cameras observation, we validate its accuracy and precision using total station measurements.

The basis for this approach is to work on DEMs building and maps for different dates for the years: 2012, 2013, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018. Those maps and DEMS show: the shape, the height and limits of the snow cover through different dates. The latter will be using to extract other results such as the calculation of snow quantities and HS, how does it melt (speed), and the behavior of snow cover decreasing in term of surface, volume and HS ([Abou Chakra, 2013](#); [Elali, 2014](#)).

This approach was applied just on “Jabal el Dib” area (see: study area). Generally, the work was divided into field and office work.

2.2.2.1 Field work

Let us assume that each time we make the topographic survey it represent the snow cover for this specific date. In this part, we used Total Station: i) Leica TS06; ii) Ruide rts-862r; iii) Pentax R-1505N (see: 2.1.1 Total Station). Each time we make the survey, we measure manually all the details which can give us the correct representation of the snow cover;

likewise, exhibiting the limits of snow and the shape of its cover, the slopes, concavity and cornice (Figure 39).

Before any topographic survey, we have to proceed by different steps:

- Firstly, we start by discovering the area and its snow cover changes. This step is very important because it allows to know how we can move with the holding equipment and to have a general strategic plan to start the topographic survey (Abou Chakra, 2013; Elali, 2014). The tour also gave us an idea of the contents of the map that we will be creating and the shape and access to the right representation of the snow cover. By drone and camera, we also take pictures for the land with all its details to distinguish the general view in each date.

- Secondly, we have to choose the best location for the total station installation and direction. All of this depends on the quantities of snow, its height, the cornice location, and how it is distributed within the study area. Choosing the best location for total station installation is considered as basis for covering the largest number of points using minimum number of stations. In fact, the most revealing point on the study area is the optimal one to install the total station if it is not too far, i.e. 200 to 250 m at most. Then, we oriented the total station using Resection or free station³³ operation, based on the geodetic point "CCQU" and a point that Abou Chakra (2013) has created and called A2.

All of these stages are essential before starting any topographic survey. After installing and orienting total station, we started to define the limits of the snow cover (Firn limit). We obtain a closed line representing the limits of the snow cover by each date (figure). The collected points measured with Total Station allow drawing a closed line that is given the attribute "L" for "Limit". We note that on some dates, the limits we draw are not the correct limits (See: 1.4.1 Snow Surface). Actually, they are natural on both sides and virtual on the

³³ Method for determining an unknown position (X,Y & Z) measuring angles with respect to known positions. Measurements can be made Theodolite or with a total station using known points of a Geodetic network or landmarks of a map

remaining two sides. This happens if the snow cover is still covering the sinkhole interfluvium without forming a closed line within the study area, which obliged us to take two virtual lines and combine them with the natural limit of the snow cover.

Now, we have reached the most important stages. We will start to represent the terrain. Any topographic map cannot be considered as completed if the three dimensions XYZ do not exist. In fact, we create a fictive grid of points (figure 39). It is important to create a topography map centered on a considered number of points in the study area, i.e. the map that should be created. Works and measurements must be very detailed, so that all details can be taken, especially when there are any curve changes in the shape of the terrain. More we increase the number of surveyed points, more we obtain a representative DEM (Figure 39). In another meaning, more the surveyed points are close to each other, more we get an accurate map and resembling to the reality. In our case, we considered 5 to 10 meters the distance interval between points with decreasing distance when we have curved or elliptical shape. We also need to observe the measured points in terms of their presence on the snow cover or on the bare land (Figure 39).

It should also be noted that we took the measurements by either using the laser (reflectorless) with or using the prism reflector, depending on the geometric condition. Although, the measurement-using reflector prism is more accurate, most of the observation was done using laser. We used the laser in order to save time because it is difficult to move on the snow cover in addition of the risk when we face the hard slopes on the snow cover. The Laser allows us to cover the area with largest number of point's survey within minimum of time. Reflector prism is used when we do not have perpendicular intersection between laser signal and surface of target (Figure 39).

Figure 39: a) Total station; b) random points and survey

2.2.2.2 Office work and data processing

While working in the field, each point measured by the total station include: point number, point descriptor (code), prism height, horizontal and vertical angles, distance, Northing y, Easting E, and elevation Z and all these elements will be saved in memory (Lavine et al., 2003). Because total station make automatically the calculation, we were interested on Point number, Easting, Northing, elevation and code. Code is keys to now characterize what we are observing on site (limit, snow bare land).

In order to observe the points shown, we have called the points as follows:

S: point of snow; TN: point of bare land; L: limit snow cover; M: wall of cornice

When the stage of field collection is done, data is downloaded from the total station into software. Then, generating reports in a table format, which contain the raw data, and X, Y, Z coordinates for each point. After separating the files, they should be converted from a “.TXT” format, to a “shapefile” format. Then, data is transferred into a ArcMap to obtain raster elevation (Figure 40). (Lavine et al., 2003; Ghilani, 2012; Abou Chakra, 2013). Thus, we can start the cartography.

Cartography is the science of maps and conversion from digital information into graphical information and forms that can be geometric sometimes. The cartography in our work included the process of drawing the limits between the snow and the ground in each date and terrain mapping. The extracted maps could be “Raster and Vector”. In this stage, we used all the points surveyed to extract map and Digital elevation model. In addition to the drawing of the sections, we used to calculate the quantities and identify HS. With a sufficient data to generate a 3D surface model, it can be transferred into software that intercalates a 3D surface based on TIN surface (Ghilani, 2012).

At any orientation, profiles can be rapidly generated through all surfaces or selected surfaces in order to help setting a structural interpretation. Data, which are easily transferable into software packages, are also integrated into solid 3D geologic models Earth Vision software to better understand the HS variation and melting behavior.

Figure 40: steps to obtain raster DEM from shape points (Abou Chakra et al., 2016)

2.2.3 Snow cover observation with time lapse steady camera

Recently, time-lapse photography in environmental studies has been used increasingly, even for snow dynamic monitoring in small and medium-sized catchments (Garvelmann et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2015; Revuelto et al., 2016). Time-lapse photography is a new technique that is not expensive, a tool that can be implemented easily for snow monitoring in mountain environments (Parajka et al., 2012; Revuelto et al., 2016). Before the study of Revuelto et al., (2016) high-resolution snowpack reconstruction in small-scale study area was not been directly implemented. Various parameters, including the daily Snow Covered Area (SCA) and the first snow melting that happened after peak snow accumulation (Revuelto et al., 2016) are taken from the previous mentioned information. However, further spatial analyses become feasible if the images can be orthorectified and georeferenced (Kepski et al., 2017).

Although, it is easily possible to get Snow Covered Area (SCA) and other continuous information in an automatic way (Revuelto et al., 2016; Kepski et al., 2017), however, it is not simple to obtain automatically either DEMs or volume of snow cover. In this context, photogrammetry is a frequently accepted technique used to get spatial datasets aiming to DEMs building and then calculating the volume (Lowe, 2004; Morgan et al., 2016; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Balaguer-Puig et al., 2017).

In the last decade, photogrammetry has widely used SfM technique in order to obtain (3D) modelling (Snavely et al., 2007; Vasuki et al., 2014; Brunier et al., 2016; Aguera-Vega et al., 2016; James et al., 2016; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Balaguer-Puig et al., 2017; Cimoli et al., 2017). SfM techniques have been widely implemented in many applications (Westoby et al., 2012; Fonstad et al., 2013; Micheletti et al., 2015; Morgan et al., 2016). In addition, Mertes et al., (2017), in a recent study, used essentially SfM for having benefits from oblique images resulting from the study of glacier changing. The user can then apply a 3D transformation to the point cloud so that the cloud is scaled and referenced in a specific local reference system.

In addition of photogrammetry, we need an approach for the automatic coregistration of DEMs and orthophotos. For this issue, Iterative closest point's algorithm (ICP) became

popular in the last decades in order to find rigid transformation between 3D point clouds (Suominen et Gotchev, 2013).

The novelty part of this work, is combining time-lapse photography with SfM photogrammetry and ICP (see: 1.3 DEM aligning by Iterative Closest Points) in order to get snow cover DEMs and orthophotos changes according to the snow process behavior. Those DEMs and orthophotos will be validated in terms of accuracy and precision by total station measurements.

An automatic time-lapse cameras system has been installed (see: 2.2.1.3 Installation of steady cameras) next to the summit of Jabal El Dib (see: study area) overlooking the pilot sinkhole at Jabal El Dib. These systems are appropriate because they require minimal maintenance. In addition, the continuous activity of the automatic weather station at Jabal El dib provides an excellent climatological background for further correlation with different DEMs of snow cover.

As general workflow, the cameras take automatically images on a daily basis. It capture the images, three times per day. This allows selecting the best ones for every day. As for the processing of images, we wish to proceed by a multiple tests. Those processing will be done by SfM and ICP algorithm using Agisoft photoscan and Ames Stereo Pipeline (ASP) software.

2.2.3.1 Field work

The precise coordinates X, Y and Z of the cameras (Figure 41 and Table 2) and GCPs are highly required. We measured their accurate position by total station (see: 2.1.1 Total Station) and their approximate orientations (Table 2 and Figure 41: Steady cameras location). The automation system of capturing the images is the main advantage of this experience. After installing the system and painting the Ground control points GCPs, (see: 2.2.1.3 Steady Cameras Installation & 2.2.1.2.1 Ground Control Points), it remain the maintenance to be sure that the system works without any problem due to storms or any others conditions.

Figure 41: Steady cameras location

Figure 42: Approximate camera orientation measurements (photograph by Elias ABOU CHAKRA)

Camera	Easting	Northing	Elevation	Precision	Yaw	Pitch	Roll
Camera 1	-304176.83	-19307.97	2327.2	0.1	196	20	0
Camera 2	-304178.05	-19302.32	2327.26	0.1	200	20	0
Camera 3	-304180.03	-19297.41	2327.14	0.1	199	20	0

Table 2: Cameras coordinates and approximate orientation (yaw, pitch and Roll).

2.2.3.2 Acquisition and preparation of the images

In March 2015, images started to be acquired by an automatic system. The system kept working automatically until the snow cover disappears in the summer (Figure 43: Series of daily captured pictures with time-lapse system). In fact, it was working until mid-July. Data acquisition was downloaded weekly from the site or each two weeks.

A selection from the data set of daily images is being made, a single daily image (if available due to the meteorological conditions) from each camera. The better time for favorable lightening condition was between 8 am to 1 pm. The system has three sequences of images taken at local time: (8:00, 10:00 and 12:00; or 9:00, 11:00 and 13:00). While the selection of daily images, we have chosen, the same time for all the cameras because they register in the same radiometric conditions.

Figure 43: Series of daily captured pictures with time-lapse system

2.2.3.3 Data processing

We selected Agisoft Photoscan Professional software to create orthophoto and DEMs because they integrate all the SfM protocol stages with a user-friendly interface (see: 1.2.3 DEM and orthophoto Generation). In addition of Agisoft Photoscan, we used Ames stereo Pipeline software (ASP), it allows an automatic Iterative Closest Point (ICP) to extract automatically orientation of DEMs with minimum of means errors and standard deviation. The procedure is based on similitude operations by reducing absolute vertical and horizontal errors (Suominen and Gotchev 2013; Shean et al., 2016; He et al., 2017) (see: 1.3 DEM aligning by Iterative closest points).

Images were selected and imported into Agisoft photoscan software. They were captured on a daily basis. However, the processing was done for some selected days that match the same dates of manual observation taken by total station (see: 2.2.2 Snow cover monitoring by total station). Hence, the aim of this thesis part is the validation of the best method between: processing under Agisoft photoscan without using of GCPs; processing under Agisoft photoscan taking to consideration GCPs and processing based on ICP algorithm.

2.2.3.3.1 Processing without GCPs

In photogrammetry, we could obtain acceptable results without need of GCPs, with condition of having accurate coordinates for the center of the taken images and parameters orientation IMU³⁴ (yaw, pitch and roll) (Figure 44) (Irschara et al., 2010; Gabrlik, 2015 ;Krsal et al., 2016; Morgan et al., 2016; Mizinski and Niedzielski, 2017). That is why we want to

³⁴ Inertial Measurement Unit

benefit from the accurate position and orientation of the cameras obtained by total station with a centimetric to millimetric precision.

Figure 44: Camera orientation (<http://www.kerschhofer.net/ptguide/01.htm>).

After importing the daily images, we proceeded by Agisoft processing (see: 1.2.3 DEM and orthophoto generation) from aligned photos until extracting DEM and orthophoto. Under ArcMap software, we added orthophoto and the DEM obtained from Agisoft, in addition of the DEM and Map obtained by total station survey (figure). Thus, we could, firstly, check the planimetric superposition and, secondly, the altimetry errors.

2.2.3.3.2 Processing with GCPs

a) Test GCPs number and geometric distribution

After testing the DEMs accuracy and precision without GCPs, we will retry the tests taking into consideration the GCPs location. The GCPs distribution has an important impact on the results of DEMs and orthophoto in terms of accuracy and precision (Aguera-Vega et al., 2016). Although wide studies are documented about the best GCPs distribution for photogrammetry, however, there is a lack of information about the oblique images while scanning sinkholes. In addition to the sinkhole geometry shape, the extended snow cover

require a special study case. Therefore, we have to proceed by making tests in order to know the best GCPs number to use and their distribution on the study area.

The geometry of the study area and the location of cameras do not allow making the best GCPs distribution with an ideal visibility from the steady camera point of view. Therefore, we will make many tests for the number and the distribution of GCPs sufficient to achieve the minimum planimetric and elevation errors between DEMs obtained by cameras and DEMs obtained by total station. Because the planimetric part is required, we will compare the polygon of firm limit got by total station with snow surface on orthophotos obtained from camera and SfM processing.

In fact, this test focuses on the accurate distribution of GCPs measured by Total Station on the snow cover directly in the study area as a first test. Therefore, we proceeded by six tests, in which we were looking at the numerous snow cover changes, increases or decreases, according to the natural factors such as rain, snow or even snow melting. These tests are designed to establish fixed points that are visible to the cameras after the snow cover begins to recede. The point distribution tests were based on increasing, decreasing number of GCPs, approaching or removing GCPs in the processing. Each GCPs distribution test has been applied twice: i) for June 18th 2015 and; ii) for June 2th 2017. The goal was to confirm the results for two dates.

i. Temporal GCPs on the snow cover

The first test was to put the GCPs directly on the snow cover (Figure 45). SfM did this test in order to know how successful it was to better represent the snow cover.

They were distributed over the entire snow cover of the study area with almost equal distances. In the distribution, the focus was on placing planted pegs with black pieces or red paint directly on the snow cover.

Figure 45: Painted GCPs on the snow cover (taken automatically by one of the steady camera)

ii. Permanent GCPs on the bare land

The problem of the first test is the continuous changing of the snow cover due to accumulation or melting. That is why we need fix GCPs marked on the stable area that is the bare land. There is one thing in common between all the tests (Figure 46), which is that the GCPs are fixed on the ground and rocks, unlike the first test, but they do not start to appear to the cameras until the snow begins to recede.

Figure 46: Test of GCPs distribution

Edge 2 GCPs: is to place two points on the top of the study area facing the observation cameras (figure 46).

Edge 4 GCPs: is very similar to “Edge 2 GCPs”, since we use the same points, adding two others in the middle on the same horizontal line so that the number of points becomes four (figure 46).

Edge 8 GCPs: is like “Edge 2 GCPs” and “Edge 4 GCPs”, since GCPs number is added on the same horizontal line to obtain 8 GCPs in total (figure 46).

Framed 2 GCPs: This test is very different from the previous ones: first, we added points at the bottom of the study area, and secondly, we lowered the horizontal line from “Edge 2 GCPs”, “Edge 4 GCPs” and “Edge 8 GCPs”. It is important to point out that we have two points in the top line and two others in the bottom line, to have a total of 4 GCPs (figure 46).

Framed 6 GCPs lower top line: this GCPs distribution, it is very similar to the previous test as we added two GCPs in the middle of the points used to maintain the same horizontal lines to have a total of 8 GCPs (figure 46).

Framed 6 GCPs upper top line: This distribution is very similar to the previous. The only difference is the positioning of GCPs that are located on the top horizontal line. This latter is considered upper than GCPs located on “Framed 6 GCPs lower top line”. Regarding the bottom line, GCPs are same as “Framed 6 GCPs lower top line”. In other word, it is a combination of i) “Edge 4 GCPs” by using its upper horizontal line, ii) in addition of using the lower horizontal line of Framed 6 GCPs lower top line. So that the total number of GCPs observed is 6 (figure 46)

b) Processing with the best GCPs distribution

After the tests we choose distribution “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line” as best result (will be explain in the next chapter) in order to proceed by generation DEMs and orthophotos for many dates that will be validated by total station (see: 2.2.2 snow observation by total

station). For the first step on Agisoft, we will proceed by the same procedure used without GCPs for the first model. Then, benefit from the coordinates (E, N and Z) obtained for GCPs (Table 3) we make 3D georeferencing by optimizing cameras and restarting the batch process on Agisoft. Thus, we obtain relocated DEMs and orthophotos for each measured date.

GCP	Easting	Northing	Elevation
44	-304221.902	-19308.505	2309.529
41	-304213.149	-19322.210	2311.461
121	-304270.179	-19301.974	2323.402
114	-304238.916	-19359.013	2326.113
116	-304252.745	-19345.201	2324.574
119	-304266.122	-19321.878	2324.388

Table 3: GCPs coordinates

2.2.3.4 Automatic aligning DEM using ICP

Iterative Closest Point (ICP) is an algorithm employed to minimize the difference between two clouds of points or two raster. Adding GCPs after initial alignment is substantially faster than prior to alignment because the software can automatically determine the location of the GCP in each image used to construct the model after the user places the first marker (Mertes et al., 2017). After each marker was positioned correctly we entered the X, Y, Z data extracted from the current DEM and performed a bundle adjustment. Then we identified all GCPs, performed model optimizations, and generated dense point clouds at high settings with moderate to aggressive point filtering (Mertes et al., 2017).

2.2.3.4.1 Creating master plan

The master plan is the “reference” for any other DEM. For this study, the master plan is a bare land DEM (without snow), it will be used to align the other DEMs based on Iterative closest points (ICP) algorithm (Nissen et al., 2012; Suominen and Gotchev, 2013; Kleber et al., 2013; Shean et al., 2016; Mizinski & Niedzielski 2017; Eltner et al., 2017). We planned to obtain two different Master DEMs since each one has his own advantage and disadvantage: i) Master DEM extracted from the steady cameras used for the time lapse system (Figure 47); ii) Master DEM extracted from aerial images.

Both master DEMs are generated under Agisoft Photoscan software. Those DEMs are very well georeferenced using Ground control points (GCPs), which are physically fixed on the field. Those GCPs for “UAV master” were observed by GPS device and GCPs for “cameras master” were observed by total station to obtain their accurate coordinates position in the Lebanese stereographic projection system.

Figure 47: Steps for having the master DEM based on the terrestrial steady cameras

2.2.3.4.2 Preparing DEMs snow for automation

The generated slaves DEMs area obtained using terrestrial images of snow cover that were geotagged using high-accuracy stereographic coordinates system (used in Lebanon) obtained by total station (see: 2.2.1.3 Steady Cameras Installation) without need to be well georeferenced based on GCPs. Each time (day) we want to monitor the snow cover and estimate its volume we have to repeat the same procedure. This DEM is mainly based on three images for each day, taken automatically from the steady cameras by time-lapse concept. Those three images have a stereoscopic overlap which allows applying Structure from motion (SfM) algorithm under Agisoft Photoscan software. Combining time-lapse photogrammetry and SfM, is mainly done to increase temporal and spatial resolution (Eltener et al., 2017). This combination allows having automatic 3D observation for the snow cover. Based on the three images, we can obtain orthophoto and DEM. The latter contain snow cover area (SCA) and the bare land that is called stable area. In order to relocate this DEM on the right location based on the master DEM using ICP we have to separate the snow cover and the bare land (Figure 48). A matrix transformation will be found between master and slave DEM. This transformation will be apply on the snow cover.

Figure 48: Slave and Snow cover extraction

2.2.4 Snow cover observation with Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (Drone)

There is a new scientific revolution called Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) designed for various engineering applications (Siebert and Teizer, 2014; Arango and Morales, 2015), Geoscience and DSM³⁵ generation (Doumit, 2018; Doumit and Pogorelov 2018). In fact, UAV have progressed exponentially in the last years, as stated by Ruiz et al., (2013) because they can proceed without a licensed pilot onboard and they provide a low-cost approach in comparison with the classical aerial photogrammetry (Eisenbeis and Zhang, 2006; Eisenbeis, 2009; Arango and Morales, 2015). Therefore, the UAV user does not need to be a certified aircraft pilot. Not only UAV are less populated and it is safer to use them than to use an aircraft (Brunier et al., 2016), but they can also fly very close (few meters and above) to the ground, contrarily to the classical aircraft which cannot do the same for safety reasons.

50 years ago, there were many efforts to map snow height by using scanned aerial imagery (Smith et al., 1967) and Cline (1993) studied the topic in detail (1993, 1994). However, the main problem was that their results have a lack in image saturation and there were insufficient reference data.

Newly, many publications have relied on UAVs for SfM photogrammetry (Harwin and Lucieer, 2012; Mancini et al., 2013; Dowling and Gallant, 2013; Mancini et al., 2013; Ouédraogo et al., 2014; Udin and Ahmad 2014; Casella et al., 2014; Gonçalves and Henriques, 2015; Ryan et al., 2015; Dietrich, 2015; Gago et al., 2015; Uysal et al., 2015; Abou Chakra et al., 2016; Watanabe and Kawahara 2016; Nikolakopoulos et al., 2016 Krsal et al., 2016; Thomas and Kennedy 2016; Cimoli et al., 2017; Gruszczynski et al., 2017; Gindraux et al., 2017; Wigmore and Mark 2017). However, serious problems have been noticed with the accuracy of these estimates although the use of SfM for HS determination was well

³⁵ Digital Surface Model

documented (Harder et al., 2016; Mizinski & Niedzielski 2017). The main reason is that the orientation (Gabrlik, 2015) and the positions of the cameras in the global coordinate system were measured while using a standard GNSS receiver mounted on a flying UAV, without using the real-time kinematic (RTK) solution (Ruiz et al., 2013; Barry and Coakley, 2013). We will be solving this problem by using Ground control points (Aguera-Vega et al., 2016). On the other hand, questions arise about the dependency of the i) flying altitude; and ii) resolution of processing on the accuracy of obtained DEMs.

In this study, we apply aerial photogrammetry (Using DJI phantom 3 advanced) and SfM in order to calculate digital surface models (DSM) by testing the speed, altitude flight, and processing on different resolutions (low, medium, high) while processing under Agisoft Photoscan software. All tests will be validated by total station instrument measurements.

2.2.4.1 Data acquisition

In accordance with the local regulation provided by the aerial forces and the Directorate of the orientation of the Lebanese army, it was possible to proceed with the UAV surveys. In fact, after obtaining the monthly license before every mission, we had to inform the aerial forces about the location and the flying altitude in order to avoid any aerial accident between the drone and other aircraft. In addition, strong winds above 15 km/h do not allow using the drone.

In our experiment, we made systematic observation during the melting season for the following years: 2016, 2017, and 2018. We used different DJI Phantom: Phantom 3 advanced, phantom 3 Pro and Phantom 4 pro (See: Appendix 6). However, for the testing altitude, speed, and processing resolution impact, we used DJI Phantom 3 UAV with a camera of 12 megapixels at a focal length of 3.61 mm so that we can scan the study area at different heights and speeds.

We can measure the flight heights from the UAV take off point knowing that the experiment is formed by 5 flight missions of 50,100, 200, 350 and 500 meters' height (FA-50, FA-100, FA-200; FA-350 and FA-500) (figure). The pictures were saved in JPEG file formats.

Figure 49: Phantom at diverse altitude above the ground

2.2.4.1.1 Flying mission preparation

In order to respect aerial photogrammetric rules, suitable flight planning should be designed and carry out (Ruiz et al., 2013; Gandor et al., 2015). Aerial photos without enough overlap become useless for generating DEMs and orthophotos; therefore, the photos will only be considered as pictures. Accordingly, mission planning is considered as a critical phase for successful DEM generation (Cimoli et al., 2017). As for the interval between two consecutive pictures, it was adjusted to two seconds which was minimum interval choice. To reach efficacious missions planning, the five UAV missions will have the same overlap (70-80% along the flight line and 60-70% as side overlap (Figure 50)) (Agisoft 2016) using a mobile autopilot Android application known as Litchi (Figure 51). We have to take into consideration

the distance between flight lines. This latter is directly related to the flight altitude and the field of view (FoV) of the camera.

Using Litchi application, allows placing waypoints to have parallel lines, which will represent the autopilot path of the drone while making the mission. Five missions were prepared (Figure 51) since each one represents a given altitude flight.

Figure 50: Example of obtained picture location and their side lap

Figure 51: The five missions' plans at different altitudes

2.2.4.1.2 Field work

For all tests, DEMs and orthophotos were calibrated by GCPs (See: 2.2.1.2.2 Control points for UAV). However, there are two situations considered for using GCPs: i) firstly, we placed the markers temporarily on the snow cover; ii) secondly, we painted GCPs on the ground. In this context, the test was achieved when GCPs were put temporarily by placing them on snow cover. Nevertheless, for continuous monitoring, we were relying on the permanent painted GCPs on the ground without snow.

During the flight, the screen will show the autopilot, which will display the flight path, the study area, and the flight parameters like coordinates, height, time ...

2.2.4.2 Data processing

First, it is important to mention that we need a powerful computer to finalize the processing (Siebert et al., 2014; Uysal et al., 2015). In fact, we do not talk about this issue while processing the data that comes from steady cameras because we are talking here about three images per date; something that is easy for any computer. However, in our case, we will need among 8 to 350 pictures in order to cover the study area according to the flight altitude. For this purpose, the processing was performed on a custom-built laptop running an Intel(R) Core (™) i7-6700 HQ CPU @2.60GHz 2.59 GHz with 4 cores and 32 GB of memory DDR4. The computer GPU is an Intel® HD Graphics 530 DDR4.

All the processing of aerial images was done under Agisoft Photoscan. The data processing is quite easy. The process starts by uploading the photos from the Drone to the computer while deleting the distorted or blurred ones. Nevertheless, it is well known that the processing of a big number of photos takes a lot of time and consumes a lot of space, especially when we use the maximum performance of the software resolution. In this context, the following question arises: will it be enough to use medium or low-resolution images and obtain enough results in terms of accuracy? For this reason, we decided to start our experiment by testing the impact of increasing or decreasing the resolution of

processing. Agisoft allows us to choose the level of alignment accuracy and dense cloud quality (Morgan et al., 2016). We tried to adjust and change the alignment accuracy setting from the “lowest” to “medium” and “highest”, and we alternated the dense cloud quality setting from “lowest” to “medium” and “ultra-high”.

On March 17th 2017, forty images were selected and were taken at 100 m as flight altitude. We have chosen 100 m flight altitude because the GCPs are clearly visible. In addition, nine GCPs were temporarily put on the snow cover and were very useful for georeferencing and optimization of aero triangulation in the photogrammetric workflow (Brunier et al., 2016).

Based on the above, we have decided to choose the “medium resolution” (see: 3.3.1 Result of Agisoft photoscan resolution). Another question arises here. It affects the covered area during the flight mission because it is directly related to the battery life. Therefore, what is the suitable flight speed in order to finalize any mission without neither losing accuracy nor wasting time? In this context, we made the flight two consecutive times: for the first flight, the speed was around 54 km/h and for the second, it was about 13 km/h. The expected results obtained showed that there is no impact by the speed change (see: 3.3.2 Impact of changing speed).

After testing the speed and the resolution impact, we pursued our study by testing the changing altitude impact. The only difference in processing between the different altitudes is the number of photos used. In fact, we used from 8 to 350 selected photos according to each flight altitude since various UAV flight altitudes led to different DSMs (Doumit and Pogorelov 2018). After the processing of all the dataset of the five missions at different flight altitudes, we started the extraction of Digital Surface Models (DSM) and orthophotos. The entire models obtained were validated by Total Station measurements.

2.2.4.3 Validation of DEMs and correlation with total station

Accuracy and precision of Digital Elevation Model has a great influence in computing accurate volumes. It is assumed that the values of points elevation measured with the total station is considered as reference. Although, this instrument do not provide for us high density comparing to TLS and SfM, however we can be sure of the accuracy of each measured point individually. Thus, the instrument will be the base for us to validate the accuracy of each generated DEM. The measured points by total station were sample points of validation since they are well distributed on each generated DEM.

Total station measurement provide multitude points locates by their three-dimensional coordinate (see: 1.2.1: Constructing DEM with manual and random points) (Figure 52). This set of points present the DEM realized by this instrument. In addition, each measured, intersect a corresponding pixel raster from any other georeferenced DEM coming from terrestrial or aerial photogrammetry. In this context, by subtracting each the value DEM UAV or DEM Steady cameras from the elevation value obtained by total station, we will obtain the errors. Thus, standards deviation, means and maximum errors will be estimated (Figure 55).

According to the source of DEMs, the evaluation of accuracy will be done with two methods. DEMs extracted with UAV will be validated by Method 1 in order to avoid the impact of interpolation. While DEMs extracted with steady cameras will be validated by method 2 due to errors on planimetric shifting.

Method 1

With ArcMap software, "Add surface information" tools are used (Figure 53). This tool allow us to have a new field on the shape file on which we add the elevation value of the raster (Figure 54)

Figure 52: distributed point's elevation that were measured by total station

Figure 53: Add surface information operation under ArcMap software

PHID	East	North	Code	Elevation	UAV 50m13	UAV 100m13	UAV 100m54	UAV 200m13	UAV 350m13	UAV 500m26
33	-304234.4972	-19304.0425	S	2317.1654	2317.105609	2317.125477	2317.026975	2317.156324	2317.046315	2316.832192
34	-304228.6171	-19312.4386	S	2316.9476	2316.928417	2316.97625	2316.916549	2317.088219	2317.113876	2317.198084
35	-304223.6583	-19318.9344	S	2316.9881	2316.961073	2316.968996	2316.879784	2316.993273	2317.088906	2317.067711
36	-304219.559	-19323.608	S	2317.3033	2317.263776	2317.280522	2317.222705	2317.390549	2317.637617	2317.655733
37	-304214.7917	-19328.8049	S	2318.0308	2318.009205	2318.021107	2317.969067	2317.962159	2318.172046	2317.681443
38	-304209.4857	-19334.2237	S	2319.1865	2319.119625	2319.190207	2319.170667	2319.186204	2319.171995	2319.039876
39	-304203.1479	-19338.5806	S	2320.3037	2320.211602	2320.184703	2320.160671	2320.171833	2320.080335	2319.88516
40	-304199.9099	-19335.0455	S	2318.2969	2318.17404	2318.160812	2318.177417	2318.120016	2318.258176	2318.000154
41	-304205.6294	-19329.489	S	2317.1267	2317.032789	2316.966621	2316.994205	2316.823046	2317.04936	2316.911249
42	-304209.9722	-19323.9019	S	2315.7043	2315.603721	2315.572146	2315.572632	2315.435881	2315.566857	2315.608603
43	-304216.8758	-19318.0616	S	2314.9861	2314.898081	2314.845092	2314.79645	2314.763694	2314.791347	2314.548399
44	-304222.4722	-19312.1397	S	2314.5467	2314.40359	2314.438375	2314.388871	2314.317875	2314.303969	2314.985209
45	-304226.8108	-19303.0234	S	2314.2114	2314.074141	2314.087416	2314.049332	2314.003551	2314.149694	2314.131443
46	-304226.6222	-19296.2968	S	2314.8079	2314.706289	2314.712405	2314.704621	2314.696113	2314.725047	2314.523577
47	-304229.3795	-19289.3596	S	2316.3163	2316.232687	2316.211335	2316.254337	2316.263233	2316.252263	2315.999911
48	-304216.6957	-19292.528	S	2315.7706	2315.664714	2315.61739	2315.62462	2315.691897	2315.685328	2315.590845
49	-304212.1274	-19297.4125	S	2315.1666	2315.074021	2315.030716	2315.058171	2315.04187	2314.912847	2314.601992
50	-304213.8574	-19303.6459	S	2313.6043	2313.478175	2313.506468	2313.468057	2313.396244	2313.6114	2313.321434
51	-304210.7873	-19307.4473	S	2313.663	2313.548276	2313.536168	2313.544137	2313.542094	2313.663139	2313.422348
52	-304210.7312	-19316.1901	S	2313.8778	2313.761024	2313.832447	2313.81314	2313.821968	2314.00377	2313.837081
53	-304206.2784	-19322.7168	S	2315.311	2315.181139	2315.215708	2315.170318	2315.111494	2315.328056	2315.065688
54	-304202.5224	-19330.0879	S	2316.9882	2316.888437	2316.881793	2316.886839	2316.896338	2317.024884	2317.014568
55	-304196.3378	-19336.9585	S	2318.4675	2318.351781	2318.338517	2318.333565	2318.390454	2318.649238	2318.44074
56	-304208.5159	-19299.1982	S	2315.4975	2315.400463	2315.350035	2315.362189	2315.380535	2315.239642	2314.688469
57	-304215.4397	-19291.8362	S	2316.0944	2316.008811	2315.972581	2315.996852	2316.034859	2315.917232	2315.740152
58	-304252.8811	-19294.0891	S	2324.3856	2324.32075	2324.331181	2324.367318	2324.400929	2324.398084	2324.355029
59	-304245.1807	-19306.2795	S	2324.5471	2324.47635	2324.467212	2324.455888	2324.533821	2324.257597	2324.421926
60	-304242.4267	-19313.1144	S	2324.5844	2324.501781	2324.503847	2324.485545	2324.544848	2324.308757	2324.380794
61	-304234.062	-19321.8782	S	2324.2935	2324.227771	2324.216884	2324.216242	2324.315386	2324.294243	2324.075318
62	-304227.5168	-19328.3102	S	2324.4058	2324.325664	2324.293042	2324.30136	2324.266019	2324.149498	2324.04463
63	-304222.7907	-19335.3073	S	2325.1713	2325.093813	2325.069264	2325.068171	2324.991777	2324.835892	2324.57577
64	-304218.6047	-19341.0482	S	2325.7829	2325.72962	2325.679544	2325.650235	2325.658461	2325.707522	2325.519027
65	-304214.5276	-19345.8674	S	2326.4317	2326.371575	2326.338546	2326.377384	2326.338119	2326.351899	2326.152968

Figure 54: obtained elevation points extracted from UAV at diverse altitude

Figure 55: example of obtained histogram to evaluation error distribution of difference altitude between DEM UAV and DEM total station.

Method 2:

Using raster calculator tools under ArcMap software, we rely subtracting DEM camera - DEM Total station (Figure 56). A new raster difference elevation is created and shows the errors distribution, in addition of the mean and standard deviation.

Figure 56: Comparison of accuracy between Total Station DEM and UAV DEM

2.3 Annual and inter-annual snow cover monitoring

The previous sections in this chapter discussed the methodologies for answering rational questions (a³⁶). However, that approach remains just validating measurement methods to be used for monitoring. Without benefiting from those approaches, they will

³⁶ Relying on low-cost observation approaches, is it possible to monitor accurately and automatically the snow cover volume decreasing during the melting season, in a pilot sinkhole, with a high spatio-temporal resolution?

remain useless and will not answer questions (b1³⁷) and (b2³⁸). In this perspective, different approaches were applied to obtain systematic and continuous snow cover observation. Firstly, we already have raw measurement data at Jabal el Dib obtained for years 2012 and 2013 from master studies about the same study area (Abou Chakra 2013 and Elali 2014). Snow cover elevation points and coordinates were obtained with total station machine. Those points are able to provide DEMs, volumes, and profiles sections. Secondly, this thesis research completed the systematic and continuous observation from 2015 using total station machines and two additional approaches: i) monitoring with steady cameras and; ii) UAV DJI Phantom. All available data along with every approach provided are summarized in (Table 4).

Area		Pilot Site				
		Jabal El Dib			Bou Mechleh	
Equipment		Total Station	Steady Cameras	UAV	Total Station	UAV
Year	2012	*				
	2013	*				
	2014					
	2015	*	*			
	2016	*		*		
	2017	*	*	*	*	*
	2018	*	*	*		*

Table 4: Available observed data with different approaches from 2012 till 2018

Although steady cameras were well validated in the research, their output data were not used for monitoring yet, but they were helpful for our first perspective. This was the full automation of snow cover monitoring for complete seasons (see perspective). In fact, HS,

³⁷ based on the pilot sinkhole observations, is it possible to understand snow melt behavior inside sinkholes

³⁸ Based on the pilot sinkhole observations, is it possible to have precise information about the snow cover decreasing or increasing from year to year?

surface, and volume decreasing with time are the main factors to monitor the melting behavior. DEMs of snow cover were extracted by total station measurements for years 2012, 2013, and 2015. While the DEMs of the years 2016, 2017, and 2018 were extracted by UAV flying missions, most of DEMs and orthophotos extracted with UAV for years 2016, 2017, and 2018 were validated with a total station. In this context, for those later years, very few DEMs were extracted by the total station as an exception. This exception was caused by strong winds and logistical problems with drones and we were prevented by air forces operations due to the presence of military aircraft at the same time.

Whatever was the approach used, snow DEMs were generated. Consequently, it was easy to obtain section profiles and calculate the volume of each observed date. Therefore, annual and inter-annual observations for snow cover were obtained in Jabal El Dib area and we were driven to understand the melt behavior. In this context, it is very important to note that understanding the snowmelt is limited in Jabal El Dib pilot sinkhole, which becomes useless in order to apply for other areas or make extrapolation on a larger area. This is why having annual and inter-annual observations of other areas become essential. The new larger area was selected in 2017. Knowing that many methods were used and many observations were conducted in a determined area, called Bou Mechleh, a certain snow melting behavior was noted. This area was observed with drones for the years 2017 and 2018. Observations at Bou Mechleh areas provided DEMs that allowed us to understand the snowmelt process far away from Jabal el Dib. Consequently, if a common melt behavior between Jabal El Dib and Bou Mechleh is noted, extrapolation becomes possible.

Chapter 3: Results and analysis

Part I: Measurement Approaches

3.1 Introduction

Among all instruments, Total Station is considered as the most accurate and its measurements are thought to be reference. Therefore, the total station was continuously used to monitor snow cover at Jabal El Dib for the years 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018. In addition, Total Station was the tool used to validate all the tests: i) by steady cameras with different GCPs distribution; ii) by UAV with different resolutions; iii) by UAV with different speeds and; iv) by UAV with diverse flight altitudes.

This part will mainly focus on illustrating results obtained by each instrument under different conditions and methods.

3.2 Steady cameras

Using steady cameras for 3D automatic monitoring of snow cover in a pilot sinkhole was the most innovative component of this study both on the national and international level. It benefited from combining time lapse and SfM terrestrial photogrammetry for a small area to monitor the snowmelt behavior. However, the ideal condition was not met. It faced various issues as the cameras location, since it is impossible to stabilize a drone permanently to obtain automatic observations. In addition, snow accumulation does not allows us to install cameras everywhere since HS could reach 10m and steady cameras are “only”2m above the ground. There is also a problem that is relevant to the GCPs distribution due to the geometry of the study area and the snow accumulation, in addition to the camera vibration caused by the strong winds.

Serious issues challenged this experiment. It was impossible to apply automatic daily time lapse to aerial photogrammetry; therefore, we lost ideal field view of images. Consequently, two main problems arise: i) we observe the sky where we have “infinity view” and; ii) due to the inclined cameras, important ground distortion close to cameras location is present as well as on the horizontal land (Figure 57).

To solve the above-mentioned problems, many tests were conducted to define the best methods (see: 2.2.1: Snow cover monitoring by steady cameras). Results of those tests will be shown in the coming paragraphs.

Figure 57: Problem of using terrestrial photogrammetry

3.2.1 Processing without GCPs

Firstly, centimetric accuracy was obtained from steady cameras. In addition, we can measure (even approximately) the orientation of the cameras. Those parameters allow us to apply direct photogrammetry (Gabrlik, 2015). The Orthophoto and DSMs results have been validated with total station measurement in term of both planimetry and altimetry.

Concerning planimetry errors commonly called “horizontal shifting”; the snow patch borders were drawn accurately with the total station. (Figure 58a) shows a shifting error of 3m since the red line in (Figure 58a) presents the true location of snow patch borders. In addition, altimetry validation test has been conducted. In fact, we superposed the two DSMs on ArcMap and calculated the errors (Figure 58b). So, we found unacceptable errors, the interval is between -2 and -15 m, which mean errors of -8.7m and standard deviation of 2.7m, values that are unacceptable. The errors start at 2m where the model is a little bit closer to the cameras location and continues to increase at the end of the view field where we find 15m. As per our analysis those big errors are caused by the lack of the GCPs. In addition, the external orientation was not measured by a gyroscope; this may cause a negative impact on the obtained results.

Figure 58: Planimetric and altimetric errors without GCPs

3.2.2 Processing with GCPs

Due to the bad results obtained without GCPs, many test GCPs with have been conducted. Multiple tests were needed on the GCPs distribution because of this “unclassical” case with possible adjustment of the GCPs setting. It is possible to set GCPs on snow; however, they need to be installed every day. Therefore, this is not feasible, and it does not meet the criteria of a ‘fully automated observation systems’. Impact of the GCPs distribution is explained below.

3.2.2.1 Temporal GCPs on the snow cover

The first stage was to assess the impact of GCPs set directly on the snow cover (Figure 59) for two main reason: i) The SfM method applicability was not definite in our conditions (homologue points on snow cover and camera positions); ii) during the first approach the whole study area was covered by snow and it was impossible to find any stable place on bare land to set the GCPs (Figure 59). The maximum elevation error is around 160 cm; this is considered unacceptable. However, while checking (Figure 60b) it is noticeable that the extreme error is located on the edge of the study area where maximum distortion occur. Mean and the standard deviation are equal to 36cm and 25cm respectively (Figure 60 and Figure 61) which are acceptable in such environmental conditions.

With steady cameras, we are able to extract a relatively accurate 3D model and consequently comparatively accurate orthophotos and DEM. In a deep analysis of the results, (Figure 59) show green (2, 4, 7, 5, 6, 130, 131 and 132) and grey flags (137, 140 and 141), all of them present GCPs location. At green flags (2, 4, 7, 5, 6, 130, 131 and 132) location, we found high accuracy, while, at grey flags (137, 140 and 141) Agisoft was not able to construct neither DEM nor orthophoto. The main cause of this failure is the maximum distortion due to the camera’s locations and to the horizontality of snow cover on this area (Figure 57) since the software could not find homologue points, regardless of the gap of data caused by the bad visibility.

The experiment was successful. However, it is very constrained because it requires physical installation of the GCPs; and therefore, it limits applicability for an automated system. Consequently, many tests will be evaluated in the next section when the snow cover starts melting and the ground become clear. Thus, we can installed permanent GCPs on the bare land (natural ground).

Figure 59: GCPs distribution on snow, green flags show the good position, while the above grey flags show problem on finding homologues points.

Figure 60: a) obtained orthophoto of snow cover; b) raster difference elevation between DEM camera and DEM Total station and spatial error distribution.

Figure 61: statistical result of raster difference elevation between DEM camera and DEM Total station

3.2.2.2 Permanent GCPs on the bare land

We will be talking about the GCPs on land followed by the characteristics of the GCPs distributions. The evaluation of each test is done for two dates. Using the same images for each date, six experiments have been conducted by changing the GCPs number and position distribution as mentioned in the section (2.2.3.3.2.a ii: Permanent GCPs on the bare land). Results of the tests are summarized in (Table 5). Large errors were found with tests “Edge 2 GCPs”, “Edge 4 GCPs and Edge 8 GCPs” when GCPs are distributed just on the upper horizontal line of the study area. Although expected, we tried to benefit from them due to the existed snow cover in the bottom of the sinkhole. Acceptable results were achieved with tests “Framed 2 GCPs”, “Framed 6 GCPs lower top line” and “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line”. All means and standards deviation were under 40 cm. Among all tests, “Framed 6 GCPs lower top line” is the best since we obtained minimum elevations difference errors, acceptable mean and standard deviation equal to 6 and 26 cm respectively as the average between both dates, and the best error distribution (nearly Gaussian). However, the use of “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line” distribution is preferable although it has little bigger marge of errors. Distribution of GCPs on the test “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line” allows earlier automatic monitoring start because when starting monitoring by test “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line”, GCPs of “Framed 6 GCPs lower top line” remain sheltered by snow cover. Thus, this test causes a delay in the launch of the automatic observation. With “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line”, relatively accurate and precise DEM is extracted since it has maximum mean errors

equal to 6 cm, while 27 cm is gained for the standard deviation (Figure 62 and Table 5). More detail about processing results is provided in Appendix 2.

GCP Distribution	Test number	Number of GCPs	Date	Minimum (m)	Maximum (m)	Mean (m)	Standard deviation (m)	RMSE
	Edge 2 GCPs	2	2-Jun-17 18-Jun-15	-2.6 -0.75	1.1 0.8	-0.33 -0.045	1.06 0.35	1.11 0.35
	Edge 4 GCPs	4	2-Jun-17 18-Jun-15	-2.13 -1.06	0.95 -0.18	0.22 -0.62	0.79 0.2	0.82 0.65
	Edge 8 GCPs	8	2-Jun-17 18-Jun-15	-1.78 -1.35	3.36 4.5	0.77 2.63	1.35 0.6	1.55 2.70
	Framed 2 GCPs	4	2-Jun-17 18-Jun-15	-1.05 -1.01	2.06 0.39	-0.2 -0.09	0.48 0.27	0.52 0.28
	Framed 6 GCPs lower top line	6	2-Jun-17 18-Jun-15	-0.79 -0.61	0.88 0.57	0.05 0.07	0.3 0.22	0.30 0.23
	Framed 6 GCPs upper top line	6	2-Jun-17 18-Jun-15	1.03 -0.21	1.29 1.31	-0.01 -0.06	0.27 0.27	0.27 0.28

Table 5: results of difference in elevation data between DEM total station and DEM Camera between for the divers GCP tests.

Figure 62: Spatial and statistical distribution or elevation errors between DEM total station and DEM Cameras between for "Framed 6 GCPs upper top line".

3.2.2.3 Processing with the best GCPs distribution

Test “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line” was selected as the best solution of GCP distribution. It provides the best compromise between accuracy and maximum days of observation. What is meant by Maximum Days of Observation is that, as a first option, we could have set the number of GCPs on a lower level and the result would have been the best ones. Another option is to place them at a higher level, showing slightly weaker results, though; but they will be covered by snow at this point. That is why when choosing a higher level, the days of observation would be longer when are using time-lapse cameras.

To continue processing and validation of 2015 melting season, some dates (Figure 64) are selected and processed relying on this test “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line”. The selected dates (Figure 64) are the same as when total station measurements were taken. The validation started from May 20th 2015 to July 4th 2015 that was one week before total snow melting in the study area. As an exception, just images of May 20th 2015 were processed using “edge 4 GCPs” (Figure 63) because snow cover was still covering the bottom of the sinkhole. In addition, limitation of putting GCPs just on the upper horizontal line of the sinkhole will be proved.

All statistical results are summarized in (Table 6). As expected, May 20th 2015 has the worst results. The maximum, mean, and standard deviation of the elevation differences between the two DEMs are 3.39, 1.50, and 1.06 m, respectively. Therefore, the presence of snow cover on a strategic location in the sinkhole does not allows accurate 3D model calibration with GCPs. Looking at the results of the remaining dates (Table 6), we find that they are acceptable. Mean and standard deviation vary from 3 to 28 cm and 8 to 28 cm respectively, and 1.44 m as an extreme value.

(Figure 65) shows distribution of altimetric errors for each date. Starting on May 20th 2015, on the lower part of the study area, and on the cameras side, extreme errors are found. It is expected and well documented that the absence of GCPs causes the presence of large errors. However, providing the accurate coordinate position of steady cameras was encouraging to solve this issue. Unfortunately, cameras coordinates were not helpful to rely

on in order to relocate 3D model extracted from inclined images. Regarding other validated dates (from June 4th, 2015 to July 4th, 2015), acceptable results and spatial distribution errors are obtained. Green yellow and light blue colors show errors less than 50cm (Figure 65). These colors (Green, yellow and light blue), occupy most of the raster difference in elevation (May 20th, 2015). Nevertheless, dark blue color occupies a minor area for June 4th and 29th 2015 and a slightly major one on June 18th 2015. Dark blue color presents an error between 50 and 75 cm that is unacceptable. These errors are centered on the lower middle of the study area and are responsible for increasing mean and standard deviation values. These errors and their locations are most probably caused by two facts: i) Agisoft advises to capture 8 images to construct accurate orthophoto and DEM and; ii) a lot of distortions are found close to the cameras. Logically, these facts can negatively affect the DEMs accuracy. For other perspectives, solving the first problem could be possible by capturing additional images for the study area.

Generally, acceptable results were obtained when GCPs were visible to cameras and covered within the stereoscopic overlap area. However, this approach required steady cameras without any vibration because of the wind, during all the observed season. In addition, sometimes one of the cameras is damaged and must be removed for repair. Therefore, the camera loses its initial orientation. Moreover, automatic import markers become useless (Figure 66) due to the translated captured pictures. Consequently, manually painted GCPs are required to facilitate automation.

Figure 63: example at 20 May 2015 when snow cover still cover the bare land and do not allow the visibility on the GCP 41 and 44.

Figure 64: the fifth date of validation

Figure 65: spatial error distribution on raster difference in elevation obtained by subtracting DEM total station from DEM cameras on each dates

Date	Test number	Number of GCPs	Minimum (m)	Maximum (m)	Mean (m)	Standard deviation (m)	RMSE
20-May-15	Edge 4 GCPs	4	-0.21	3.39	1.5	0.81	1.70
4-Jun-15	Framed	6	-0.57	0.81	0.167	0.2	0.26
18-Jun-15	6 GCPs	6	-0.46	1.44	0.28	0.27	0.39
29-Jun-15	upper	6	-0.03	0.77	0.3	0.12	0.32
4-Jul-15	top line	6	-0.18	0.33	0.03	0.08	0.09

Table 6: Errors extracted from each raster difference elevation obtained by subtracting DEM total station from EM cameras on each dates

Figure 66: Impact of camera rotation or vibration on the automatic importing markers

3.2.3 Automatic relocating DEM using ICP

The following is an experiment that shows automatic co-registration of DEMs based on ICP and without needing any GCPs. The goal is to relocate snow DEMs, relying on a base master bare land DEM. For each date of observation, clipped snow and bare land DEM (slave) were prepared. Each slave bare land will be superposed depending on the Master DEM location and orientation. Therefore, vector transformation needs to be extracted. This latter will be applied too on snow DEM to be relocated. Hence, we do not need to put GCPs for each date.

As mentioned in section (2.2.3.4.1 creating master DEM), this experiment was done twice, i) firstly using extracted master DEM with UAV acquisitions; ii) secondly, using master DEM extracted from stereoscopic reconstruction using steady cameras. Regarding the justification of this experience, validation of the DEMs was done in two ways. On the first hand, statistical difference elevation between master DEM and relocated DEM slave bare land was estimated. On the other hand, subtraction of Total Station snow DEM from relocated slave snow DEM provides raster difference in elevation. In addition, superposition of exact snow limit measured by the total station on slave bare land DEM gives us a clear idea about any planimetric shifting.

Statistical results are summarized in (Table 7). The procedure is to start by validating the obtained RMSE³⁹ for the co-registration of stable areas, or in other words bare land.

For both cameras and UAV, master DEM's RMSE decrease from 102 cm to ~ 30 cm from May 8th to July 4th 2015 respectively. This period, from May 8th 2015 to July 4th 2015, is the time of snow melting that induces a reduction of the error margin through time. This is due to the decrease of snow cover areas during snow melting. When the snow melts, a larger

³⁹ Root Mean Square Errors

terrain surface appear; because the part of the bare land has a more accurate DEM than the snowy part, the relocating becomes better. Concerning the quality of DEMs, they become acceptable and the errors decrease to less than 50 cm after June 4th 2015. The stable land, in fact, grows in area and ICP can find more common points between slave and master DEM, which is important for relocation quality (Figure 67 and Figure 69).

Moving to the validation of snow cover DEM with a total station, bad superposition is notable between i) the snow limit extracted by the Total Station and ii) the prepared slave DEM, for both of May 8th and 20th 2015. This bad superposition (Figure 67 and Figure 69) can explain the above results for the same dates, since orthophoto and DEM are not well constructed while using already SfM. The main reason is caused by the big distortion closely to the camera's field of view and nearby study area borders. Regarding June 4th and 18th 2015, we obtained, using master camera DEM, RMSE of 54 and 97 cm respectively. While for the same dates (June 4th and 18th 2015), we attained with Master UAV DEM, an RMSE of 91 and 35 cm respectively (Figure 68 and Figure 70). Consequently, neither UAV Master nor camera Master DEM was preferred. As for the remaining dates, RMSE is acceptable and we can rely on it.

Evaluating the power of both master DEM (camera bare land and UAV bare land), six dates were fixed to validate the ICP method for this study case. Concerning the preferable master to be used later, those six justification dates have not confirmed which Master DEM is the most favorable. Generally, acceptable results are obtained with some limitations that are caused by the big difference in terms of the field of view between steady cameras and UAV (Figure 71). Consequently, DEM is proposed for extraction of a new Master DEM with inclined images taken by the drone (Figure 72). This ensures an area with low deformations. For the bare land, images will be provided especially when they are taken approximately with the cameras same points of view. Therefore, recommendations of Agisoft Photoscan regarding 80 % overlap and 60% of side lap will be respected.

Date	Master DEM	On Snow cover					On bare land	
		Minimum (m)	Maximum (m)	Mean (m)	Standard deviation (m)	RMSE (m)	RMSE (m)	
8-May-15	Camera	-6.78	0.09	-2.23	1.4	2.63	0.57	
	Drone	-3.32	0.53	-0.79	0.63	1.01	1.02	
20-May-15	Camera	-3.1	3.35	0.66	1.06	1.25	0.82	
	Drone	-0.06	4.45	2.05	1.03	2.29	0.87	
4-Jun-15	Camera	-1.86	0.32	-0.35	0.41	0.54	0.44	
	Drone	-3.12	0.11	-0.73	0.54	0.91	0.53	
18-Jun-15	Camera	-0.54	2.2	0.74	0.63	0.97	0.34	
	Drone	-0.94	1	0.17	0.31	0.35	0.46	
29-Jun-15	Camera	-0.1	0.91	0.43	0.21	0.48	0.29	
	Drone	-0.48	0.33	0.02	0.14	0.14	0.30	
4-Jul-15	Camera	-0.22	0.68	0.27	0.187	0.33	0.29	
	Drone	-0.96	0.27	-0.15	0.25	0.29	0.32	

Table 7: statistical results for six date of validation using ICP based on Master UAV DEM and Master camera DEM

Figure 67: Relocated Slave Bare land DEM based on cameras Master DEM

Figure 68: Relocated Slave Snow DEM based on cameras Master DEM and their spatial elevation errors distribution

Figure 69: Relocated Slave Bare land DEM based on UAV Master DEM

Figure 70: Relocated Slave Snow DEM based on UAV Master DEM and their spatial elevation errors distribution

Figure 71: a) obtained field of view with UAV; b) obtained field of view with steady camera

Figure 72: suggested method for extracting the best Master DEM with UAV

3.3 UAV

In this section, the influence of flights parameters is being highlighted, particularly; the assessment of the resolution processing (alignment accuracy and dense cloud quality) on the snow DEMs quality will be exposed, in addition to the impact of diverse flight altitudes and speed. All tests were done on snow cover of March 28th 2018, since we could make all the flights needed and take the required measurement with total station without any problem such as army authorization, availability instruments, and good meteorological condition like wind speed and fog.

DEMs accuracy is evaluated relying on two methods. On one hand, Agisoft Photoscan provides many statistics errors including GCPs placement error (Appendix 3, 4). It provides estimation of the difference between the actual coordinates and the estimated position from SfM processing. The error is expressed as RMSE, easting – northing – elevation differences. These errors are minimized within the SfM workflow by optimizing the point cloud while minimizing errors position from GCPs. On the other hand, the 187 points measured with Total Station (Figure 73) are compared to the elevation that is extracted from the DEM surface to give deeper information about the error distribution on the snow cover.

Elevation errors are calculated by subtracting the UAV DEM from the Total station:

Elevation difference = Point value of DEM UAV - Point value of DEM Total Station

Figure 73: Distribution of the 187 points measured points elevation with total station at March 28th 2017

3.3.1 Result with Agisoft photoscan resolution

Although, choosing the suitable resolution of Agisoft processing (alignment photo accuracy and dense cloud quality) has been well documented for Glaciers (Gindraux et al., 2017) and flume laboratory (Morgan et al., 2016), it was very important to respectively choose suitable processing accuracy and quality (highest, Medium or Lowest) of photos alignment and dense cloud for snow cover. This selection avoids time wasting and space storage without losing the required DEM accuracy and resolution. The processing resolution was practiced on the same pictures taken at 100m flight altitude. After analyzing this result, acceptable values for all the resolutions have been obtained, especially for mean and standard deviation. On the first hand, the best mean is acquired with the low resolution that is equal to 5mm while it is 4 and 5 cm for the medium and high resolution respectively. Regarding the values of standard deviation, we get 37cm for low resolution, while it is 13 and 15cm for the medium and high resolution respectively (Figure 74). On the other hand, looking at the error distribution in Figure 75 shows that the best distribution error was noticed with the Medium resolution. Talking about the obtained pixel size for DEMs, we found 4 cm, 16 cm and 60 cm for highest, medium and lowest resolution respectively. In fact, 16 cm is considered as an acceptable result to get precise DEM for snow cover.

Surprisingly, processing accuracy and quality do not have a serious impact on orthophotos resolutions because the obtained pixel size of orthophotos is around 4 cm for the lowest medium and high processing resolutions (Table 8). In addition, Figure 75a shows a good errors repartition with medium processing which is nearly to the theoretical Gaussian curve.

Based on the above information, medium accuracy and quality for respectively alignment photos and dense cloud appeared to be suitable, as well as shifting to analyzing storage space and consuming time for each resolution. Processing time and space storage is the primary differences between the variations in Agisoft Photoscan settings. Processing the 20 images on the used laptop took around 30 minutes, 60 minutes and 5 hours for lowest, medium and highest processing respectively. While the stored size for the Agisoft project

became 235 MB, 292 MB and 1.14 GB for lowest, medium and highest resolution respectively. Thus, we have additional arguments to continue using medium processing.

Figure 74: Influence of alignment accuracy and dense cloud quality on elevation difference between DEM UAV and DEM Total station

Figure 75: Errors distribution for different Agisoft accuracy and quality processing for alignment and dense cloud respectively; a) Low, b) Medium, c) High.

Date	Resolution	UAV height (m)	Speed (km/h)	Number of images	DEM Resolution (m)	Orthophotos Resolution (m)	Agisoft Project Size	Time Processing
28-Mar-17	Lowest	100	13	20	0.644	0.040248647	235 MB	30 minutes
	Medium	100	13	20	0.161	0.040325244	292 MB	60 minutes
	Highest	100	13	20	0.040	0.040138372	1.14 GB	5 hours

Table 8: Processing time consuming, space storage output, DEM and Orthophotos pixel size for different Agisoft accuracy and quality processing for alignment and dense cloud respectively.

3.3.2 Impact of changing speed

Most documents on photogrammetry do not consider the impact of flight speed changes on DEM accuracy, whereas it could affect the snow cover evaluation. Testing this impact was then required. After analyzing the results, we did not find any impact of flight changing speed, neither on the means of error nor on the standard deviation (Figure 76). Consequently, we can plan any mission without taking into consideration the speed. Thus, we can benefit from more battery time.

Figure 76: Impact of different speed flight (13 and 54 km/h) on DEM accuracy.

3.3.3 Results of diverse flying altitudes

Changing the flight altitudes has a great impact on several levels. It affects the sharpness of objects, the scanning area per unit time, the DEM accuracy and the orthophotos resolution, the correlation with true elevation values, Gaussian errors distribution, the number of images required to cover the study area, among other ...

In our experiment, five DEMs for the same study area with different spatial resolution were obtained from UAV at different flight altitudes (50m, 100, 200, 350m, 500m) and a DEM was extracted with total station measurement for validation. This experiment was done incompletely for many dates due to technical and logistical problems such as a battery, wind speed or authorization. However, on March 28th 2017 we achieved the whole tests regarding the flight altitude changes.

3.3.3.1 Texture Sharpness

Several researchers have confirmed the relation between the clearness and the scales (Chang & Tsai, 1991; Wood, 1996; Florinsky & Kuryakova, 2000; Evans, 2003; Hengl, 2006; Arrell et al., 2007; Deng et al., 2007; Pogorelov & Doumit, 2009; Wood, 2009). It is expected that lower altitudes lead to better textures. However, because batteries provide short flight duration, suitable altitude flight that allows sufficient visibility of GCPs is needed. (Figure 77 and Figure 78) clearly, shows the impact of the diverse flight altitudes on the texture visibility and orthophotos raster resolutions. 100 m flight altitude seems to be the best compromise between GCP's enough sharpness, contrast and the area size.

Figure 77: a) Temporal GCPs visibility and contrast on snow cover; b) permanent GCPs visibility and contrast on bare land.

Figure 78: Relation between orthophoto pixel size and flying altitude

3.3.3.2 Flight altitude impact on DEM quality, Scale, covering area, time acquisition and processing

In the previous subsection, it was demonstrated that 100m as flight altitude is the best compromise between GCP's enough sharpness and the maximum covered area, with benefiting of maximum flight time of the battery.

The use of diverse flight altitudes with Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) is leading to different DSMs resolutions, scale (Hengl and Evans 2009; MacMillan and Shary 2009; Doumit and Pogorelov 2018) and accuracy of the point cloud. Point cloud leads to generation of DEMs and orthophotos. Hence, it is expected that lower flights tend to arise the DSM quality (Leitao et al., 2016; Doumit, 2018; Doumit and Pogorelov 2018) and accuracy.

Firstly, proportional increasing DEM pixel size (Table 9 and Figure 79) the flight altitude has been noted. Results show pixel sizes that are equal to 8 cm, 16 cm, 32 cm, 58cm , 84 cm

and GSD⁴⁰ equal to 2, 4.03, 8.24, 14.5, 20.9 cm for flight altitudes of 50 m, 100 m, 200 m, 350 m and 500 m respectively (Table 9). However, notable decreasing of points cloud density per square meter according to increasing of flight altitude has been estimated (Figure 80, Table 9 and Appendix 3). The results show points cloud density varying from 1.43 points/m² (which is sufficient to flat areas) to 156 points/m² (which is very valuable for high slope and extremely change in ground details). The density of points cloud affects directly DSM accuracy at the location of a steep slope (Figure 83 and Figure 84). High altitude flight directly affects the points cloud density and therefore, the raster DSM and the representation of terrain roughness (Figure 83 and Figure 84).

Secondly, almost great linear regression from correlation scatterplots of all the elevation values has been obtained. The correlation was established between UAV DSM at diverse altitudes flights with total station point's elevation measurements (Figure 85). The coefficient of determination R^2 is equal to 99% for all altitudes flights. However, by analyzing the results more deeply, some errors were detected. These showed an increase with flight altitude (Figure 83, Figure 84, Figure 85, Figure 86 and Figure 87). (Figure 87) manifests the location of points errors above |30 cm| (which is quite enough and logical for this study) for all the altitudes flights. Remarkable errors were found on snow cornice location and on the steep slope under it. Going deeper, sample section is created along the study area (Figure 81). (Figure 82) shows a sample section that is selected in the middle of the study area. (Figure 83 and Figure 84) focus on cornice graphic representation with a total station and diverse flight altitudes. Those figures also display how the image sharpness is loose if increasing the flight altitude that was already expected after obtaining the results on (Table 9, Figure 83 and Figure 84).

⁴⁰ Ground Sample Distance

Among all flights altitude used for this test, flight altitude 50 m gave the best clearness terrain texture, GCPs visibility and best representation of relief such as DEM Slope (Figure 88) as it was already expected. However, we cannot forget the advantage of high flight altitude on the covering extended area (Figure 90). High flight altitude provides a larger field of view in comparison to low flight altitude; it will give acceptable results if we do not need visibility for a feature where the variability of slope does not play an important role on the required accuracy. Regarding the benefit from maximum flight time by one battery Figure 91 show sufficient information on possible covered areas according to flight altitude decided and using one battery.

Date	UAV height (m)	DEM Resolution (m)	Points density (points/m ²)	GSD (cm/pix)
28-Mar-17	50	0.08	156	2
	100	0.16	38.4	4.03
	200	0.32	9.2	8.24
	350	0.58	2.96	14.5
	500	0.84	1.43	20.9

Table 9: Pixel size, points density and GSD according to flight altitude

Figure 79: Pixel size according to flight altitude.

Figure 80: point cloud density according to flight altitude.

Figure 81: a) Aerial orthophoto and sample section location on the study area; b) terrestrial picture showing the cornice location and shape

Figure 82: Sample profile number

Figure 83: Comparison of altitude along the sample section extracted from Total Station and UAV at different altitude flight at 50, 100, 200, 350 and 500 meter above the ground.

Figure 84: Zoom in on figure 83.

Figure 85: Scatter plot of correlation between DEM total station and UAV DEM at diverse altitudes: a) 50m, b) 100m, c) 200m d) 350m, e) 500m

Figure 86: Histogram plot of elevation differences (errors) between measured elevation by total station and the DEM extracted by UAV at diverse altitudes flights

Figure 87: location of error above |30 cm| as per each flight altitude

Figure 88: Slope maps for altitude flight 50 and 500m

Figure 89: Accuracy of DEM UAV accuracy extracted from multiple flight altitudes comparing to Total Station measurements.

Figure 90: Example of extending study area with diverse altitudes flights

Figure 91: Maximum covered area at diverse altitudes flights using battery of 14 minutes lifetime flight (case of phantom 3)

3.3.3.3 Flight altitude impact on snow cover volume accuracy

Once the impact of diverse flights altitudes on the DEM quality has been understood, it is important to evaluate its influence on the accuracy of the obtained volume. Without taking into consideration the interpolation impact, we assume that the volume acquired with Total Station's DEM is the reference. Therefore, the volume calculated from each flight altitude is compared with the volumes achieved from the Total station. As mentioned in (Figure 92), very good results were obtained since the percentage of errors ranges from 0.2% to 7 % for flight altitudes equal to 50 m and 500 m respectively.

Figure 92: Accuracy of volume obtained from UAV's DEM extracted from multiple flight altitudes comparing to Total Station measurements.

3.4 Conclusion and discussion of the methods

This part of the chapter answers successfully the question (a) of rational. Time-lapse terrestrial photogrammetry and aerial photogrammetry approaches were validated for snow cover measurement. Although it is weak in providing dense cloud, Total station instrument was an excellent instrument for DEMs validation. Based on time-lapse images from the different steady cameras and respecting some conditions, a combination of ICP and SfM algorithms generates acceptable results. In addition, UAV showed different acceptable DEMs accuracy according to diverse flight altitudes and processing resolution. Developing the above-mentioned ideas, the coming paragraph will explain the advantages and limitations of each approach, in addition to summarizing the evaluation in the (Table 11).

Total station:

Total Station instrument plays a fundamental role in this research. Indeed, every generated DEM, from either terrestrial or aerial photogrammetry was accompanied with Total Station validation. On one hand, Agisoft software provides accurate reports concerning RMSE based on 6 or 9 GCPs. On another hand, ASP provides bias and histogram frequency

errors distribution for the bare land area. Consequently, Agisoft and ASP software do not assess directly the DEM accuracy of snow cover. In this context, Total Station allows having more than 100 points of elevation and well distributed on snow cover. This big number of points allows safe assessment of each generated DEM. Although Total Station has low points density, we are sure of the exactitude of each point's elevation separately.

Additionally, the wide advantage could be noted about using the total station for snow cover mapping. It is a relatively low cost for a small area, providing millimetric accuracy, always useful except during rainfall situation and could freely be used anywhere on the accessible area. Moreover, Total Station becomes important when strong wind prohibits the flying mission or during aerial forces activity, or during snow cover measurement or also when a parasite signal affects drone coordinates positioning by satellites GPS.

Despite all mentioned advantages of using Total Station, this instrument also has some limitations. Total Station requires site visiting. It is hard to carry on back and it needs long topographic process in the absence of geodetic points and direct visibility between Total Station and measured points targets. In addition, Total Station requires manual observations since measures are taken point-by-point offering low density compared to SfM photogrammetry and TLS. Then its use remains limited for small areas. Total Station provides points of elevation without pictures. Therefore, their data do not allow orthophotos creation.

Steady cameras:

Using steady cameras, we presented a new approach for reconstructing snow cover DEMs, based on inclined terrestrial time-lapse photogrammetry system. Many tests were completed: i) processing images without GCPs: this approach was unacceptable since more than 10 m errors were obtained; ii) processing with seven possibilities of GCPs distribution: two of them were highlighted for giving the best results; ii-1) processing with GCPs on snow cover: this distribution has acceptable DEM accuracy with RMSE of 44 cm; however, this required placing GCPs physically for each measured date which is not practical for an automation approach; ii-2) processing with "Framed 6 GCPs upper top line": the distribution was applied and obtained $9 \text{ cm} < \text{RMSE} < 40 \text{ cm}$ that is also acceptable; iii) combination of ICP

and SfM: for this test, two accurate Master DEMs (with terrestrial and aerial photogrammetry) were prepared to be the based map for snow DEM relocation, 14 cm <RMSE <263 cm was obtained and was not acceptable; however, when filtering the dates in order to obtain a big surface of free snow errors, it is reduced to be 14 cm <RMSE <91 cm. However, 2/8 values are more than 50 cm. Therefore, while applying this method for all the season (see: perspective), the decreasing trend will be acceptable.

Despite all errors obtained in the above-mentioned results, time-lapse photogrammetry becomes the only way for automatic snow cover monitoring with high spatio-temporal resolution. A low-cost approach required steady cameras with an electronic system. By the way, it is the first automatic system to obtain a 3D model for snow cover monitoring and it is the most innovative part of this thesis.

In comparison to UAV and Total station, many advantages should be noted. Time-lapse photogrammetry system provides automatic and daily observation. It is based on daily captured pictures that are considered as a wonderful database to understand the behavior of snow melting and calculate the melting speed. Moreover, this system does not require any military authorization like the drone. Besides, the most important advantage of the system is that we do not need to go to the field to take measurements; it is an automatic measurement approach.

Despite all the mentioned advantages of using steady cameras, this system has also some limitations. Steady cameras cover a very small area compared to the Total Station and the drone. In addition, we were restricted by choosing the location of the camera due to the geometry of the study area and the snow accumulation process. The relatively bad camera's location gave some high errors and distortions at study area borders. Either storms or vandal passing humans could also damage this system. Another limitation is noted regarding the weakness of extracting DEM when all sinkhole become covered by snow and no free snow area is visible.

UAV:

Use of diverse flight altitudes, processing resolutions, and speed flight drove us to find suitable parameters to obtain visible orthophotos and accurate DEMs with maximum coverage area. Negligibility of changing speed on DEM accuracy was proven. In addition, using medium accuracy for alignment and medium quality for dense cloud DEM provides mean and standard deviation equal to 4 and 13 cm respectively.

Regarding altitudes flight, five different missions' plans have been done at 50 m, 100 m, 200 m, 350 m, and 500 m. In this context, a study has been conducted on March 28, 2017, and the DEM resolution rose from 8 to 84 cm between 50 and 500m UAV flight altitude with an extremely density decreasing from 156 points/m² to 1.43 points/m² and a GSD proportionally increasing from 2 to 20.9 cm/pix on an area of 0.03 and 1.04 km² respectively as shown in the (Table 10) below.

Date	UAV height (m)	DEM Resolution (m)	Points density (points/m²)	GSD (cm/pix)	area km²
28-Mar-17	50	0.08	156	2	0.232
	100	0.16	38.4	4.03	0.464
	200	0.32	9.2	8.24	0.835
	350	0.58	2.96	14.5	1.256
	500	0.84	1.43	20.9	1.512

Table 10: Impact of UAV altitude flight on DEM resolution, GSD and covered areas

UAV has many advantages: it is relatively low-cost, easy to handle knowing that one conduct person could do missions. UAVs are able to provide centimetric resolution for DEMs and orthophotos. With UAV, we have the ability to fly at different altitudes according to our needed resolution and covered area. Moreover, the created 3D model is satisfactory to realize topography and we can easily draw the snow cover limit based on georeferenced orthophotos. Compared to Steady Cameras and Total Station, UAV have many advantages

for covering a large area, can be used anywhere and is useful for inaccessible and/or dangerous areas. Regarding time, it is much faster than the Total Station. As an example, the sinkhole at Jabal El Dib required around 3 hours of measurement with Total Station. The drone could finalize the mission with less than 7 minutes and one person will be able to make the flight. A highly dense cloud could be provided compared to the Total Station. Indeed, for medium processing 1.43 <points density <156 points/m² could be obtained according to flight altitude, while it is 0.2 points/m² with a Total Station.

Despite all mentioned advantages, UAV also has some limitations. Drone is designed for small areas around 500 m² and a short lifetime battery that is equal to 15 minutes limits it. In addition, UAV can take off and land at the limited open area with autopilot controlling. Moreover, drones require specific authorization from the Directorate of orientation, information, and aerial forces before each flight while respecting the maximum permitted flight according to coordination with general operations of Lebanese aerial forces army. Besides, using drones could be limited by a meteorological condition such as foggy and speed wind. This latter should be less than 15 km/h. Additionally, UAV photogrammetry require a professional operator with the obligation of the sites visiting for taken photos. Furthermore, the processing of images taken required high computer performance and storage. Furthermore, validation of volume obtained from diverse altitude flight has been elaborated. Finally, limitation of this part is that all results are obtained and based on Phantom 3 advanced carrying a 12-megapixel camera. Results could change when using another camera resolution.

Based on all the above discussion, the below (Table 11) summarizes all the advantages and limitations of using Total Station, Steady Cameras, and UAV.

a)	Advantages	Limitations
Total Station	Always useful expected during rainfall situation	Manual measurement
	Low cost for small areas	Small Area
	Very accurate (Millimetric)	Obligation of visiting the site
	Could be used anywhere	Low points density
	No need for authorization	Hard to carry on back
	Ability to generate DEM	Need long topographic process when absence of geodetic points
	Best instrument for validation	Need direct visibility between total station and measured points targets
	Serve during strong wind and aerial military events	Only points elevation obtained
	Important for GCPs measurement and study area preparation	No image or orthophoto provided
Not practical for large area		
3 hours on site		

b)	Advantages	Limitations
Steady Cameras	Automatic and daily observation	Small Area
	Automatic taking photos	Restricted for camera location installation
	Ability to obtain 3D models, orthophoto and DEM	Need maintenance done
	No need visiting the site for monitoring	High errors and distortion to study area border
	Acceptable DEM and orthophoto in term of accuracy	Risk to be damaged by humain
	No need for military license or authorization	Blurry images while storm
	Low cost also	Not efficacy during accumulation season
	Could be applicable without GCPs	

c)	Advantages	Limitations
Drone UAV	Cover larger Area than total Station and Camera	Limited (2 km) distance from remote control
	Taking photos automatically	Short flying time per battery (15 minutes)
	Autopilot mission	Require military authorization
	Could be used anywhere	Require high computer performance and storage
	Useful for inaccessible area	Necessity of low wind speed (less than 15 km/h)
	Centimetric accuracy of DEM and orthophoto	Obligation of visiting the site
	Ability for diverse flight altitude	Require good operator for photogrammetry
	Low cost	Need satellite GDOP
	5 minutes for jabal El Dib study area	

Table 11: Advantages and disadvantages of each instrument; a) Total Station, b) Steady cameras, c) UAV.

Part II: Snow cover analysis and discussion

3.5 Inter-annual fluctuations of snow cover melt

This part aims to answer questions (b) of rational by showing the results of snow cover monitoring from 2012 till 2018 at the studies areas. In this context, it is assumed that every time we make a topographic survey, it represents the snow cover for this specific date because we are working on a dynamic area due to snow melt and accumulation. For that, we were using Total Station and UAV-Drone (Phantom 3 Advanced, Phantom 3 Pro, and Phantom 4 Pro) (see: 2.1 Instrumentations). Every time we make the survey, we measured all the details that give the correct representation of the snow cover either manually by total station or automatically by UAV. By this way, we could draw the needed details after obtaining orthophotos and the snow cover DEMs. Those are the following: exhibiting the limits of the snow and the shape of its cover, its slopes and concavity (Figure 93).

The temporal resolution was around three weeks when we start the precise observations in 2012 and 2013. However, this resolution increased until 1 week from 2015 to 2018.

Figure 93: Snow cover melting monitoring during 2012; colors indicates different dates of measurement (EarthVision®: petroleum suite; software by Dynamic Graphics, Inc., Alameda, CA, USA)

3.5.1 Snow Cover at Jabal El Dib monitoring

Since 2012 until 2018, the study area at Jabal El Dib has been observed accurately with different instruments (Total station, steady cameras and drones). The observation was done during the melting season. Thus, we could observe the snow cover diminution for each year (Figure 94). We have also observed from 2012 to 2018 the snow volume (Figure 95) and snow cover decay behavior from a year to another (Figure 96).

Figure 94: Snow cover monitoring make by drone during 2017 year as example

Figure 95: Annual and Inter annual snow cover volume at Jabal El Dib from 2012 to 2018

Figure 96: Annual and Inter annual snow cover decreasing at Jabal El Dib from 2012 to 2018

In regard to the reduction of the snow cover, it is noteworthy that, whatever the tools of observation are, the behavior shown by the curves is approximately identical for all the years with, however, a difference in time (date) according to the years. In fact, the curves show a rapid linear decrease from the beginning of the melt season followed by a deceleration at the end of the season; this may be due to the compaction of the snow cover that may be makes the snow less vulnerable to the wind effects.

Concerning the year-to-year volume changes at a given moment, it is important to note that:

- in 2018, the volume of the snow cover was 4 times smaller than in 2012;
- at the end of March 2018, the volume was comparable to the volume of May 15th 2017, and June 15 th 2012. The snowmelt is in 2018 and for the considered volume, a month and a half ahead of 2017 and a little over three months ahead of 2012.
- the trend in snow amounts has been decreasing since 2012 (Figure 95 and Figure 96);
- Total melting date of the snow is different from one year to another (Figure 97). It is related to the volume of snow accumulated each year. The dates vary between May and August depending on the years. For example, in 2012 the snow disappeared on August 12th, whereas in 2013, its disappearance was on July 25th. In 2018, the total melt will occur around June 15 (with 10 days more or less).
- Early disappearances confirm and underline the decreasing trend of snow quantities.

Figure 97: Total snowmelt date from 2012 to 2018 at Jabal el Dib area

Total snow melt at Jabal el Dib

The last two graphs (Figure 96 and Figure 97) show the snow volume quantity decreasing. It has almost the same behavior in surface diminution timing from year to another. However, the volume diminution did not record a linear equation it was mostly polynomials of second degree, which makes the early prediction of total snowmelt difficult or sometimes impossible. Thus, we also observed the doline snow area. The following graph (Figure 98) shows inter annual fluctuations of the surfaces of snow cover at Jabal El Dib.

Like for the volume we have obtained almost the same behavior from year to year. However, the behavior for the area is almost linear. Therefore, we can benefit from this result to make a prediction for total snowmelt for the 2018 year. By testing the prediction for the years from 2012 until 2018, we have noted a maximum error of 10 days between the observed and the predicted day of total snowmelt.

Consequently, we have projected the trends obtained from the first three observed points after the last snowfall and we get June 15 as a predicted day of total snowmelt in the sinkhole in Jabal El Dib (Figure 98 and Figure 99).

Figure 98: Inter annual Fluctuations of snow cover surface at Jabal El Dib / Total snow melt projected date— - - -

Figure 99: Snow cover monitoring 2018 at Jabal El Dib area with a prediction of total snowmelt date

3.5.2 Snow cover at Bou Mechleh

Bou Mechleh was considered as a validation site of the results obtained at Jabal el Dib. We focused on the snow volume and surface and their melting behavior. This area was just observed by drone since this technique was well validated. We note that this zone was monitored during the melting season of 2017 and 2018 (Figure 100).

Figure 100: Snow cover monitoring by drone for 2017 and 2018 years at Bou Mechleh area. (Differences between areas with similar snow volumes)

It is notable that there was a same difference and delay in both regions (Jabal El Dib and Bou Mechleh) in 2017, 2018, which is one month and a half (Figure 100 and Figure 101). It is also remarkable that after the last snow accumulation, the cover decreasing behavior is still almost the same from a year to another; however, there is a certain delay or advance in

the dates depending on the accumulation level. When there is more snow, more time is required for snow melting and the total melting has a proportional delay.

Comparing those results with result of Jabal El Dib we note mostly the same behaviors of melting. It starts with a linear behavior at the first, and then occur a deceleration of the shrinkage speed as we can observe at Jabal El dib. Likewise Jabal El dib monitoring, at Bou Mechleh area sample section profile is provided for the observed years (Figure 102). This section show clearly the melting behavior at Bou Mechleh that is very similar to Jabal El Dib despite the timing shifting.

Figure 101: Inter annual Fluctuations of snow cover volume at Bou Mechleh area for 2017 and 2018

Figure 102: Annual and Inter annual snow cover decreasing at Bou Mechleh for 2017 and 2018

3.6 General conclusion of snow melt monitoring

This part of the chapter successfully answers the question (b) of rational. In fact, Total station and UAVs have highly contributed to a systematic and continuous snow cover monitoring from year 2012 to 2018 except 2014. Two study areas were mapped: i) firstly, a pilot sinkhole at Jabal El Dib observed from 2012 to 2015 with total station, while observations of 2016 to 2018 were done combining drone and total station; ii) secondly, Bou Mechleh area was observed with drone during years 2017 and 2018.

At Jabal El dib: Snow melting season for years 2012 and 2013 were monitored every 3 or 4 weeks during master thesis ([Abou Chakra 2013 and Elali 2014](#)). During this recent study, snow evolution was observed every week for years 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018. It was noticed that top of snow cover surface decrease vertically toward the ground, for each observed years. Therefore, monitoring the same area for six years has driven to many benefits as good understanding of aspects of melting behavior. However, this result remains restricted for Jabal El dib pilot sinkhole. This sinkhole is a very small area comparing to whole plateau. Because it is impossible then to generalize results on other areas or at national scale without validation, Bou Mechleh area was selected for validation.

At Bou Mechleh: Therefore, common melting behavior has been observed between Jabal El Dib and Bou Mechleh during commons two years of observation. Those two areas are at 3.5 km horizontal distance and 300m of elevation difference. Snow melting season were observed during 2017 and 2018. Observations confirm that top of snow cover surface decrease vertically like in Jabal El Dib.

Finding same behavior at two areas lead to think that everywhere in the plateau this behavior aspect is the same ([Abou Chakra et al., 2018](#)). That open a door to prediction of total melt date. Then approximate early prediction of total snowmelt has been estimated. Errors of one week have been obtained between observed date and estimated date. The main advantage of the results is that after two weeks of the final snowfall, it is possible to

have idea about the date of total snowmelt. This prediction could be an important indicator for hydrologist, because total melting means the end of groundwater recharge by snow.

At an annual level, a decreasing trend was observed at both of Jabal El dib and Bou Mechleh. We cannot count too much on Bou Mechleh only two years observations results. However, the six years of observation at Jabal El Dib highlight a decreasing trend in snow volume from 2012 to 2018. As example, in 2018 snowmelt totally with an advance of two months comparing to 2012. This changes are indicators of a climatic change (Karam 2018; Abou Chakra et al., 2018) although, precipitation trend is almost stable from 40 years until now (Fayad et al., 2017; Karam 2018). However, rising in temperature cause a shifting from snowfall to rainfall which affect the Lebanese hydrological regime by advancing the low flow date. In fact we can say that rain recharge more quickly aquifers than the slow and longer recharge by snow melt.

With those results question (b) of rational has been answered. All measurements, have well documented the snow cover evolution. However, some limitations are notable. This research did not covered the relationship between snow cover melting and meteorological factors such as temperature, solar radiation, humidity, speed wind and speed direction. Those parameters may explain deeply the reason for early melt. Therefore, further work should aims at realizing snowmelt modeling that take into consideration the volume of a snow cover.

General Conclusion

Snow presents a major component of the hydrological cycle in Lebanon. As part Mediterranean regions, Lebanon is considered as climate change hot spot, because it has the highest mountains in the Middle East. This change is indicated by the temperature rising trend and cause a shifting in hydrological regime from snowfall to rainfall. Consequently, diminution in snow cover leads to a diminution of the most important water reserve in Lebanon. In front of this danger, continuous and systematic observation of this reserve becomes essential.

This study represents the first annual and inters annual monitoring of Lebanese snow cover in a small area using high accurate instruments and new geomatics approaches. In addition, automatic 3D observation of snow covers using time-lapse photogrammetry present the most innovative part of this research. According to our knowledge, this technique has never been applied on snow cover until now. Moreover, this is the first study in Lebanon that used aerial and terrestrial photography and photogrammetry over many years in order to collect data and generate accurate snow mapping. The collected data constitute an important database about Lebanese snow cover at small scale.

Regarding snowfields monitoring, this work demonstrate that the methods used are applicable, financially inexpensive, do not require a big team and that the volumes of the snowfields can be calculated.

The research was mainly divided into two parts: i) finding accurate, easy, low cost technique for snow cover monitoring and ii) demonstrate the interest of data collected to follow snow cover changes at annual and inter annual scale.

i) Snow cover mapping with a total station, steady cameras and UAV has proven to be an excellent tools for snow cover observations. In addition, total station was considered as good instrument for validation.

Steady cameras: with steady cameras, terrestrial time-lapse photogrammetry system has been realized. This system captured pictures on a daily basis. Those were the input data

to generate orthophotos and DEMs. Their processing was done under agisoft Photoscan software relying on SfM algorithm. However, georeferencing orthophotos and DEMs were done using several GCPs distribution or using a Master DEMs with an ICP algorithm. Regarding GCPs distribution tests, "Framed 6 GCPs upper top line" was considered as the best distribution with an RMSE between 28 and 39 cm. While a georeferencing with ICP generate high elevation errors at the beginning of melting season with an RMSE between 14cm and 263m. However, those errors were reduced to an RMSE between 14 and 90 cm when areas free of snow started to appear. Despite the errors, ICP could be used on daily basis because it shows the (decreasing) trend of snow quantities over the years. Steady cameras remains the best option for automatic low cost observation. In addition, tested cases offer the best compromise between snow DEMs accuracy and benefiting of maximum possible days of snowmelt observation.

UAV: UAV was the best instrument to extend the study area and it allows wide overviews. As example Bou Mechleh area was almost impossible or extremely expensive to be monitored with total station or steady cameras in regards to its larger surface and hard physical accessibility. Moreover, monitoring of Bou Mechleh area with total station required at least 20 hours of working survey for each time, while it took less than 17 minutes with UAV. Monitoring of Bou Mechleh area was very important in this study to compare its melting behavior with Jabal El dib. Furthermore, UAV serve monitoring of surrounding area of Jabal El Dib because it provide a proof that the pilot site could be representative of trends in nearby areas.

Regarding flight parameters such as speed and diverse flight altitude of UAV, numerous tests has been done. Acceptable mean and standard deviation has been obtained for all flight altitudes. However, many GCPs visibility problems were found for flight altitudes above 100m. Therefore, when we are looking for georeferencing using GCPs, a flight at 100 m of altitude become acceptable. While georeferencing based on the DEM master could be possible with a flight of 500m altitude if weather conditions are good. Therefore, testing

parameters (processing, altitude flight and speed) changes of UAV flight provide practical manual for further easy and powerful survey according to the needed accuracy.

ii) Regarding snow cover monitoring, two important results were obtained: Firstly, remarkable common melting behavior is obtained between Jabal El Dib and Bou Mechleh, that highlights the possibility of generalizing the snowmelt model (see: perspective) to larger areas and then to national scale. In addition, it has been demonstrate also that the snow cover decreasing can be used to predict melting date. Secondly, decreasing trend on snow volume from 2012 to 2018 cause an advance of the date of total snowmelt. As example, observations of 2018 shows a significant advance in volume and surface decrease and a deficit in snow quantity compared to previous years. That is pointing to the need and necessity to maintain a snow observatory.

We can say at the end of all our samplings and processing work that we have establish a field work protocol for monitoring a snow cover. As many possibilities in the field were tested and evaluated, next survey using the best procedures used will be easy and rapid.

Limits of this thesis

The scientific approach of the study answered to rational questions. However, some limitations are notable. On one hand, for: i) terrestrial photogrammetry, specific cameras were used at a specific pilot sinkhole with a location and shape dimension, therefore, obtained results are applicable to those specific cameras and sinkhole characteristics; ii) aerial photogrammetry, DJI Phantom 3 advanced are used for testing parameters flight, therefore, obtained results are applicable to this drone that hold a 12 megapixel camera. On the other hand, although vertical parallel melt behavior was notable for all observed years and areas, however, the melting speed is probably related to meteorological conditions (Fayad 2017; Fayad et al., 2017). Snow compaction may play also an important role in snowmelt speed, as decreasing curves shows a slow down at the end of the melting season. Additionally, output orthophotos and DEMs extracted with steady cameras were just used

to be validated by Total Station instrument. Consequently, further work should focus on automation process to have an operational system (see: perspectives)

Perspectives

In regards of all of the research and its limitations, four perspectives could be important:

- Since steady camera's results were just used some days for validation, it will be important to automate the series of all the seasons. This automation should be done for all series since 2015 until the coming years, for a continuous observatory for Lebanon. Additionally, it will be important to have online access to the captured daily images. Thus, real time snow volume could be estimated.
- This research was based on snow cover measurement, without taking to consideration the meteorological conditions. Estimated volumes during the years of observation (2012, 2013, 2015, 2016, 2017 and 2018) could present an important factor with AWS data to realized reliable snowmelt modeling. Consequently, snow measurement for this thesis, will be one of the most important factors to realize snowmelt modeling based on volumes and meteorological data. Those latter at Jabal El Dib area, are well acknowledged due the installed AWS by IRD-CESBIO as part of Olife project and Lebanese snow observatory composed of USJ, IRD-CESBIO and CNRS-L research teams.
- Due to limitation of using UAV without using GCPs, national Lebanese DEM done by Lebanese army (DAG) with a spatial resolution between 50 and 150 cm, could be a good solution. ICP algorithm rely on a master DEM to relocate other DEMs. In this context, DEM done by DAG could be considered as master DEM. Therefore, we could have the flexibility to flight UAV anywhere at any altitude. Then, extracted from DEM from UAV will relocate using the national master DEM that done by DAG. This

approach will allow aerial snow cover monitoring anywhere and could omit physical GCPs placing.

- Observations in this study focused on karstic areas characterized by sinkholes. In fact, we were interested on estimating HS, surface and volume of snow cover. On one hand, snow cover surface could be easily estimated through 2D satellite imagery. As example, imagery provided by “Planet” website, were sufficient for high spatio-temporal resolution monitoring ([Abou Chakra et al., 2018](#)). On the other hand, calculating volume and HS, required 3D stereoscopic imagery. This latter is very expensive comparing to 2D satellite imagery. In this perspective, deepen relationship between the volumes and the surfaces of the snow cover will be helpful for snow cover observation at national scale.

Bibliography

- Abdullah Q, Bethel J, Hussain M, Munjy R. (2013). Photogrammetric project and mission planning. In *Manual of Photogrammetry*, McGlone JC (ed.). American Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing: Bethesda, MD; 1187–1220.
- Abou Chakra C., Somma J., Drapeau L., Fanise P., Gascoin S. (2018). Suivis annuels des névés sur les hauts plateaux du Mont-Liban. Effets des fluctuations du couvert neigeux sur la période de sécheresse. *Seminaire sur la neige et l'hydrologie (en collaboration entre le CREEN, le Département de Géographie (USJ) et l'UNICEF)*, ESIB, 15 Mai 2018.
- Abou Chakra C. (2013). Suivi topographique de la fonte des neiges : étude d'une doline des plateaux de Jabal el Dib (Ouyoun el Simane, Mont-Liban). *Mémoire de Master, université Saint Joseph*.
- Abou Chakra C., Somma J., Drapeau L., Fanise P., Gascoin S., el Ali T., Assaf B. (2015). Precision estimation of snow volumes by terrestrial measures. Communication aux «Troisièmes journées Franco-Libanaises »
- Abou Chakra C., Somma J., Drapeau L., Doumit J. (2016). Snow Cover Digital Elevation Models Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle and Total Station. *Communication au colloque Promitheas*, Athènes, 12-14octobre.
- Abhayapala, R., De Costa, J., Malaviarachchi, W., Kumara, A., Suriyagoda, L., & Fonseka, R. (2018): Exploitation of differential temperature-sensitivities of crops for improved resilience of tropical smallholder cropping systems to climate change: A case study with temperature responses of tomato and chilli. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, 261, 103–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AGEE.2017.10.027>
- Agisoft LLC. (2016). Agisoft PhotoScan User Manual. *Professional Edition, Version 1.2*, 37. Retrieved from www.agisoft.ru
- Agisoft PhotoScan User Manual - Professional Edition, Version 1.2. (2015). Retrieved from http://www.agisoft.com/pdf/photoscan-pro_1_2_en.pdf
- Agüera-Vega, F., Carvajal-Ramírez, F., & Martínez-Carricondo, P. (2016). Assessment of photogrammetric mapping accuracy based on variation ground control points number using unmanned aerial vehicle. *Measurement: Journal of the International Measurement Confederation*, 98, 221–227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2016.12.002>
- Anderson, J.A. (2008). ISIS camera model design. In: 39th Lunar and Planetary Science Conference Abstracts, p. 2159.
- Aouad Rizk, A., Job, Jean.-olivier., Khalil, S., Touma, T., Bitar, C., Bocquillon, C., Najem, W. (2005). Snow in Lebanon: a preliminary study of snow cover over Mount Lebanon and a simple snowmelt model. *Hydrol. Sci. J.* 50, 555–569.
- Aouad, A., Travi, Y., Blavoux, B., Job, J.-O., & Najem, W. (2004). Etude isotopique de la pluie

- et de la neige sur le Mont Liban: premiers résultats / Isotope study of snow and rain on Mount Lebanon: preliminary results. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 49(3). <https://doi.org/10.1623/hysj.49.3.429.54341>
- Arango, C., & Morales, C. A. (2015). Comparison between multicopter UAV and total station for estimating stockpile volumes. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences - ISPRS Archives*, 40(1W4), 131–135. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-1-W4-131-2015>
- Arrell, K. E., Fisher, P. F., Tate, N. J., & Bastin, L. (2007). A fuzzy c-means classification of elevation derivatives to extract the morphometric classification of landforms in Snowdonia, Wales. *Computers & Geosciences*, 33(10), 1366–1381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CAGEO.2007.05.005>
- Asadi Zarch, M. A., Sivakumar, B., Malekinezhad, H., & Sharma, A. (2017). Future aridity under conditions of global climate change. *Journal of Hydrology*, 554, 451–469. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHYDROL.2017.08.043>
- Balaguer-Puig, M., Marqués-Mateu, Á., Lerma, J. L., & Ibáñez-Asensio, S. (2017). Estimation of small-scale soil erosion in laboratory experiments with Structure from Motion photogrammetry. *Geomorphology*, 295, 285–296. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2017.04.035>
- Barabant, M. (2003). Maitriser la topographie, des observations au plan. *Groupe Eyrolles, Paris*, 542 pages
- Barnett, T. P., Adam, J. C., & Lettenmaier, D. P. (2005). Potential impacts of a warming climate on water availability in snow-dominated regions. *Nature*, 438(7066), 303–309. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature04141>
- Barry, P., & Coakley, R. (2013). Accuracy of UAV Photogrammetry compared with Network RTK GPS. *Baseline Surveys Ltd*. Retrieved from <http://www.irlogi.ie/wp-content/uploads/2013/10/Field-Accuracy-of-RPAS-Photogrammetry-Paudie-Barry.pdf>
- Bento, L. C., Bonnifait, P., & Nunes, U. J. (2017). Cooperative GNSS positioning aided by road-features measurements. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 79, 42–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2017.01.002>
- Berghuijs, W. R., R. A. Woods, and Hrachowitz, M. (2014). A precipitation shift from snow towards rain leads to a decrease in streamflow, *Nat. Clim. Change*, 4(7), 583–586, [doi:10.1038/nclimate2246](https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2246).
- Bernier, M., Fortin, J.-P., Gauthier, Y., Carbane, C., Somma, J., & Dedieu, J. P. (2003). Intégration de données satellitaires à la modélisation hydrologique du Mont Liban. *Hydrological Sciences*, 48(6), 999–1112. <https://doi.org/10.1623/hysj.48.6.999.51428>.
- Bitar, C. (2002). Equivalent en eau de la neige sur le Mont Liban. Mémoire de DEA, Université St Joseph, Centre Régional de l'Eau et de l'Environnement, Beyrouth, Liban, 54 P.
- Bormann, K., Westra, S., Evans, J., McCabe, M. (2013). Spatial and temporal variability in

- seasonal snow density. *J. Hydrol.* 484, 63–73.
- Bretar, F., Arab-Sedze, M., Champion, J., Pierrot-Deseilligny, M., Heggy, E., Jacquemoud, S. (2013). An advanced photogrammetric method to measure surface roughness: Application to volcanic terrains in the Piton de la Fournaise, Reunion Island. *Remote Sens. Environ.* 135, 1– 11. doi:10.1016/j.rse.2013.03.026.
- Broxton, M. J., Nefian, A. V., Moratto, Z., Kim, T., Lundy, M., & Segal, A. V. (2009). 3D Lunar Terrain Reconstruction from Apollo Images (pp. 710–719). Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-10331-5_66
- Bründl, M., Etter, H.-J., Steiniger, M., Klingler, C., Rhyner, J., & Ammann, W. J. (2004). IFKIS - a basis for managing avalanche risk in settlements and on roads in Switzerland. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Science*, 4(2), 257–262. <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-4-257-2004>
- Brunier, G., Fleury, J., Anthony, E. J., Gardel, A., & Dussouillez, P. (2016). Close-range airborne Structure-from-Motion Photogrammetry for high-resolution beach morphometric surveys: Examples from an embayed rotating beach. *Geomorphology*, 261, 76–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2016.02.025>
- Bühler, Y., Marty, M., Egli, L., Veitinger, J., Jonas, T., Thee, P., & Ginzler, C. (2015). Snow depth mapping in high-alpine catchments using digital photogrammetry. *Cryosphere*, 9(1), 229–243. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-9-229-2015>
- Bühler, Y., Marty, M., & Ginzler, C. (2012). High Resolution DEM Generation in High-Alpine Terrain Using Airborne Remote Sensing Techniques. *Transactions in GIS*, 16(5), 635–647. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9671.2012.01331.x>
- Capuano, V., Shehaj, E., Blunt, P., Botteron, C., & Farine, P. A. (2017). High accuracy GNSS based navigation in GEO. *Acta Astronautica*, 136(October 2016), 332–341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actaastro.2017.03.014>
- Carrivick, J.L., Smith, M.W., Quincey, D.J. (2016). *Structure from Motion in the Geosciences*. Wiley- Blackwell, Chichester, UK. doi:10.1002/9781118895818
- Casella E, Rovere A, Pedroncini A, et al. (2014). Study of wave runup using numerical models and low-altitude aerial photogrammetry: A tool for coastal management. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science* 149: 160–167.
- Che, T., Dai, L., Wang, J., Zhao, K., & Liu, Q. (2011). Estimation of snow depth and snow water equivalent distribution using airborne microwave radiometry in the Binggou Watershed, the upper reaches of the Heihe River basin. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 17(1), 23–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2011.10.014>
- Corbane, C., Somma, J., Bernier, M., Fortin, J.-P., Dedieu, J.-P., & Gauthier, Y. (2004). Application d'un modèle d'estimation de l'équivalent en eau du couvert nival à partir d'images RSO de RADARSAT-1 en montagne libanaise. *Téledétection*, 4, 1–18.

- Cimoli, E. (2015). Determining Snow Depth Distribution from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles and Digital Photogrammetry. *MSc Thesis, Technical*.
- Cimoli, E. & Marcer, M. (2014). Digital Elevation Model Reconstruction of a Glaciarized Basin Using Land- Based Structure from Motion, Copenhagen: Arctic Technology Centre.
- Cimoli, E., Marcer, M., Vandecrux, B., Bøggild, C. E., Williams, G., & Simonsen, S. B. (2017). Application of low-cost uass and digital photogrammetry for high-resolution snow depth mapping in the Arctic. *Remote Sensing*, *9*(11), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9111144>
- Clark, D. R., Meffert, C., Baggili, I., & Breitingner, F. (2017). DROP (DRone Open source Parser) your drone: Forensic analysis of the DJI Phantom III. *Digital Investigation*, *22*, S3–S14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.diin.2017.06.013>
- Cline, D. W. (1993). Measuring Alpine Snow Depths by Digital Photogrammetry - Part 1: Conjugate Point Identification. *Proceedings 50th Eastern Snow Conference, Quebec*.
- Corbane, C., Somma, J., Bernier, M., Fortin, J. P., Gauthier, Y., & Dedieu, J. P. (2005). Estimation de L’e?quivalent en Eau du Couvert Nival en Montagne Libanaise a? Partir des Images RADARSAT-1/Estimation of Water Equivalent of the Snow Cover in Lebanese Mountains by Means of RADARSAT-1 Images. *Hydrological Sciences Journal/Journal Des Sciences Hydrologiques*, *50*(2), 355–370. <https://doi.org/10.1623/hysj.50.2.355.60657>
- d’Oleire-Oltmanns, S., Marzloff, I., Peter, K., & Ries, J. (2012). Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) for Monitoring Soil Erosion in Morocco. *Remote Sensing*, *4*(11), 3390–3416. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs4113390>
- Deems, J., Painter, T., Glaciology, D. F.-J. (2013). Lidar measurement of snow depth: a review. *Cambridge.Org*. Retrieved from <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/journal-of-glaciology/article/lidar-measurement-of-snow-depth-a-review/4419DF5C778946103080CB6187D434C0>
- Delacourt, C., Allemand, P., Jaud, M., Grandjean, P., Deschamps, A., Ammann, J., ... Suanez, S. (2009). DRELIO: An Unmanned Helicopter for Imaging Coastal Areas. *Journal of Coastal Research*. Coastal Education & Research Foundation, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.2307/25738037>
- Deng, Y., Wilson, J. P., & Bauer, B. O. (2007). DEM resolution dependencies of terrain attributes across a landscape. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, *21*(2), 187–213. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13658810600894364>
- Déry, S. J., & Brown, R. D. (2007). Recent Northern Hemisphere snow cover extent trends and implications for the snow-albedo feedback. *Geophysical Research Letters*, *34*(22), L22504. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2007GL031474>
- Dettinger, M. (2014). Impacts in the third dimension. *Nature Geoscience*, *7*(3), 166–167. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2096>
- Dietrich, J. T. (2016). Riverscape mapping with helicopter-based Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry. *Geomorphology*, *252*, 144–157.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2015.05.008>

- Doumit, J. A. (2018). Multiscale Landforms Classification Based on UAV Datasets, *3*(2), 128–141. <https://doi.org/10.22158/se.v3n2p128>
- Doumit, J. A., & Pogorelov, A. V. (2018). Multi-scale Analysis of Digital Surface Models Based on UAV Datasets. *Modern Environmental Science and Engineering*, *03*(07), 460–468. [https://doi.org/10.15341/mese\(2333-2581\)/07.03.2017/004](https://doi.org/10.15341/mese(2333-2581)/07.03.2017/004)
- Dowling, T. I., & Gallant, J. C. (2013). High Resolution DEMs from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles. *20th International Congress on Modelling and Simulation*, (December), 1–6. Retrieved from www.mssanz.org.au/modsim2013.
- Dozier, J., Bair, E., Davis, R. (2016). Estimating the spatial distribution of snow water equivalent in the world's mountains. *Wiley Interdis. Rev. Water* *3*, 461–474.
- Drapeau L., Shaban A., Somma J. (2013). Pour un observatoire de la neige au Liban. L'eau face au changement climatique. Séminaire présenté à l'IFPO (Institut Français pour le Proche Orient), mars.
- Duraffourd M. C. (1930). Rapport sur les travaux de triangulation poursuivis dans les états de SYRIE, du LIBAN et des ALAOUITES sous le mandat Français en vue de l'établissement du CADASTRE. *Paris Au secretariat de la section 78, Rue D'ANJOU* (8) 80 pages.
- Egli L. (2008). Spatial variability of new snow amounts derived from a dense network of Alpine automatic stations. *Annals of Glaciology* *49*: 51–55. DOI: [10.3189/172756408787814843](https://doi.org/10.3189/172756408787814843).
- Eisenbeiss, H. (2009). UAV photogrammetry. Retrieved from <https://www.research-collection.ethz.ch/handle/20.500.11850/20976>
- Eisenbeiss, H., & Zhang, L. (2006). Comparison of DSMs generated from mini UAV imagery and terrestrial laser scanner in a cultural heritage application. *International Archives of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, *36*(5), 90–96. <https://doi.org/10.1.1.221.8350>
- El-Fadel, M., Zeinati, M., & Jamali, D. (2000). Water Resources in Lebanon: Characterization, Water Balance and Constraints. *International Journal of Water Resources Development*, *16*(4), 615–638. <https://doi.org/10.1080/713672540>
- Elali T. (2014). Suivi topographique de la fonte des neiges : étude d'une doline des plateaux de Jabal el Dib (Ouyoun el Simane, Mont-Liban). *Mémoire de Master, université Saint Joseph*
- El-Fadel, M., Zeinati, M., Water, D. J.-I. J. (2000). Water resources in Lebanon: Characterization, water balance and constraints. *Iahr.Tandfonline.Com*. Retrieved from <http://iahr.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/713672540>.
- El Hage, M., Faour, G., Polidori, L. (2011). The impact of the elevation of the sea level (2000-2100) on the shore of Lebanon A remote sensing and diachronic mapping approche.

- El Hage, M., Simonetto, E., Faour, G., & Polidori, L. (2012). Evaluation of Elevation, Slope and Stream Network Quality of Spot Dems. *ISPRS Annals of Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 1-2(September), 63–67. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsannals-1-2-63-2012>
- Eltner, A., & Baumgart, P. (2015). Accuracy constraints of terrestrial Lidar data for soil erosion measurement: Application to a Mediterranean field plot. *Geomorphology*, 245, 243–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2015.06.008>
- Eltner, A., Kaiser, A., Abellan, A., & Schindewolf, M. (2017). Time lapse structure-from-motion photogrammetry for continuous geomorphic monitoring. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 42(14), 2240–2253. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4178>
- Evans, I. S. (2003). Scale-Specific Landforms and Aspects of the Land Surface, 61–84. Retrieved from <https://www.terrapub.co.jp/e-library/ohmori/pdf/061.pdf>.
- Fassett, C.I. (2016). Ames stereo pipeline-derived digital terrain models of mercury from MESSENGER stereo imaging. *Planet. Space Sci.*
- Fayad, A. (2017). Evaluation of the snow water resources in Mount Lebanon using observations and modelling Abbas Fayad To cite this version : HAL Id : tel-01755397.
- Fayad, A., Gascoin, S., Faour, G., Fanise, P., Drapeau, L., Somma, J., Escadafal, R. (2017). Snow observations in Mount-Lebanon (2011-2016). Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313890191_Snow_observations_in_Mount-Lebanon_2011-2016/fulltext/58ade590aca2725b540ddb0b/313890191_Snow_observations_in_Mount-Lebanon_2011-2016.pdf?origin=publication_detail
- Fayad, A., Gascoin, S., Faour, G., López-Moreno, J. I., Drapeau, L., Page, M. Le, & Escadafal, R. (2017). Snow hydrology in Mediterranean mountain regions: A review. *Journal of Hydrology*, 551, 374–396. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2017.05.063>
- Fawaz, M. (2009). Towards a Water Policy in Lebanon. ESIB, Beirut, Lebanon, p. 259(in Arabic)
- Florinsky, I. V., & Kuryakova, G. A. (2000). Determination of grid size for digital terrain modelling in landscape investigations—exemplified by soil moisture distribution at a micro-scale. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 14(8), 815–832. <https://doi.org/10.1080/136588100750022804>
- Fonstad, M. A., Dietrich, J. T., Courville, B. C., Jensen, J. L., & Carbonneau, P. E. (2013). Topographic structure from motion: a new development in photogrammetric measurement. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 38(4), 421–430. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3366>
- Furukawa, Y., Curless, B., Seitz, S. M., & Szeliski, R. (2010). Towards Internet-scale multi-view stereo. In *2010 IEEE Computer Society Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* (pp. 1434–1441). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CVPR.2010.5539802>
- Furukawa, Y., & Ponce, J. (2007). Accurate, Dense, and Robust Multi-View Stereopsis.

Retrieved from http://willow.ai.uiuc.edu/ponce_grp/publication/paper/cvpr07a.pdf

- Gabrlik, P. (2015). The use of direct georeferencing in aerial photogrammetry with micro UAV. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 28(4), 380–385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2015.07.064>
- Gago, J., Douthe, C., Coopman, R. E., Gallego, P. P., Ribas-Carbo, M., Flexas, J., ... Medrano, H. (2015). UAVs challenge to assess water stress for sustainable agriculture. *Agricultural Water Management*, 153, 9–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2015.01.020>
- Gandor, F., Rehak, M., & Skaloud, J. (2013). PHOTOGRAMMETRIC MISSION PLANNER FOR RPAS. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-1-W4-61-2015>
- Gao, Y., Gao, X., & Zhang, X. (2017). The 2 °C Global Temperature Target and the Evolution of the Long-Term Goal of Addressing Climate Change—From the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change to the Paris Agreement. *Engineering*, 3(2), 272–278. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENG.2017.01.022>
- Garvelmann, J., Pohl, S., & Weiler, M. (2013). From observation to the quantification of snow processes with a time-lapse camera network. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 17(4), 1415–1429. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-17-1415-2013>
- Geara, D. (Leesu/Université P.-E., Moilleron, R. (Leesu/Université P.-E., El Samarani, A. (Lebanese A. E. C., Lorgeoux, C. (Leesu/Université P.-E., & Chebbo, G. (Faculty of E. U. (2010). State of Art About Water Uses and Wastewater Management in Lebanon. *Lebanese Science Journal*, 11(2), 139–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/1geoforum.2008.11.002>
- Ghilani, C. D. (2012.). *Elementary surveying : an introduction to geomatics*.
- Gindraux, S., Boesch, R., & Farinotti, D. (2017). Accuracy assessment of digital surface models from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles' imagery on glaciers. *Remote Sensing*, 9(2), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9020186>
- Giorgi, F. (2006). Climate change projections for the Mediterranean region. *Elsevier*. Retrieved from <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0921818107001750>
- Giorgi, F., & Lionello, P. (2008). Climate change projections for the Mediterranean region. *Global and Planetary Change*, 63(2–3), 90–104. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GLOPLACHA.2007.09.005>.
- Goodison, P., Louie, P. Y. T. and Yang, D. (1998). WMO solid precipitation measurement intercomparison final report. WMO/TD-No. 872, IOM No. 67, World Meteorological Organization, 212 p.
- Gómez-Gutiérrez, Á., Schnabel, S., Berenguer-Sempere, F., Lavado-Contador, F., Rubio-Delgado, J. (2014). Using 3D photo-reconstruction methods to estimate gully headcut erosion. *Catena* 120, 91–101. doi:10.1016/j.catena.2014.04.004.
- Gonçalves, J. A., & Henriques, R. (2015). UAV photogrammetry for topographic monitoring of coastal areas. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 104, 101–111.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ISPRSJPRS.2015.02.009>

- Goulden, M., National, R. B.-P. (2014). Mountain runoff vulnerability to increased evapotranspiration with vegetation expansion. *National Acad Sciences*. Retrieved from <http://www.pnas.org/content/111/39/14071.short>
- Grünewald, T., Schirmer, M., Mott, R., & Lehning, M. (2010). Spatial and temporal variability of snow depth and ablation rates in a small mountain catchment. *The Cryosphere*, 4(2), 215–225. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-4-215-2010>
- Gruszczynski, W., Matwij, W., & Cwiakala, P. (2017). Comparison of low-altitude UAV photogrammetry with terrestrial laser scanning as data-source methods for terrain covered in low vegetation. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 126, 168–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprs.2017.02.015>
- Guan, B., Waliser, D. E., Ralph, F. M., Fetzner, E. J., & Neiman, P. J. (2016). Hydrometeorological characteristics of rain-on-snow events associated with atmospheric rivers. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 43(6), 2964–2973. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016GL067978>
- Guo, F., Li, X., Zhang, X., & Wang, J. (2016). The contribution of Multi-GNSS Experiment (MGEX) to precise point positioning. *Advances in Space Research*, 59(11), 2714–2725. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asr.2016.05.018>
- Harder, P., Schirmer, M., Pomeroy, J., & Helgason, W. (2016). ACCURACY OF SNOW DEPTH ESTIMATION IN MOUNTAIN AND PRAIRIE ENVIRONMENTS BY AN UNMANNED AERIAL VEHICLE. *The Cryosphere Discussions*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-2016-9>
- Harpold, A. A., Molotch, N. P., Musselman, K. N., Bales, R. C., Kirchner, P. B., Litvak, M., & Brooks, P. D. (2015). Soil moisture response to snowmelt timing in mixed-conifer subalpine forests. *Hydrological Processes*, 29(12), 2782–2798. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10400>
- Harwin, S., & Lucieer, A. (2012). Assessing the Accuracy of Georeferenced Point Clouds Produced via Multi-View Stereopsis from Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) Imagery. *Remote Sensing*, 4(6), 1573–1599. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs4061573>
- He, Y., Liang, B., Yang, J., Li, S., & He, J. (2017). An Iterative Closest Points Algorithm for Registration of 3D Laser Scanner Point Clouds with Geometric Features. *Sensors*, 17(8), 1862. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s17081862>
- Hengl, T. (2006). Finding the right pixel size. *Computers & Geosciences*, 32, 1283–1298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2005.11.008>
- Hengl, T., & Evans, I. S. (2009). Chapter 2 Mathematical and Digital Models of the Land Surface (pp. 31–63). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481\(08\)00002-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481(08)00002-0)
- Hill, D. L. G., Batchelor, P. G., Holden, M., & Hawkes, D. J. (2001). Medical image registration. *Physics in Medicine and Biology*, 46(3), R1–R45. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0031-9155/46/3/201>

- Immerzeel, W. W., Kraaijenbrink, P. D. A., Shea, J. M., Shrestha, A. B., Pellicciotti, F., Bierkens, M. F. P., & de Jong, S. M. (2014). High-resolution monitoring of Himalayan glacier dynamics using unmanned aerial vehicles. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, *150*, 93–103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2014.04.025>
- Irschara, A., Irschara, A., B, V. K., A, M. K., A, H. B., & A, F. L. (2010). Towards fully automatic photogrammetric reconstruction using digital images taken from UAVs. *IN PROC. INTERNATIONAL SOCIETY FOR PHOTOGRAMMETRY AND REMOTE SENSING SYMPOSIUM*. Retrieved from <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/summary?doi=10.1.1.420.8067>
- James, M. R., & Robson, S. (2012). Straightforward reconstruction of 3D surfaces and topography with a camera: Accuracy and geoscience application. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Earth Surface*, *117*(F3), n/a-n/a. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2011JF002289>
- James, M. R., & Robson, S. (2014). Mitigating systematic error in topographic models derived from UAV and ground-based image networks. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, *39*(10), 1413–1420. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3609>
- James, M. R., Robson, S., d'Oleire-Oltmanns, S., & Niethammer, U. (2016). Optimising UAV topographic surveys processed with structure-from-motion: Ground control quality, quantity and bundle adjustment. *Geomorphology*, *280*, 51–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2016.11.021>
- Javernick, L., Brasington, J., & Caruso, B. (2014). Modeling the topography of shallow braided rivers using Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry. *Geomorphology*, *213*, 166–182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2014.01.006>
- Job, J.-O., Khalil, S., Bocquillon, C. & Najem, W. (2002). DKM: un modèle de fonte de la neige pour le Mont Liban. First Int. Seminar on Snow Hydrology in Mediterranean Regions (Beirut, 15–17 December 2002) (unpublished).
- Jonas, T., Marty, C., & Magnusson, J. (2009). Estimating the snow water equivalent from snow depth measurements in the Swiss Alps. *Journal of Hydrology*, *378*(1–2), 161–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JHYDROL.2009.09.021>
- Kapnick, S. B., & Delworth, T. L. (2013). Controls of Global Snow under a Changed Climate. *Journal of Climate*, *26*(15), 5537–5562. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-12-00528.1>
- Kępski, D., Luks, B., Migala, K., Wawrzyniak, T., Westermann, S., & Wojtuń, B. (2017). Terrestrial Remote Sensing of Snowmelt in a Diverse High-Arctic Tundra Environment Using Time-Lapse Imagery. *Remote Sensing*, *9*(7), 733. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9070733>
- Kaiser, A., Neugirg, F., Rock, G., Müller, C., Haas, F., Ries, J., Schmidt, J. (2014). Small-scale surface reconstruction and volume calculation of soil erosion in complex moroccan Gully morphology using structure from motion. *Remote Sens.* *6*, 7050–7080. [doi:10.3390/rs6087050](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs6087050)
- Karam G, (2018) : changement climatique à l'échelle locale : cas de la plaine de la Béqaa au Liban. Thèse présentée en vue de l'obtention du doctorat, université Saunt-Joseph,

Beyrouth, 399p.

- Khalil, S. (2002). Modelisation de la fonte des neige sur le Mont Liban. Mémoire de DEA, Université St Joseph, Centre Régional de l'Eau et de l'Environnement, Beyrouth, Liban.
- Kinab, E., & Elkhoury, M. (2012). Renewable energy use in Lebanon: Barriers and solutions. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 16(7), 4422–4431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.04.030>
- Kleber, E., Nissen, E., & Arrowsmith, J. R. (2013). Topographic Change Detection Using CloudCompare, 1–13.
- Krsak, B., Blistan, P., Paulikova, A., Puskarova, P., Kovanic, L., Palkova, J., & Zeliznakova, V. (2016). Use of low-cost UAV photogrammetry to analyze the accuracy of a digital elevation model in a case study. *Measurement: Journal of the International Measurement Confederation*, 91, 276–287. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2016.05.028>
- Kumar, S., Zwiers, F., Dirmeyer, P. A., Lawrence, D. M., Shrestha, R., & Werner, A. T. (2016). Terrestrial contribution to the heterogeneity in hydrological changes under global warming. *Water Resources Research*, 52(4), 3127–3142. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2016WR018607>
- Kyselý, J., Beguería, S., Beranová, R., Gaál, L., & López-Moreno, J. I. (2012). Different patterns of climate change scenarios for short-term and multi-day precipitation extremes in the Mediterranean. *Global and Planetary Change*, 98–99, 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloplacha.2012.06.010>
- Lavine, A., Gardner, J. N., & Reneau, S. L. (2003). Total station geologic mapping: An innovative approach to analyzing surface-faulting hazards. *Engineering Geology*, 70(1–2), 71–91. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-7952\(03\)00083-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0013-7952(03)00083-8)
- Leitão, J. P., Moy De Vitry, M., Scheidegger, A., & Rieckermann, J. (2016). Assessing the quality of digital elevation models obtained from mini unmanned aerial vehicles for overland flow modelling in urban areas. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 20(4), 1637–1653. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-20-1637-2016>
- Levoy, M., Pulli, K., Curless, B., Rusinkiewicz, S., Koller, D., Pereira, L., ... Fulk, D. (2000). The Digital Michelangelo Project: 3D Scanning of Large Statues. Retrieved from <http://graphics.stanford.edu/projects/mich/>
- Li, K. (Computer scientist), Xue, Y., Cui, S., Niu, Q. (Computer scientist), Yang, Z., Luk, P., & International Conference on Intelligent Computing for Sustainable Energy and Environment. (2016). Nanjing Shi, C. (n.d.). *Advanced computational methods in energy, power, electric vehicles, and their integration : International Conference on Life System Modeling and Simulation, LSMS 2017 and International Conference on Intelligent Computing for Sustainable Energy and Environment, ICSEE 2017, Nanjing, China, September 22-24, 2017, Proceedings. Part III.*
- Loarie, S. R., Duffy, P. B., Hamilton, H., Asner, G. P., Field, C. B., & Ackerly, D. D. (2009). The

- velocity of climate change. *Nature*, 462(7276), 1052–1055. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature08649>
- López-Moreno, J. I., & Nogués-Bravo, D. (2005). A generalized additive model for the spatial distribution of snowpack in the Spanish Pyrenees. *Hydrological Processes*, 19(16), 3167–3176. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.5840>
- López-Moreno, J. I., & Nogués-Bravo, D. (2006). Interpolating local snow depth data: an evaluation of methods. *Hydrological Processes*, 20(10), 2217–2232. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.6199>
- López-Moreno, J. I., Vicente-Serrano, S. M., Moran-Tejeda, E., Zabalza, J., Lorenzo-Lacruz, J., & García-Ruiz, J. M. (2010). Impact of climate evolution and land use changes on water yield in the Ebro basin. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, 7(2), 2651–2681. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hessd-7-2651-2010>
- Lowe, D. G. (2004). Distinctive Image Features from Scale-Invariant Keypoints. *International Journal of Computer Vision*. Retrieved from <https://www.cs.ubc.ca/~lowe/papers/ijcv04.pdf>
- Luce, C. H., Lopez-Burgos, V., & Holden, Z. (2014). Sensitivity of snowpack storage to precipitation and temperature using spatial and temporal analog models. *Water Resources Research*, 50(12), 9447–9462. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2013WR014844>
- MacMillan, R. A., & Shary, P. A. (2009). Chapter 9 Landforms and Landform Elements in Geomorphometry. *Developments in Soil Science*, 33, 227–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481\(08\)00009-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2481(08)00009-3)
- Mancini, F., Dubbini, M., Gattelli, M., Stecchi, F., Fabbri, S., & Gabbianelli, G. (2013). Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) for High-Resolution Reconstruction of Topography: The Structure from Motion Approach on Coastal Environments. *Remote Sensing*, 5(12), 6880–6898. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs5126880>
- Marzloff, I., & Poesen, J. (2009). The potential of 3D gully monitoring with GIS using high-resolution aerial photography and a digital photogrammetry system. *Geomorphology*, 111(1–2), 48–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GEOMORPH.2008.05.047>
- Marzloff, I., Ries, J. B., & Poesen, J. (2011). Short-term versus medium-term monitoring for detecting gully-erosion variability in a Mediterranean environment. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 36(12), 1604–1623. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.2172>
- McCabe, G. J., Clark, M. P., & Hay, L. E. (2007). Rain-on-Snow Events in the Western United States. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 88(3), 319–328. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-88-3-319>
- Mertes, J. R., Gullely, J. D., Benn, D. I., Thompson, S. S., & Nicholson, L. I. (2017). Using structure-from-motion to create glacier DEMs and orthoimagery from historical terrestrial and oblique aerial imagery. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 42(14), 2350–2364. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4188>.

- Mhawej, M., Faour, G., Fayad, A., & Shaban, A. (2014). Towards an enhanced method to map snow cover areas and derive snow-water equivalent in Lebanon. *Journal of Hydrology*, 513, 274–282. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.03.058>
- Micheletti, N., Chandler, J. H., & Lane, S. N. (2015). Investigating the geomorphological potential of freely available and accessible structure-from-motion photogrammetry using a smartphone. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 40(4), 473–486. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3648>
- Micheletti, N., Chandler, J. H., & Lane, S. N. (2015). Structure from Motion (SfM) Photogrammetry. *British Society for Geomorphology Geomorphological Techniques*, 2(2), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-5-W4-37-2015>
- Milles S., Lagofun J. (1999). Topographie et topometrie moderne. Tome 1 – Techniques de mesure et de representation. No 2287,1999, 540 pages.
- Milles S., Lagofun J. (1999). Topographie et topometrie moderne. Tome 2 – calcul. No 2289,1999, 344 pages.
- Mills, J., & Barber, D. (2004). Geomatics Techniques for Structural Surveying. *Journal of Surveying Engineering*, 130(2), 56–64. <https://doi.org/10.1061/ASCE0733-94532004130:256>
- Milly, P., Dunne, K., Nature, A. V. (2005). Global pattern of trends in streamflow and water availability in a changing climate. *Nature.Com*. Retrieved from <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature04312>
- Miziński, B., & Niedzielski, T. (2017). Fully-automated estimation of snow depth in near real time with the use of unmanned aerial vehicles without utilizing ground control points. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 138, 63–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coldregions.2017.03.006>.
- Mizukami, N., Smith, M., (2012). Analysis of inconsistencies in multi-year gridded quantitative precipitation estimate over complex terrain and its impact on hydrologic modeling. *J. Hydrol.* 428–429, 129–141.
- Molotch, N. P., Colee, M. T., Bales, R. C., & Dozier, J. (2005). Estimating the spatial distribution of snow water equivalent in an alpine basin using binary regression tree models: the impact of digital elevation data and independent variable selection. *Hydrological Processes*, 19(7), 1459–1479. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.5586>
- Moratto, Z. M., Broxton, M. J., Beyer, R. A., Lundy, M., & Husmann, K. (2010). Ames Stereo Pipeline, NASA's Open Source Automated Stereogrammetry Software. *41st Lunar and Planetary Science Conference, Held March 1-5, 2010 in The Woodlands, Texas. LPI Contribution No. 1533, p.2364, 41, 2364*. Retrieved from <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2010LPI...41.2364M>
- Morgan, J. A., Brogan, D. J., & Nelson, P. A. (2016). Application of Structure-from-Motion photogrammetry in laboratory flumes. *Geomorphology*, 276, 125–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2016.10.021>.

- Morán-Tejeda, E., Lorenzo-Lacruz, J., López-Moreno, J., Rahman, K., Beniston, M. (2014). Streamflow timing of mountain rivers in Spain: Recent changes and future projections. *J. Hydrol.* 517, 1114–1127.
- Nouwakpo, S.K., James, M.R., Weltz, M.A., Huang, C.-H., Chagas, I., Lima, L. (2014). Evaluation of structure from motion for soil microtopography measurement. *Photogramm. Rec.* 29, 297– 316. doi:10.1111/phor.12072.
- Nikolakopoulos, K. G., Soura, K., Koukouvelas, I. K., & Argyropoulos, N. G. (2017). UAV vs classical aerial photogrammetry for archaeological studies. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, 14, 758–773. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2016.09.004>
- Nissen, E., Krishnan, A. K., Arrowsmith, J. R., & Saripalli, S. (2012). Three-dimensional surface displacements and rotations from differencing pre-and post-earthquake LiDAR point clouds. *Geophysical Research Letters*, 39(16), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2012GL052460>.
- Nitu, R., Wong, K. (2010), WMO/TD-No. 1544, IOM No. 102: CIMO Survey on national summaries of methods and instruments for solid precipitation measurement at AWS, WMO/TD-No. 1544, IOM No. 102, World Meteorological Organization, 57 p.
- Nogués-Bravo, D., Araújo, M. B., Errea, M. P., & Martínez-Rica, J. P. (2007). Exposure of global mountain systems to climate warming during the 21st Century. *Global Environmental Change*, 17(3–4), 420–428. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GLOENVCHA.2006.11.007>
- Nohara, D., Kitoh, A., Hosaka, M., & Oki, T. (2006). Impact of Climate Change on River Discharge Projected by Multimodel Ensemble. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*, 7(5), 1076–1089. <https://doi.org/10.1175/JHM531.1>
- Nolan, M., Larsen, C., & Sturm, M. (2015). Mapping snow depth from manned aircraft on landscape scales at centimeter resolution using structure-from-motion photogrammetry. *The Cryosphere*, 9(4), 1445–1463. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-9-1445-2015>
- Ouédraogo, M. M., Degré, A., Debouche, C., & Lisein, J. (2014). The evaluation of unmanned aerial system-based photogrammetry and terrestrial laser scanning to generate DEMs of agricultural watersheds. *Geomorphology*, 214, 339–355. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2014.02.016>
- Paraforos, D. S., Reutemann, M., Sharipov, G., Werner, R., & Griepentrog, H. W. (2017). Total station data assessment using an industrial robotic arm for dynamic 3D in-field positioning with sub-centimetre accuracy. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture*, 136, 166–175. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compag.2017.03.009>
- Parajka, J., Holko, L., Kostka, Z., & Blöschl, G. (2012). MODIS snow cover mapping accuracy in a small mountain catchment – comparison between open and forest sites. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 16(7), 2365–2377. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-16-2365-2012>.
- Pimentel, R., Herrero, J., Zeng, Y., Su, Z., Polo, M. (2015). Study of snow dynamics at subgrid

- scale in semiarid environments combining terrestrial photography and data assimilation techniques. *J. Hydrometeorol.* 16, 563–578.
- Pomerleau, F., Colas, F., Siegwart, R., & Magnenat, S. (2013). Comparing ICP Variants on Real-World Data Sets Open-source library and experimental protocol. Retrieved from <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01143458/document>.
- Pogorelov, A. V., & Doumit, J. A. (2009). Relief of Kuban river basin: Morphometric analysis (p. 208). M.: Geoc. (In Russian).
- Prokop, A. (2008). Assessing the applicability of terrestrial laser scanning for spatial snow depth measurements. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 54(3), 155–163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coldregions.2008.07.002>
- Prokop, A., Singer, F., Pulfer, G., Naaim, M., Thibert, E., & Soruco, A. (2014). Merging terrestrial laser scanning technology with photogrammetric and total station data for the determination of avalanche modeling parameters. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 110, 223–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coldregions.2014.11.009>
- Prudhomme, C., Giuntoli, I., Robinson, E. L., Clark, D. B., Arnell, N. W., Dankers, R., ... Wisser, D. (2014). Hydrological droughts in the 21st century, hotspots and uncertainties from a global multimodel ensemble experiment. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 111(9), 3262–7. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1222473110>
- Qiu, J. (2012). Snow survey hopes for avalanche of data. *Nature*, 491(7424), 312–313. <https://doi.org/10.1038/491312a>
- Reuter, H.I., Hengl, T., Gessler, P. and Soille, P. (2008). Preparation of DEMs for Geomorphometric Analysis. In: T. Hengl and H.I. Reuter, ed. *Geomorphometry: Concepts, Software, Applications, Developments in Soil Science*, vol. 33, Elsevier, 87–120.
- Revuelto, J., Jonas, T., & López-Moreno, J. I. (2016). Backward snow depth reconstruction at high spatial resolution based on time-lapse photography. *Hydrological Processes*, 30(17), 2976–2990. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.10823>.
- Robertson DP, Cipolla R. (2009). Structure from motion. In *Practical Image Processing and Computer Vision*, Varga M (ed.). John Wiley & Sons: Chichester.
- Ruiz, J. J., Diaz-Mas, L., Perez, F., & Viguria, A. (2013). Evaluating the Accuracy of Dem Generation Algorithms From Uav Imagery. *International Archives of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, XL(September), 4–6. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XL-5-529-2014>
- Ryan, J. C., Hubbard, A. L., Box, J. E., Todd, J., Christoffersen, P., Carr, J. R., ... Snooke, N. (2015). UAV photogrammetry and structure from motion to assess calving dynamics at Store Glacier, a large outlet draining the Greenland ice sheet. *The Cryosphere*, 9(1), 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-9-1-2015>.

- Schneider, B. (2001). On the uncertainty of local form of lines and surfaces. *Cartography and Geographic Information Science*, 28 (4), 237–247.
- Schofield, W. (Wilfred), & Breach, M. (Mark). (2007). *Engineering surveying*.
- Scipión, D. E., Mott, R., Lehning, M., Schneebeli, M., & Berne, A. (2013). Seasonal small-scale spatial variability in alpine snowfall and snow accumulation. *Water Resources Research*, 49(3), 1446–1457. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wrcr.20135>
- Shaban, A., Darwich, T., Drapeau, L., & Gascoin, S. (2014). Climatic Induced Snowpack Surfaces on Lebanon's Mountains. *The Open Hydrology Journal*, 8(OCTOBER 2014), 8–16. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874378101408010008>
- Shaban, A., Darwich, T., & El, M. (2013). Studying Snowpack-Related Characteristics on Lebanon Mountains. *International Journal of Water Sciences*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.5772/57435>
- Shaban, A., Faour, G., Khawlie, M., & Abdallah, C. (2004). Remote sensing application to estimate the volume of water in the form of snow on Mount Lebanon / Application de la télédétection à l'estimation du volume d'eau sous forme de neige sur le Mont Liban. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 49(4), 37–41. <https://doi.org/10.1623/hysj.49.4.643.54432>
- Shaban, A., & Houhou, R. (2015). Drought or humidity oscillations. The case of coastal zone of Lebanon. *Journal of Hydrology*, 529, 1768–1775. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2015.08.010>
- Shaban A.; Darwish T. (2011). The role of sinkholes in groundwater recharge in the high mountains of Lebanon. *Journal of environmental hydrology*. Volume 19 paper 9 April 2011; p. 1-12.
- Shean, D. E., Alexandrov, O., Moratto, Z. M., Smith, B. E., Joughin, I. R., Porter, C., & Morin, P. (2016). An automated, open-source pipeline for mass production of digital elevation models (DEMs) from very-high-resolution commercial stereo satellite imagery. *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 116, 101–117. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2016.03.012>
- Shean, D. E., Fahle, J., Malin, M. C., Edwards, L. J., & Posiolova, L. (2011). MRO CTX STEREO IMAGE PROCESSING AND PRELIMINARY DEM QUALITY ASSESSMENT. Retrieved from http://ti.arc.nasa.gov/m/project/ngt/asp_book_1.0.1.pdf.
- Siebert, S., & Teizer, J. (2014). Mobile 3D mapping for surveying earthwork projects using an Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) system. *Automation in Construction*, 41, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2014.01.004>
- Smith. (1967). Measuring snow depth by aerial photogrammetry. Evaluation and recommendation.
- Smith, M.W., Vericat, D. (2015). From experimental plots to experimental landscapes: topography, erosion and deposition in sub-humid badlands from Structure-from-Motion

- photogrammetry. *Earth Surf. Process. Landforms* 40, 1656–1671. doi:10.1002/esp.3747.
- Snapir, B., Hobbs, S., Waive, T.W. (2014). Roughness measurements over an agricultural soil surface with Structure from Motion. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* 96, 210–223. doi:10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2014.07.010.
- Snavely, N., Seitz, S. M., & Szeliski, R. (2017). Modeling the World from Internet Photo Collections. *Int J Comput Vis.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-007-0107-3>
- Snavely, N., Seitz, S. M., & Szeliski, R. (2008). Modeling the World from Internet Photo Collections. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 80(2), 189–210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11263-007-0107-3>
- Somma, J., Drapeau, L., & Abou Chakra, C. (2014). Caractérisation de la capacité de rétention de neige d'un plateau karstique. Essai méthodologique pour le plateau du Jabal Jraid (Liban). *Revue Internationale de Géomatique*, 24(1), 87–99. <https://doi.org/10.3166/rig.24.87-99>
- Somma, J., Drapeau, L., Abou Chakra, C., & El-Ali, T. (2014). Geomatics contributions to key indicators for estimation and monitoring of snow cover input to hydrogeological resources. *American Geophysical Union, Fall Meeting 2014, Abstract Id. C43C-0404*. Retrieved from <http://adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2014AGUFM.C43C0404S>
- Somma, J., Gérard, J., Corbane, C., & Bernier, M. (2001). EVOLUTION DU MANTEAU NEIGEUX LIBANAIS : PREMIERE APPROCHE , HIVER 2001 Plan de l' exposé.
- Somma, J., & Luxey, P. (2006). Modélisation Volumique des Névés sur les Hauts Plateaux Karstiques du Mont Liban .
- Suominen, O., & Gotchev, A. (2013). Circular trajectory correspondences for iterative closest point registration. *3DTV-Conference*, 0–3. <https://doi.org/10.1109/3DTV.2013.6676634>
- Surfleet, C. G., & Tullos, D. (2013). Variability in effect of climate change on rain-on-snow peak flow events in a temperate climate. *Journal of Hydrology*, 479, 24–34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2012.11.021>.
- Svoma, B. M. (2011). Winter Climatic Controls on Spring Snowpack Density in the Western United States. *Arctic, Antarctic, and Alpine Research*, 43(1), 118–126. <https://doi.org/10.1657/1938-4246-43.1.118>.
- Telesca, L., Shaban, A., Gascoin, S., Darwich, T., Drapeau, L., Hage, M. El, & Faour, G. (2014). Characterization of the time dynamics of monthly satellite snow cover data on Mountain Chains in Lebanon. *Journal of Hydrology*, 519(PD), 3214–3222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2014.10.037>.
- Teza, G., Galgaro, A. Zaltron, N. and Genevois, R. (2007). Terrestrial laser scanner to detect landslide displacement fields: A new approach, *Int. J. Remote Sens.*, 28(16), 3425–3446.
- Thomas, H., & Kennedy, M. A. (2016). A new methodology for accurate digital planning of archaeological sites without the aid of surveying equipment. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports*, 10, 887–892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2016.06.006>.

- Touma, T. (2002). Calcul des superficies enneigées sur le Mont Liban. Mémoire de DEA, Université St Joseph, Centre Régional de l'Eau et de l'Environnement, Beyrouth, Liban, 51 P.
- Triggs, B., Mclauchlan, P., Hartley, R., & Fitzgibbon, A. (1999). Bundle Adjustment — A Modern Synthesis 1 Introduction. *Vision Algorithms: Theory & Practice*, 34099, 1–71.
- Udin, W. S., & Ahmad, A. (2014). Assessment of Photogrammetric Mapping Accuracy Based on Variation Flying Altitude Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 18, 012027. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/18/1/012027>.
- Uysal, M., Toprak, A. S., & Polat, N. (2015). DEM generation with UAV Photogrammetry and accuracy analysis in Sahitler hill. *Measurement*, 73, 539–543. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.MEASUREMENT.2015.06.010>.
- Vano, J. A., Nijssen, B., & Lettenmaier, D. P. (2015). Seasonal hydrologic responses to climate change in the Pacific Northwest. *Water Resources Research*, 51(4), 1959–1976. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014WR015909>.
- Vasuki, Y., Holden, E.-J., Kovesi, P., & Micklethwaite, S. (2014). Semi-automatic mapping of geological Structures using UAV-based photogrammetric data: An image analysis approach. *Computers & Geosciences*, 69, 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CAGEO.2014.04.012>.
- Verhoeven, G. (2011). Taking computer vision aloft - archaeological three-dimensional reconstructions from aerial photographs with photoscan. *Archaeological Prospection*, 18(1), 67–73. <https://doi.org/10.1002/arp.399>.
- Viviroli, D., Dürr, H. H., Messerli, B., Meybeck, M., & Weingartner, R. (2007). Mountains of the world, water towers for humanity: Typology, mapping, and global significance. *Water Resources Research*, 43(7). <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006WR005653>.
- Wagner, A. (2015). A new approach for geo-monitoring using modern total stations and RGB + D images. *Measurement: Journal of the International Measurement Confederation*, 82, 64–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2015.12.025>.
- Wang, J., Ge, Y., Heuvelink, G. B. M., Zhou, C., & Brus, D. (2012). Effect of the sampling design of ground control points on the geometric correction of remotely sensed imagery. *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*, 18, 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2012.01.001>.
- Watanabe, Y., & Kawahara, Y. (2016). UAV Photogrammetry for Monitoring Changes in River Topography and Vegetation. *Procedia Engineering*, 154, 317–325. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2016.07.482>.
- Watters, W. A., Geiger, L. M., Fendrock, M., & Gibson, R. (2015). Morphometry of small recent impact craters on Mars: Size and terrain dependence, short-term modification. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Planets*, 120(2), 226–254. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014JE004630>.

- Webber, B.B., (1995). Testing the vertical accuracy of United States Geologic Survey 7.5 minute and 1 degree digital elevation models. Unpublished Master's thesis, University of Idaho, Moscow, ID, United States. 73 pp.
- Westoby, M. J., Brasington, J., Glasser, N. F., Hambrey, M. J., & Reynolds, J. M. (2012). 'Structure-from-Motion' photogrammetry: A low-cost, effective tool for geoscience applications. *Geomorphology*, 179, 300–314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2012.08.021>.
- Whitehead, K., Moorman, B. J., & Hugenholtz, C. H. (2013). Brief Communication: Low-cost, on-demand aerial photogrammetry for glaciological measurement. *The Cryosphere*, 7(6), 1879–1884. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-7-1879-2013>.
- Wigmore, O., & Mark, B. (2017). Monitoring Tropical Debris Covered Glacier Dynamics from High Resolution Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Photogrammetry, Cordillera Blanca, Peru. *The Cryosphere Discussions*, 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-2017-31>.
- Wood, J. (1996). The geomorphological characterisation of digital elevation models. Retrieved from <https://ira.le.ac.uk/handle/2381/34503>.

Appendix 1
Publication and research activities

Snow Cover Digital Elevation Models Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle and Total Station

by

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Abstract

Impact of climatic changes and human activities on water resource is a global major socio-economic concern. Middle East is expected to face severe water challenges both in terms of quantity and quality. In Lebanon specifically, water uses has increased over recent decades, due to population and economic growth. The country is expected to reach water scarcity level in the coming years. Therefore long term assessment to address deteriorating water resources is becoming crucial.

Snowfalls on Lebanon and Anti-Lebanon mountains are known to be the major input source for underground water. Snowpack act as natural water storage in winter, and supply fresh water during spring and summer. Estimation of water provided by snow requires accurate snow cover volume quantification. However, this evaluation is difficult because of the relief heterogeneity and its impact on snow cover thickness distribution. It is therefore most important to investigate new methodologies enabling these quantifications at low cost, both in terms of human resources and sensors for data collection. For the last five years, we monitored volumes evolution for a witness sinkhole at "Ouyoun el Simane". The region has been studied with very precise topographic approach using Total Station. This approach is now correlated to aerial digital photogrammetric images captured by UAV (SFM¹: structure from motion). It will enable extrapolation of these evaluations to larger scales, with high accuracy, for snow cover monitoring. Our objectives are to combine and compare topographic and photogrammetric results prior to snow cover volume assessment, in order to validate the low cost photogrammetric method for both methods.

Keywords: Snow cover, Volume, Digital Elevation Model, low cost, topography, UAV, sinkhole

¹ SFM (structure from motion): is a technic to obtain 3D modeling from to sequences images

1. Introduction

Climate changes has an important negative impact on water resources at an international scale due to the cumulative effect of temperature rise as well as decreasing snowfall and rainfall (Abou chakra et al., 2015; Drapeau et al., 2013; Somma et al., 2006). Middle East countries were impacted by these changes as most of the region is an arid area (Mhawej et al., 2014; Abou Chakra, 2013). Although Lebanon has one of the richest snow cover in the Middle East area (Shaban, 2011; Shaban et al., 2004), it is importantly affected by climate change and has decreasing water resources.

In addition of its decreasing water resources, Lebanon is facing an important growth of its population especially after hosting a large number of refugees due to regional wars. Water needs supply is crucial for majority of Lebanese people especially during the dry summer season, caused by the above reason and due to lack of water resources legal control (Telesca et al., 2014; Shaban et al., 2011; Fawaz, 2009; El-Fadel et al., 2000). Consequently, continuous and systematic water supply observation is needed for water management planning within current climate change framework (Somma et al., 2014; Somma, 2006; Luxey et al., 2005).

The high Lebanese mountains play an important role for snowfall and rainfall precipitation distribution (Telesca et al. 2014; Mhawej et al., 2014; Shaban, 2011; Jonas et al., 2009). The Lebanese snow covers contribute around 30% of water resources, and account for about 31 % of rivers and spring discharges (Telesca et al., 2014; Mhawej et al., 2014). In addition, snow covers could cover around 25% of the Lebanese territory (Shaban et al., 2004).

Based on the above, continuous monitoring of snow cover is one of the most important component of water resources investigation (Somma et al., 2014). From 2000 until now, few studies were done for the Lebanese snow cover and in progress on the monitoring of snow covers by terrestrial and spatial methodology (Abou chakra et al., 2015; Abou Chakra, 2013). From 2011, we started a systematic and continuous observation of a snow melt by estimating the decreasing of snow volumes on a witness sinkhole located at "Ouyoun el Simane" (Kfardebiane) (figure 1). This observation can helps us to predict complete snow cover melting date and consequently to predict low water flow date. With this achievement we could supply water manager with essential key information to prepare suitable plan for water resources management. Our measurements were taken with very detailed topographic approach using Total Station. Whereas this method is very accurate both in planimetry and altimetry (Milles et al. 1999), it is impossible to use for a large territory (Abou Chakra, 2013). For such scales, high cost topographic equipment and important human resources deployments are required (Somma et al., 2014), in order to survey simultaneously the area involved. Snow cover is dynamic relatively to meteorological conditions and the areas of investigation are

uneasy to reach by vehicles. Hence, we planned to experiment an unmanned aerial vehicle "UAV" to monitor the area and compare the results with the survey of total station for several dates to be able to use stereoscopic approach for larges territory using low cost methodology and instruments. The digital photogrammetric DEM computed from UAV gave an acceptable result on the bare lands (Arango et al., 2015) nevertheless we aim to test it on the snow cover.

The focus of this paper is the monitoring of snow cover by comparing measurement using total station tool and the UAV to validate efficiency of low cost digital photogrammetric method.

2. Study area

Lebanon, a country with of 10452 km², has large and high mountain chains with karstification geomorphological phenomena (Somma et al., 2014; Mhawej et al., 2014; Shaban, 2011; Shaban et al., 2004). Those high mountains play an important role by governing the distribution of snowfall and rainfall (Mhawej et al., 2014; Telesca et al., 2014; Qiu, 2012). The high plateaus are characterized by sinkholes with different geometric aspects (Somma et al., 2014). They constrain snow covers to melt inside the sinkholes then the melt water penetrate the subsurface and feed the underground water resources (Somma, 2014; Elali, 2014; Shaban, 2011; Somma al., 2005).

The witness sinkhole is approximately about 20000 m² (figure 1), located at Oyoun el Siman (Kfardebiane) at 2300m above sea level and equipped by: meteorological station, geodetic point, and cameras for daily observation for many Scientifics targets.

Figure 1: Location of the study area

3. Methodology

Extraction of Digital Elevation Model "DEM" is the most important element to estimate snow cover volume (Arango et al. 2015; Elali, 2014; Abou Chakra 2013; Milles et al., 1999). Thus, the accuracy of measurements plays an important role by defining calculated volume precision. Our objective is to evaluate errors and validity of using UAV instead of total station for creating digital elevation model for snow cover. We could then estimate snow cover volumes by comparing bare lands DEM with snow covers DEM. Therefore, the bare land was surveyed as well as the snow cover for two different dates (10 May 2016 and 3 June 2016) using total station and UAV for this witness sinkhole.

3.1. Data acquisition

3.1.1. Total Station

To create the digital elevation models for the bare land and the snow cover we used the total station Leica TS06 (figure 2). This total station is an electronic/optical instrument used usually to model the topography of land by taking many points with their coordinate x, y, z in order to represent the digital elevation model by interpolation method, based on the measured points (Doumit, 2009; Milles et al., 1999).

Figure 2: From left to right, Total station (Leica TS06) during modeling then, the observed points (firn polygon, snow cover and the GCPs)

Using total station, we surveyed the bare land before the snow fall. For the three dates we set temporary many ground control points (figure 3) regularly distributed over the study area. The

observed points by total station were distributed relatively to terrain relief. It was mainly an approximated grid of 5 by 10m. Using total station, we also surveyed the limit of the firm.

Figure 3: One of the ground control points (GCP) measured by total station and observed by UAV in order to relocate and calibrate the Model created by Agisoft Photoscan

3.1.2. Unmanned Aerial Vehicle, UAV

For data acquisition with UAV, we used a "Phantom 3 Advanced" (figure 4). This aircraft is equipped with a built-in camera of 12 Megapixels, with a 17 minutes fly autonomy. The fly plan defined for the UAV was to capture pictures every 5 seconds in order to obtain 80% of overlapping by flying at 13 km/h. The fly was at an altitude of 100m above ground in order to cover the whole study area minimizing the number of pictures but keeping high resolution quality picture. We selected this option because it achieves the lowest possible cost comparing with other aircrafts. Moreover, this aircraft is not basically created for making digital elevation model. Nevertheless, it has a CA code GPS and autopilot system. We tried to use and test it. Those criteria allow us got the global tridimensional coordinate of each taken pictures and prepare a systematic mission using a tablet Samsung and Litchi Application (figure 5, and we managed the requested overlap in photogrammetric approach (60 % to 80 % according to Agisoft tutorial) for the stereoscopic procedures. Often, the flight missions were aborted because of strong wind at these altitudes precluding the UAV to fly safely.

Figure 4: Phantom 3 Advanced

Figure 5: Litchi application, show the flight mission with the height of UAV and its speed

As mentioned, we surveyed the snow cover for two dates 3 June 2016 and 10 May 2016. For the 3 June 2016 we captured pictures with and 90 degrees, and we also captured three pictures with an inclined angle (figure 7) to test the interest of taking photos by several angles in addition to the horizontal images.

3.2. Data processing

3.2.1. Bare Land

The bare land is modeled using total station data only with 620 points distributed according to the land relief around 5m between each two consecutive points. This survey will act as the reference to calculate the volume for the further snow cover models. Using ArcMap we transformed the points shape to tin surface then to raster.

3.2.2. Snow cover

Data acquisition for the snow cover was achieved with total station and UAV at the same time the 3 June 2016 and the 10 May 2016. With the total station we proceeded with the same procedure as the one used for bare land, but the data were collected just for the snowed area with measurement of the firm limit in order to obtain a closed polygon to crop the snow cover raster for the two dates (figure 6).

Figure 6: the steps to obtain raster DEM from shape points

The 10/05/16 DEM created with UAV, was based on captured pictures with classical stereoscopic approach. The pictures were captured horizontally in order to cover the entire area of interest. The same procedure was applied for the 03/06/16 (Figure 7).

Figure 7: From left to right, the horizontal photos taken for 3 June and 10 May 2016

The 03/06/16 we captured 3 additional inclined pictures (figure 8) to test the interest of these to support the classical horizontal pictures. We obtained one model based on horizontal pictures on 10 May 2016, and two models on 3 June 2016.

Figure 8: Additional inclined photos taken on 3 June 2016

We selected Agisoft Photoscan for the UAV data processing in line with our “low cost approach”. For the three models we used separately the following procedure: Add photos, align photos, build dense cloud, build mesh, build texture, build tiled model, create marker, update, import GCPs, Build DEM, Build orthomosaic, export DEM and export orthophoto (figure 9).

Figure 9: Different steps to obtain the DEM and rectified photo from taken image by UAV

We added the DEMs and the orthophotos on ArcMap to start the georeferencing process for the computed models according to GCPs. However, the obtained models are not only for the snow cover. The UAV covered the whole area. Therefore we have to slip the snow cover from the DEM by clipping the DEM according to the firm limit measured by total station (see 4.1 first method).

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Comparing the DEMs accuracy

The Digital Elevation Model is an important reference factor to estimate volumes. And its precision has a great influence in computing accurate volumes. It is assumed that the value measured with the total station is the reference therefore called the “true value”. Consequently with ArcMap software, we use raster calculator to obtain the difference between the UAV’s DEM and the other obtain by Total station.

For the model computed with the total station we obtained the raster DEM based on the measured points and its tin² surface. While, for the UAV’s DEM we assess two methods:

-First method:

We used the whole clipped DEM obtained from Agisoft Photoscan (figure 10)

² TIN: Triangulated Irregular Network

Figure 10: Realizing the clipped DEM of only the snow cover

- Second method:

We created a new DEM by modification of the points taken by total station, therefore we use add functional surface under ArcMap by adding the pixel value of UAV with the total station (figure 11). Consequently, we could see the exact error on each point to remove the interpolation impact for this stage.

Snow3June2016					
Point	Easting	Northing	Elevation Total Station	Code	Elevation Drone
24	-304189.6336	-19371.9464	2323.2354	L	2322.9654
25	-304191.3138	-19372.8412	2323.7512	L	2323.4560
26	-304192.9492	-19372.4591	2323.8241	L	2323.6149
27	-304196.4561	-19369.5698	2323.9423	L	2323.6899
28	-304197.0199	-19368.7457	2323.8737	L	2323.5726
29	-304198.3056	-19368.9147	2324.0035	L	2323.5381
30	-304198.6784	-19370.1141	2324.1499	L	2323.7684
31	-304200.0985	-19370.1503	2324.2576	L	2324.0239

Figure 11: DEM's elevation of total station and UAV

Under ArcMap we used raster calculator to carry out the difference between total station and UAV's DEM. The difference between the both methods is mentioned in (table 1) based on the raster classification, (figure 12) show a graphic example of the differences based on the general formula:

$$DEM_{UAV} - DEM_{Total\ Station} = Difference$$

Figure 12: Obtained raster by subtracting UAV's DEM from Total Station's DEM for the same firm in the same time

Dates	10 May 2016 (Horizontal images)				3 June 2016 (Horizontal images)				3 June 2016 (horizontal & incline images)			
According to ArcMap Classification raster (meter)	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	standard deviation	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	standard deviation
First Method	-0.57	0.86	0.1	0.22	-1.93	0.5	-0.21	0.33	-1.27	0.7	0.005	0.252
Second Method	-0.3	0.5	0.08	0.17	-0.79	0.4	-0.19	0.27	-0.45	0.6	0.007	0.22

Table 1: difference between the first and second method to carry out the accuracy of obtained models

The maximum difference for the standard deviation and mean between the first and the second method is 6 cm. Therefore it is acceptable according to our topographic experience. Consequently we could use the unmanned aerial vehicle phantom 3 Advanced, with 100 m as flying altitude to achieve an error of standard deviation between 22 and 33 cm, according to above table. Furthermore, if we compare the resulting image taken horizontally with the image taken with additional inclined photo, the DEM is better and closer to the points of total station because the inclined photos support the horizontal photo to increase the overlapping area on SFM (figure 13). As we observed on the (figure 13), the model of 3 June 2016 taken by horizontal and inclined photos has the most overlapping percentage.

Figure 13: Overlapping percentage of each model extracted from Agisoft reports.

4.2. Volume estimation

After analyzing the DEMs and its accuracy, we proceeded toward the snow volume estimation, using the Cut and Fill 3D analyst tools available in ArcMap. In (table 2), we used the bare land's DEM created by total station with the snow cover made by total station and UAV using the first and second methods obtained above (see 4.1).

Data		Volume			Volume error percentage %		
Bare land	Snow Cover	10 May 2016 Horizontal photo	3 June 2016 Horizontal Photos	3 June 2016 Horizontal & inclined Photos	10 May 2016 Horizontal photo	3 June 2016 Horizontal Photos	3 June 2016 Horizontal & inclined Photos
Total Station	Total Station	9165	2676	2676			
Total Station	UAV first method	9381	2700	2975	-2.30%	-0.80%	-11.20%
Total Station	UAV second method	9960	2563	2879	-6.17%	5.07%	3.20%

Table 2: The snow cover volume estimated from different data and its error percentage by assuming that the volume obtained by DEM's total station as reference.

Thus, we considered the volume obtain by the DEMs (bare land and snow cover) obtained by total station as reference, because each point of DEM was taken absolutely. In the volume result we got errors range from 0.89% to 11%, and errors range from 3.2 to 6.1% for the second method. The results obtained (table 1) are acceptable with as means and standards deviations values. The increasing errors on volume are due to some outlier values for minimum and maximum in (table 1). The majority of DEM's UAV fit around ninety percent of the total station's DEM. So it is rational to get such error for volume estimation. Furthermore, it is important to compare first and second method volumes estimation. The DEM computed with the second method is based on located points acquired with total station. Nevertheless, a large number of points, from the points cloud obtain by UAV and Agisoft are lost because we just used the points taken by total station. In addition, the DEM taken by total station is measured by an approximate grid of points distribution and for each slope changing, beside, it is not taken by a laser scanner. That is why the result was better on the first method. With the inclined photos we computed more accurate DEM. However, we arrived to bigger error for volume caused by some outlier. Using ArcMap we classified the raster images obtained by difference between Total station's DEM and UAV's DEM (figure 14). As per our analysis of error distribution between the three models in the figure, we did not notice any general rule of errors distribution. Thus, we can deduce that Agisoft collect the common pixels randomly to build the 3D model. Therefore we think

on the next studies to repeat the processing for the same model many times in order to clarify the distribution of error and deduce the impact of the random algorithm in the Agisoft program.

Figure 14: Distribution errors for each model.

Finally, we were able to verify the efficiency of our method: using phantom 3 Advanced, equipped by a camera 12 Megapixels, flying speed 13 km/h with an altitude 100 m above the ground and made the processing with Agisoft Photoscan give us a maximum error of 11% for the volume estimation. So that we could predict the date of final snow melt and extend other hydrological factors to support the water manager in addition information regarding the volume and its equivalent in water.

Conclusion and recommendation

The similarity test between UAV and total station justified the ability of using the digital photogrammetric method and its efficiency to estimate snow cover volume. First of all, the use of this new approach has a lot of advantages: the survey by UAV take less time than the survey with total station and it is not compulsory to have access to area for each observation. The captured pictures with UAV provide points clouds, whereas the total station provided only the captured points taken manually by the human operator. In addition we could get an orthorectified photo which allows us to draw the firm limit and define the snow cover area. Eventually we are able to evaluate a larger area with ease and gain of time.

This experience has some weak points, Although we got ideals means and standard deviations for the similarities test between total station and UAV, some large value for minimum and maximum errors are present and influenced the volume estimation. We recommend test the same model on

several dates to evaluate furthermore the efficiency of Agisoft and/or to test other softwares. We plan to investigate the same procedure using Lidar and a more efficient camera allowing an increased flying altitude for the UAV while saving the accuracy. In addition, it will be interesting to test a UAV equipped with a differential GPS (RTK) on the snow cover, avoiding the total station uses to measure the GCPs (ground control points). Eventually, we planned to change the flight altitude to estimate its exact impact, we could estimate the best altitude in order to cover an even larger territory with the lowest possible cost.

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References

- ABOU CHAKRA C., SOMMA J, DRAPEAU L., FANISE P., GASCOIN S., EL ALI T., ASSAF B. ; 2015 : Estimation de la précision des mesures photogrammétriques terrestres de volume de neige : *Présentation orale durant les troisièmes journées Franco-Libanaises JFL 3*.
- ABOU CHAKRA C. ; 2013: Suivi topographique de la fonte des neiges : étude d'une doline des plateaux de Jabal el Dib (Ouyoun el Simane, Mont-Liban). *Mémoire de Master, Université Saint Joseph (in Arabic)*.
- CIMOLIE. ; 2015: Determining Snow Depth Distribution from Unmanned Aerial Vehicles and Digital Photogrammetry. *Technical University of Denmark, 2015 (<http://kho.unis.no/doc/Emiliano.pdf>)*.
- DOUMIT J. ; 2009: Introduction a la topographie. *Surveying courses for Geographers and civil Engineering, p.41*.
- DRAPEAU L., SHABAN A., SOMMA J. ; 2013: Pour un observatoire de la neige au Liban. L'eau face au changement climatique. *Seminar presented at IFPO (Institut Français pour le Proche Orient), mars*.

- EL-FADEL, M., ZEINATI M., JAMALI D. ; 2000: Water resources in Lebanon: characterization, water balance, and constraints. *J. Water Res. Dev.* 16, 619–642.
- FAWAZ, M. ; 2009: Towards a Water Policy in Lebanon. ESIB, *Beirut, Lebanon*, p. 259 (in Arabic).
- LUXEY P., SOMMA J., DHONT D. ; 2005: The volumetric representation of geological formations: an aid to better underground water management. *Présentation à la conférence internationale : Beirut Water Week*.
- MHAWEJ, M., FAOUR, G., FAYAD, A., SHABAN, A.; 2014: Towards an enhanced method to map snow cover areas and derive snow-water equivalent in Lebanon. *J. Hydrol.* 513, 274–282.
- MILLES S, LAGOFUN J.; 1999: Topographie et topométrie moderne. Tome 1 - Technique de mesure et de représentation. No 2287, 1999, 540 pages. Eyrolles.
- QIU J. ; 2012: Snow survey hopes for avalanche of data. *Climate Science. Volume 491*.
- SHABAN, A.; 2011: The role of sinkholes in groundwater recharge in the high mountains of Lebanon. *Journal of environmental hydrology. Volume 19*.
- SHABAN A., FAOUR G., KHAWLIE M., ABDALLAH C.; 2004: Remote sensing application to estimate the volume of water in the form of snow on Mount Lebanon. *Hydrological Science Journal*, 49 (4), 643-653.
- SOMMA J., DRAPEAU L., ABOU CHAKRA C. ; 2014: Caractérisation de la capacité de rétention de neige d'un plateau karstique. Essai méthodologique pour le plateau du Jabal Jraïd (Liban). *Revue internationale de géomatique*, n°1, 87-99.
- SOMMA J., DRAPEAU L., ABOU CHAKRA C., EL ALI T. ; 2014: Geomatics contributions to key indicators for estimation and monitoring of snow cover input to hydrogeological resources. *AGU fall meeting, San Francisco; 15-19 December*.
- SOMMA J., LUXEY P. ; 2006: Modélisation volumique des névés sur les hauts plateaux karstiques du Mont Liban. *Actes de la conférence WATMED3, 1-3 Nov. 06, Tripoli, 11 p.*
- TELESCA L., SHABAN A., GASCOIN S., DARWICH T., DRAPEAU L., EL HAGE M., FAOUR G. ; 2014: Characterization of dynamic of monthly satellite snow cover data on Mountain chains in Lebanon. *Journal of hydrology (2014)*, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydro.2014.10.037>.

Caractérisation de la capacité de rétention de neige d'un plateau karstique

Essai méthodologique pour le plateau du Jabal Jraid (Liban)

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RÉSUMÉ. L'observation continue et systématique des réserves d'eau constituées par le couvert neigeux s'impose pour la planification de la gestion de l'eau en ces temps de changements climatiques. Les hauts plateaux du Liban, de par leur relief karstique, ont une capacité de rétention et de stockage des précipitations neigeuses de toute importance. Cet article expose une approche méthodologique pour l'estimation de la capacité de rétention maximum qu'offre un tel type de relief.

ABSTRACT. The continuous and systematic observation of water supply constituted from snow cover is needed for water management planning within current climate change framework. The highlands of Lebanon with their karstic relief have a significant capacity of retention and storage of snowfall. This paper outlines a methodological approach for estimating the maximum storage capacity that can be concealed by this type of relief.

MOTS-CLÉS : rétention, neige, Karst, modélisation volumique.

KEYWORDS: retention, snow, Karst, volume modeling.

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1. Introduction et problématique

La préservation des ressources en eau devient une priorité en ces temps de changements climatiques. Aussi, la recherche s'oriente actuellement vers une meilleure appréhension qualitative et quantitative des réserves hydrologiques. Sur cette thématique le pourtour méditerranéen fait l'objet d'une attention particulière notamment dans les zones à hauts reliefs où le couvert neigeux constitue une part importante de ces ressources.

Au Liban, les besoins en eau se font cruellement sentir à la période de l'étiage et jusqu'aux premières précipitations conséquentes pour la recharge des aquifères. Ces dernières surviennent essentiellement en saison froide ou fraîche (automne et hiver) et leur répartition dans l'espace est très variable selon les saisons hivernales. En effet, les séries temporelles d'enneigement basées sur la télédétection entre les années 2001 et 2011 (figure 1) illustrent cette variabilité.

Figure 1. Variabilité spatiotemporelle de l'enneigement sur trois massifs méditerranéens : le Haut-Atlas, le Mont-Liban (vert) et les Pyrénées à partir de MOD10A2 (source : Gascoin et al., 2012)

Il existe également des variations dans l'accumulation du couvert neigeux, comme il apparaît des variabilités temporelles de fonte selon les années (Drapeau *et al.*, 2013). Or la détermination de la date de fonte totale constitue un indicateur important pour les gestionnaires de l'eau dans la prévision de la date de l'étiage et la gestion des rationnements (Gédéon, 2004 ; Gédéon *et al.*, 2004).

Ces fluctuations contribuent à modeler la forme et l'épaisseur du couvert et à en modifier le volume stocké dans les creux des reliefs. Ceci est particulièrement observable sur les hauts plateaux du Mont Liban dont la constitution karstique est à l'origine de la formation d'une multitude de dolines ou d'ondulations. Celles-ci représentent autant de pièges à neige et entraînent une fonte différentielle selon l'orientation des pentes de ces petits bassins versants (figure 2, photo 1).

*Figure. Photo 1. Plateaux ondulés du Mt Liban
(fonte différentielle selon l'orientation, image SPOT).*

L'évaluation quantitative des réserves d'eau contenues sous forme de neige sur les sommets doit passer par une évaluation des volumes emmagasinés dans les formes du relief ; le calcul de l'équivalent en eau prenant en compte le volume et la densité de la couverture neigeuse (Corbane *et al.*, 2001, 2004, 2005 ; Bernier *et al.*, 2001, 2003). Des tentatives d'évaluation ont fait, au Liban, dans le début des années 2000, l'objet de quelques recherches (Corbane *et al.*, 2001, 2004, 2005 ; Bernier *et al.*, 2001, 2003 ; Shaban *et al.*, 2004 ; Aouad *et al.*, 2004, Aouad-Rizk *et al.*, 2005 ; Gédéon *et al.*, 2004). Toutefois ce n'était, pour un début, que des approximations en l'absence d'appareils de mesure et d'équipes de terrain. Aussi conviendrait-il aujourd'hui de pousser plus loin ces essais pour permettre d'estimer de façon plus précise les volumes de neiges résiduelles, considérant que se sont celles-ci qui alimentent en continu les réservoirs souterrains et retardent le tarissement des sources à l'étiage (Drapeau *et al.*, 2013 ; Gédéon, 2004 ; Gédéon *et al.*, 2004).

L'utilisation de la télédétection reste incontournable pour des évaluations sur de grandes surfaces, entreprendre un suivi de la fonte et en modéliser les résultats. Cependant une étape préliminaire à cela serait d'évaluer la capacité de rétention de neige d'un relief. En effet, la connaissance de la capacité de rétention de la neige par un relief creux ou en dépressions fermées permettrait d'une part, de mieux caractériser les relations entre la morphologie karstique et le volume neigeux et, d'autre part, de servir de référence pour l'évaluation du pourcentage d'occupation des dépressions par les névés à différents stades de fonte.

Afin d'évaluer cette capacité de stockage de la neige, une première étape consiste à déterminer la surface initiale du relief avant érosion, en regard de la topographie actuelle ; l'hypothèse sous jacente est que la surface « avant érosion » constitue une surface enveloppe qui passe par tous les sommets topographiques.

Ce travail, a pour terrain expérimental le plateau karstique de Jabal Jraid dont la surface (photo 2) est ponctuée par de nombreuses dolines (plus de 40 au km²). Leur morphologie préserve les névés et n'en permet que la sublimation ou l'infiltration des eaux de fonte. L'objectif principal de cette étude est d'estimer des volumes potentiels de neige qui pourraient être piégés dans ces dépressions lors de la période d'enneigement hivernal maximal. Ceci constituera également un apport supplémentaire aux études précédentes sur les caractéristiques du plateau (Bou-Jaoude *et al.*, 2010 ; Somma et Luxey, 2006 ; Gédéon *et al.*, 2004 ; 2004 ; Bou-Jawdeh *et al.*, 2001).

La méthodologie suivie couple des données de télédétection à haute résolution spatiale avec un modèleur 3D pour calculer les volumes. En cela elle est novatrice et pourrait non seulement s'appliquer à l'ensemble des hauts plateaux du Mont Liban mais également à tout relief présentant des dépressions fermées.

L'évaluation de la capacité de stockage est basée sur une modélisation volumique réalisée à l'aide du géomodeleur EarthVision 8.1™. Cette dernière nécessite un MNA (modèle numérique d'altitude) de haute résolution spatiale

(60 cm) permettant d'identifier les limites des dépressions fermées (dolines) à partir desquelles est calculée la surface enveloppe ou initiale.

2. La zone d'étude et son intérêt

Le Jabal Jraid surplombe les villages de Hrajel et Faraya dans le caza (région administrative) du Kesrouane (figure 3) et présente divers avantages tant pour ce travail que pour des activités de recherches ultérieures :

Figure 3. Casa du Kesrouane, localisation du plateau

- ses altitudes s'étagent entre 1700 et 1900 m. Il est donc sujet à enneigement durable sur deux ou trois mois (Gascoin *et al.*, 2012);

- sa surface couvre environ 4 km² dans sa partie principale, il est ainsi assez facile à parcourir pour des études de terrain.

Par ailleurs, des recherches ultérieures sur son fonctionnement hydrogéologique pourraient bénéficier de ses caractéristiques suivantes :

- de par son insertion entre 4 vallées, celles de Nahr el Kalb et de Nahr Ibrahim, de Chabrouh et de Nabh el Qana, il représente un système quasi indépendant du

reste des hauts plateaux environnants. Il n'est rattaché au plateau de Ouyoun el Simane que par un mince éperon qui ne joue pas un rôle important dans son alimentation en eau souterraine (Bou Jaoudé *et al.*, 2010) (figure 4 et photo 2) ;

Figure 4. Photo 2. Le plateau de Jabal Jraid (image tirée de Google Earth : a) Plateau de Jabal Jraid ; b) barrage de Chabrouh ; c) partie du plateau de Ouyoun el Simane ; d) sources de Nabh el Cana)

- c'est un plateau calcaire présentant de multiples dolines qui constituent autant de contenants à neige et favorisent l'infiltration de l'eau. Ces dolines s'alignent pour la majorité sur des fractures en réseau dense ;

- les sources qui lui sont tributaires sont peu nombreuses (une vingtaine environ) ce qui peut permettre des mesures de débit pour évaluer la réponse du terrain au moment de la fonte des neiges ;

- la construction récente du barrage de Chabrouh semble avoir modifié les circulations d'eau souterraine (Bou Jaoudé *et al.*, 2010).

3. Matériels et méthodes

La surface « avant érosion ou initiale » est calculée en six étapes (figure 5). Elles sont effectuées à l'aide de trois logiciels dont les fonctionnalités sont complémentaires (EarthVision 8.1™, PCIGeomatica 10.1™ et ArcGIS 10™).

Figure 5. Les différentes étapes ou procédures de traitement

La topographie du lieu étant indispensable, un modèle numérique d'altitude (MNA) à 60 cm de résolution pour la surface du plateau a été réalisé par procédés photogrammétriques à partir de photos aériennes avec PCI Geomatica 10.1™ (Procédure 1 ou P1). Ce MNA, transformé en grille sous EarthVision 8.1™ a été corrigé avec un filtrage passe-bas (P2) afin de lisser et d'éliminer les artefacts.

générés suite aux erreurs de reconnaissance de points homologues lors de la procédure de réalisation du MNA (P1) (figure 6).

Figure 6. Le MNA filtré

Un nouveau MNA (raster) est élaboré sans les erreurs (P3). Afin de pouvoir calculer la surface avant érosion (initiale), les points hauts du paysage sont extraits à partir du relief actuel. Ils déterminent les limites de bassins-versants. Les lignes de crêtes sont analysées soit manuellement à partir des « interfluves » des dolines afin d'en extraire les contours (fichier vectoriel), soit automatiquement selon une procédure décrite ci-dessous. Il est possible d'utiliser indifféremment les fonctionnalités des logiciels PCIGeomatica 10.1TM ou ArcGis 10TM caractérisant l'hydrologie -ci permettent :

- d'identifier la direction du flux ;
- de définir les zones d'accumulation du flux ;

– de cerner les « bassins », soit les différentes zones de drainage ou, autrement dit, l'ensemble des sous-bassins versants de la zone.

Le traitement se poursuit par l'extraction des contours des bassins dans un format vectoriel et par l'attribution d'une altitude (issue du MNA) à tout point de la ligne. Cette étape est réalisée indistinctement par la procédure « Back interpolation » sous EarthVision 8.1™ ou par jointure spatiale entre le MNA et les points sous ArcGis 10™ ou PCIGeomatica 10.1™ (P5)

A partir des altitudes des points de crêtes, une nouvelle surface peut être interpolée, elle représente la surface avant érosion ou initiale. Elle permettra la réalisation du modèle volumique (figure 7) (P6). La capacité de rétention maximale du plateau (ou volume de rétention maximale de la neige) est obtenue par différence entre les deux surfaces représentant la topographie actuelle et la topographie dite initiale, soit respectivement le MNA et la surface avant-érosion.

4. Résultats et discussion

Le modèle volumique est réalisé à partir de deux surfaces. La première correspond à la surface avant érosion (passant par les points des crêtes de chaque doline et dont la modélisation a été décrite par les procédures P4 à P6). La seconde correspond à la surface actuelle du plateau (MNA). La soustraction de ces deux surfaces permet alors d'obtenir une image des creux et dépressions et d'en calculer le volume en mètres cubes. Celui-ci équivaut donc à la capacité maximum de rétention du couvert neigeux. Dans le cas présent il est égal à 1 218 339 m³.

Quelques paramètres peuvent modifier légèrement les résultats. L'intérieur des dolines a souvent une morphologie en marches d'escaliers due à l'érosion différentielle entre des couches dures et des couches tendres. Cette forme caractéristique du relief peut partiellement disparaître en fonction du filtrage qui gomme également des fractures importantes incisant le plateau sur plusieurs dizaines de mètres. Par ailleurs, la grille représentant la surface de la couche « avant érosion » montre à certains endroits des courbures (concavités et/ou convexités) qui peuvent varier en fonction du facteur de « tension » utilisé lors de l'interpolation (P5). Celles-ci sont déterminantes dans le calcul de volume. La modification de la tension de la grille (Somma et Luxey, 2006) entraîne des variations sur le calcul du volume. A titre d'exemple, un volume de 1 218 339 m³ est obtenu avec un facteur de tension de 1 et un volume de 1 218 003 m³ avec un facteur de 4¹. Toutefois, dans le cas présent, l'écart entre les deux résultats est minime (0,26 %).

1. EarthVision utilise une technique de tension minimale (courbure minimum) pour générer des maillages 2D à partir des données. Cette technique de tension est un algorithme spline bicubique itératif qui cherche à respecter les données d'entrée pour le calcul de la grille. A chaque itération, la valeur du nœud est évaluée et comparée aux données. Si un (ou plusieurs) point d'origine (appelé facteur de tension) se trouve dans la demi-largeur d'une cellule, ce

Figure 7. Les étapes P1, P2, P4, P6 de réalisation du modèle

point est comparé au nœud. Au fur et à mesure, le résidu entre le nœud et les données diminue.

L'estimation des volumes calculés reste donc proche de la réalité. Un autre exemple le confirme : un suivi de la fonte des neiges dans une doline du plateau de Ouyoun el Simane (mentionné en 2) a été réalisé par levés topographiques précis à 4 différentes dates de la saison de fonte soit les 4 mai, 6 juin, 27 juin et 20 juillet 2012 (Abou Chakra, 2013) (figure 8). La comparaison entre les volumes calculés par Abou Chakra par différentes méthodes, notamment la méthode des sections², et les volumes calculés par le géomodeleur EarthVision 8.1TM, ne montre que de faibles écarts compris entre 0,7 % et 2,34 % d'erreur selon les dates.

Figure 8. Étapes de la fonte des neiges dans une doline du Jabal el Dib.
((a) le modèle volumique au 4 mai 2012 ; (b) vu en coupe)

2. Méthode offerte par le logiciel Land Desktop (AutoCAD®)

5. Conclusion

Cet essai méthodologique est une première étape qui vise à déterminer la capacité de rétention de la neige d'une partie du plateau de Jabal Jraid. La démarche adoptée donne des résultats cohérents malgré l'approximation imposée par les imperfections du MNA. Le volume moyen de stockage de neige sur la zone d'étude est d'environ 1,2 millions de m³. Une prochaine étape devrait mettre en comparaison les volumes de névés résiduels avec la capacité totale du plateau. L'imagerie satellitale à très haute résolution permettrait, en effet, de faire un suivi diachronique tout au long de la saison de fonte par la possibilité d'ancrer les pourtours de névés observés sur un MNA précis (Somma et Luxey, 2006). Un certain nombre d'observations pourraient alors être effectuées telles que la vitesse de fonte, les dates de disparition totale de névés, les évolutions sur plusieurs années et les tendances de diminution ou d'augmentation du couvert neigeux. Il serait intéressant de tester dans quelle mesure les images tri-stéréoscopiques Pléiades permettraient d'évaluer la hauteur d'un couvert neigeux continu, autorisant ainsi une observation de celui-ci sur une plus longue durée parce que mesuré plus tôt dans la saison.

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Bibliographie

- Abou Chakra C. (2013). Suivi topographique de la fonte des neiges : étude d'une doline des plateaux de Jabal el Dib (Ouyoun el Simane, Mont-Liban). Mémoire de Master, université Saint Joseph.
- Aouad A., Travi Y., Blavoux B., Job J.O., Najem W. (2004). Étude isotopique de la pluie et de la neige sur le Mont Liban: premiers résultats. *Journal des Sciences Hydrologiques*, vol. 49, n° 3, p. 429-441.
- Aouad-Rizk A., Job J.O., Khalil S., Touma T., Bitar C., Bocquillon C., Najem W. (2005). Snow in Lebanon: a preliminary study of snowcover over Mount Lebanon and a simple snowmelt model. *Journal des Sciences Hydrologiques* vol. 50, n° 3, p. 555-569.
- Bou Jaoude L., Karanouh R., Momjian N., Chehadeh A., Cheikh Hussein A. (2010). Understanding the leaks in Chabrouh dam through detailed hydrogeological analysis of the Qana plateau (Lebanon). *Advances Research in Karst Media, Environmental Earth Sciences*, Springer, p. 407-413.

- Bou-Jawdeh I., Metni M., Nader F. (2001). Identifying preferential karstic routes within the Qana plateau, Central Lebanon: a multidisciplinary approach. *The Proceedings of the Middle-East Speleology Symposium*, p. 94-103.
- Bernier M., Fortin J.P., Gauthier Y., Corbane C., Somma J., Dedieu J.P. (2003). Intégration de données satellitaires à la modélisation hydrologique du Mont Liban. *Journal des Sciences Hydrologiques*, vol. 48, n° 6.
- Corbane C., Somma J., Bernier M., Fortin J.P., Gauthier Y., Dedieu J.P. (2005). *Journal des Sciences Hydrologiques*, vol. 50, n° 2, p. 355-370.
- Corbane C., Somma J., Bernier M., Fortin J.P., Dedieu J.P., Gauthier Y. (2004). Application d'un modèle d'estimation de l'équivalent en eau du couvert nival à partir d'images RSO de Radarsat-1 en montagne libanaise. *Télédétection*, vol. 4, n° 1, p. 481-498.
- Drapeau L., Shaban A., Somma J. (2013). Pour un observatoire de la neige au Liban. L'eau face au changement climatique. *Séminaire présenté à l'IFPO (Institut Français pour le Proche Orient)*, mars.
- Gascoin S., Drapeau L., Dubertret F., Duchemin B., Maisongrande P. (2012). Variabilité spatiotemporelle de l'enneigement autour de la Méditerranée (Haut-Atlas, Mont-Liban, Pyrénées). Comité national français pour le changement global "les changements globaux : enjeux et défis", Toulouse, France 9-11/07/2012.
- Gédéon V., Somma J., Dhont D. (2004). Utilisation de la télédétection pour la modélisation de la fusion de la neige sur un plateau karstique du Mont Liban. *Communication aux « Journées Scientifiques » du réseau de Télédétection de l'AUF*.
- Gédéon V., Somma J., Dhont D. (2004). Volume assesment of névés trapped in the Nabh el Cana karstic plateau (Lebanon) from Ikonos and KVR imagery. *Présentation au colloque IGARSS (Anchorage, Alaska)*.
- Shaban A., Faour G., Khawlie M., Abdallah C. (2004). Remote sensing application to estimate the volume of water in the form of snow on Mount Lebanon. *Hydrological Science Journal*, vol. 49, n° 4, p. 643-653.
- Somma J., Luxey P. (2006). Modélisation volumique des névés sur les hauts plateaux karstiques du Mont Liban. *Publications du Colloque Watmed3*.

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Snow cover volumes dynamic monitoring during melting season using high topographic accuracy approach for a Lebanese high plateau witness sinkhole

Charbel Abou Chakra (1), Janine Somma (1), Taha Elali (1), and Laurent Drapeau (2)

(1) Remote Sensing Laboratory, Department of Geography, Saint Joseph University, (2) S.I.E. Group, Centre d'Etudes Spatiales de la Biosphère (CESBIO)

Climate change and its negative impact on water resource is well described. For countries like Lebanon, undergoing major population's rise and already decreasing precipitations issues, effective water resources management is crucial. Their continuous and systematic monitoring over long period of time is therefore an important activity to investigate drought risk scenarios for the Lebanese territory. Snow cover on Lebanese mountains is the most important water resources reserve. Consequently, systematic observation of snow cover dynamic plays a major role in order to support hydrologic research with accurate data on snow cover volumes over the melting season.

For the last 20 years few studies have been conducted for Lebanese snow cover. They were focusing on estimating the snow cover surface using remote sensing and terrestrial measurement without obtaining accurate maps for the sampled locations. Indeed, estimations of both snow cover area and volumes are difficult due to snow accumulation very high variability and Lebanese mountains chains slopes topographic heterogeneity. Therefore, the snow cover relief measurement in its three-dimensional aspect and its Digital Elevation Model computation is essential to estimate snow cover volume. Despite the need to cover the all lebanese territory, we favored experimental terrestrial topographic site approaches due to high resolution satellite imagery cost, its limited accessibility and its acquisition restrictions. It is also most challenging to modelise snow cover at national scale. We therefore, selected a representative witness sinkhole located at Ouyoun el Siman to undertake systematic and continuous observations based on topographic approach using a total station.

After four years of continuous observations, we acknowledged the relation between snow melt rate, date of total melting and neighboring springs discharges. Consequently, we are able to forecast, early in the season, dates of total snowmelt and springs low water flows which are essentially feeded by snowmelt water. Simulations were ran, predicting the snow level between two sampled dates, they provided promising result for national scale extrapolation.

AGU FALL MEETING

San Francisco | 15–19 December 2014

C43C-0404:

Geomatics contributions to key indicators for estimation and monitoring of snow cover input to hydrogeological resources

Thursday, 18 December 2014

Janine Somma¹, Laurent Drapeau², Charbel Abou Chakra³ and Taha El-Ali³, (1)Saint-Joseph University, Beirut, 1104, Lebanon, (2)IRD Institute for Research and Development, Marseille Cedex 02, France, (3)Saint Joseph University, Beirut, Lebanon

Abstract:

Climate change is a subject of concern for the inhabitants of the semi-arid zones because water needs are greatly increasing with population growth. For the Middle East region, the karstic geology of Lebanon with its high and steep mountains makes it a real water tower and promotes an essential snow cover. Studies carried out on snow water equivalent reserve [1] remain still insufficient for the development of continuous monitoring. Modeling the lebanese high plateau made of sinkholes and undulations eases the computations of land capacity for snow retention. It is therefore an interesting testing ground for snow volumes calculations [2]. To improve previous attempts, a research project focuses on snow melting processes. It uses the cessation date of snow melt water infiltration which is crucial in the precocity or the delay of low water level [3]; and geomatics to determinate the major factor for the evaluation of stored water (spatial or vertical extension of snow cover). The project studies the sensitivity of temporal snow melting variabilities to quantities of snow precipitations and climatic conditions. Field measurements were collected at very high topographic precision [4] in a specific sinkhole and were used to create volumes models for measuring indicators such as: snow water equivalent; melting speed in relation to climatic data; forecast of completed melting date; correlations with springs discharges. Other methodological procedures take into account snow depressions (sinkholes and ripples) capacity retention; daily webcam images to monitor the accumulation and melt rate and remotely sensed Pleiades stereoscopic images to create snow cover elevation model at the time of acquisition.

[1]Corbane et al., 2004 ; 2005 ; Corbane, 2002 ; Bernier et al., 2001, 2003 ; Shaban et al., 2004; Aouad et al., 2004, Aouad-Rizk et al., 2005 ; Gédéon el al., 2004

[2] Somma et al ; 2014

[3] Drapeau et al ; 2013

[4] Drapeau et al, 2013; Somma et Drapeau, 2011 ; Somma et Luxey, 2006

C13C-0972: Monitoring the snowpack volume in a sinkhole on Mount Lebanon using time lapse Photogrammetry

Monday, 11 December 2017

13:40 - 18:00

📍 New Orleans Ernest N. Morial Convention Center - Poster Hall D-F

Lebanon is one of the richest country in the Middle East for water resources, thanks to its mountain ranges that trigger precipitation from the moist air masses coming from the Mediterranean Sea.

Snowpack acts as natural water storage in winter and supply fresh water during spring and summer. Yet, Lebanon is facing a serious water scarcity problem due to: i) decreasing amount of precipitation and climate change; ii) major growth of population of original residence and large number of refugees during regional wars. Therefore, continuous and systematic monitoring of the Lebanese water resources is becoming crucial.

The Mount Lebanon is made of karstic depressions named "sinkholes". It is important to monitor the snowmelt process inside these sinkholes because of their key role as "containers" of seasonal snow. By isolating the snowpack from sun radiation and wind, they slow down the natural melting process and sublimation, thus delaying as well the low water flow period.

An observatory is set up to monitor the snowpack evolution in a pilot sinkhole located in Mount Lebanon. The system uses three time-lapse cameras and structure-from-motion principles to reconstruct the snow volume within the sinkhole. The approach is validated by standard topographic surveys. The results indicate that snow depth can be retrieved with an accuracy between 20 and 60 cm (residuals standard deviation) and a low bias of 50 cm after coregistration of the digital elevation models.

Authors

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Day: [Monday, 11 December 2017](#)

Management of Geomatics information and challenges towards sustainable development.

Qatar, Doha, 19 20 February

High accuracy snow cover monitoring using terrestrial approach for Lebanese high plateau of kfardebiane

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Abstract

Climate change and its impact on water resource is deeply discussed and described. Middle East and Arab countries are expected to face severe water challenges both in terms of quantity and quality. For countries like Lebanon, undergoing major population's rise and already decreasing precipitations issues, water scarcity level is at sight, in the coming years. Therefore, long term assessment to address deteriorating water resources is becoming crucial. Their continuous and systematic monitoring overs long period of time is therefore an important activity to investigate drought risk scenarios for the Lebanese territory.

Snowfall on Lebanon and Anti-Lebanon mountains are known to be a major input source for underground water. Accordingly, snow cover on Lebanese mountains is an important water resources reserve. Consequently, systematic observation of snow cover dynamic plays a major role in order to support hydrologic research with accurate data over the melting season. Snowpack act as natural water storage in winter, and supply fresh water during spring and summer. Estimation of water provided by snow requires accurate snow cover volume quantification.

However, this evaluation is difficult because of the relief heterogeneity and its impact on snow cover thickness distribution. It is then important to investigate new methodologies enabling these quantifications at low cost in terms of human resources and sensors for data collection. For the last 17 years few studies have been conducted for Lebanese snow cover. They were focusing on estimating snow density and snow cover surface using remote sensing and terrestrial measurements on some zones.

Since 2012, we monitored Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of snow cover evolution for a witness sinkhole at “Ouyoun el Simane” as DEM computation is essential to estimate snow cover volume and surface for further snow water equivalent evaluation. Modelisation of DEM was done by: i) topographic approach using a total station; ii) fixed stereoscopic cameras for daily observation.

Our objectives are to combine and compare topographic and terrestrial photogrammetry results prior to snow cover volume assessment in order to validate the low cost photogrammetric method for both methods.

Since the beginning of continuous observations for the witness sinkhole, we acknowledged the relation between snow melt rate, date of total melting and neighboring springs discharges. Consequently, we are able to forecast, early in the season, dates of total snowmelt and springs low water flows which are essentially fed by snowmelt water. Simulations were ran, predicting the snow level between two sampled dates. They provided promising result for national scale extrapolation.

Participation in the competition “Ma these en 3 minutes”

Appendix 2

Agisoft PhotoScan Reports for Snow cover monitoring by steady Cameras based on “Framed 6 GCPs upper top line)

Agisoft PhotoScan

Manual Markers / GCPs Test 7

4 June 2015

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	3	Camera stations:	3
Flying altitude:	75.9 m	Tie points:	3,366
Ground resolution:	1.55 cm/pix	Projections:	7,888
Coverage area:	6.51e+03 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.549 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μ m	No
Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm).

1 pix

Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)

1 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	3750.74
Cx:	184.401	B1:	32.1544
Cy:	120.627	B2:	48.7726
K1:	-0.0748126	P1:	0.0284068
K2:	0.179619	P2:	0.00242655
K3:	-0.319801	P3:	-0.685969
K4:	0.250879	P4:	0.689248

Camera Calibration

Fig. 3. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm).

1 pix

Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)

2 images

Resolution 4608 x 3456	Focal Length 5 mm	Pixel Size 1.34 x 1.34 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	3729.24
Cx:	170.774	B1:	14.1851
Cy:	189.451	B2:	41.1304
K1:	-0.0484353	P1:	0.0246121
K2:	0.0579643	P2:	0.0106386
K3:	-0.0855547	P3:	-0.199636
K4:	0.0696205	P4:	-0.0326416

Camera Locations

Fig. 4. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
1.9698	7.16518	6.54208	7.43101	9.90044

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 5. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
6	9.51098	24.5016	9.23202	26.2828	27.8571	0.153

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
44	-15.8299	1.85967	-15.0385	21.9135	0.210 (3)
41	10.0912	16.7312	4.86517	20.1354	0.113 (3)
121	1.75738	-21.1033	-3.98004	21.5471	0.164 (3)
114	4.86103	-35.3717	-9.57773	36.9665	0.092 (3)
116	-10.035	39.886	7.01205	41.7225	0.206 (3)
119	7.93203	5.58326	10.2377	14.1032	0.071 (3)
Total	9.51098	24.5016	9.23202	27.8571	0.153

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 6. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 6.19 cm/pix
Point density: 261 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	3
Aligned cameras	3
Markers	6
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	3,366 of 3,541
RMS reprojection error	0.176804 (0.549094 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.948003 (4.10812 pix)
Mean key point size	4.15972 pix
Effective overlap	2.34228
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Highest
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	59 seconds
Alignment time	3 minutes 16 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	0 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	713,976
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	3 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	1 seconds
Model	
Faces	173,554
Vertices	87,351
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	180,000
Processing time	3 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	1 seconds
Blending time	16 seconds
DEM	
Size	2,174 x 2,281
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	5 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	7,410 x 6,663
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	23 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Manual Markers / GCPs Test 7

18 June 2015

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	3	Camera stations:	3
Flying altitude:	69.6 m	Tie points:	5,138
Ground resolution:	1.58 cm/pix	Projections:	12,193
Coverage area:	5.55e+03 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.493 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μ m	No
Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm).

1 pix

Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)

1 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	3749.71
Cx:	681.324	B1:	110.858
Cy:	-5.18944	B2:	-58.8524
K1:	-0.074326	P1:	0.0477911
K2:	0.118365	P2:	-0.00769615
K3:	-0.0902827	P3:	0
K4:	0.0235657	P4:	0

Camera Calibration

Fig. 3. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm).

1 pix

Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)

2 images

Resolution 4608 x 3456	Focal Length 5 mm	Pixel Size 1.34 x 1.34 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	3704.16
Cx:	673.581	B1:	111.737
Cy:	146.745	B2:	-4.67335
K1:	-0.085975	P1:	0.0476519
K2:	0.159134	P2:	0.00237703
K3:	-0.161563	P3:	0
K4:	0.0656207	P4:	0

Camera Locations

Fig. 4. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
14.3572	17.513	9.48791	22.6458	24.553

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 5. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
6	30.7763	25.7216	23.3921	40.1096	46.4324	0.309

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
114	22.3192	-4.01188	-3.80605	22.9941	0.115 (3)
116	-28.8954	44.7254	-6.21279	53.6088	0.226 (3)
119	-32.04	-41.9138	15.4649	54.9772	0.383 (3)
121	45.1645	-8.40416	14.9216	48.3023	0.372 (3)
44	-23.8084	1.03828	-51.4412	56.6932	0.432 (3)
41	26.7727	11.1651	11.0471	31.0399	0.195 (3)
Total	30.7763	25.7216	23.3921	46.4324	0.309

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 6. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 6.31 cm/pix
Point density: 251 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	3
Aligned cameras	3
Markers	6
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	5,138 of 5,343
RMS reprojection error	0.159862 (0.492818 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.951366 (2.80943 pix)
Mean key point size	4.08459 pix
Effective overlap	2.3775
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Highest
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	10 seconds
Alignment time	1 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1, p2
Optimization time	0 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	702,938
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	4 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	1 seconds
Model	
Faces	176,432
Vertices	88,559
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	180,000
Processing time	3 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	2 seconds
Blending time	15 seconds
DEM	
Size	1,850 x 2,022
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	4 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	6,380 x 6,428
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	20 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Manual Markers / GCPs Test 7

29 June 2015

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	3	Camera stations:	3
Flying altitude:	67.6 m	Tie points:	5,195
Ground resolution:	1.6 cm/pix	Projections:	12,449
Coverage area:	5.37e+03 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.643 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μm	No
Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm).

1 pix

Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)

1 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	3668.38
Cx:	65.4407	B1:	51.2581
Cy:	300.442	B2:	11.1361
K1:	-0.0547636	P1:	0.0126095
K2:	-0.111722	P2:	-0.000346328
K3:	0.305845	P3:	-1.16188
K4:	-0.251802	P4:	1.49596

Camera Calibration

Fig. 3. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm).

1 pix

Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)

2 images

Resolution 4608 x 3456	Focal Length 5 mm	Pixel Size 1.34 x 1.34 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	3695.01
Cx:	-1.80023	B1:	26.1277
Cy:	299.033	B2:	42.6697
K1:	-0.0622256	P1:	0.0115946
K2:	-0.11391	P2:	0.0111236
K3:	0.299772	P3:	-1.78033
K4:	-0.202403	P4:	2.09657

Camera Locations

Fig. 4. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
1.15977	11.5579	2.6003	11.6159	11.9034

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 5. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
6	34.5566	28.5517	8.5259	44.8258	45.6295	0.309

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
121	12.8967	-26.4855	11.2007	31.5161	0.225 (3)
114	42.8693	-16.0592	8.76463	46.61	0.248 (3)
44	17.1816	-1.57044	-6.93169	18.5936	0.260 (3)
41	15.5309	2.84537	-4.9276	16.5404	0.138 (3)
116	-67.4376	60.3853	-12.2295	91.3442	0.550 (3)
119	-8.75217	-16.5793	3.46152	19.0645	0.269 (3)
Total	34.5566	28.5517	8.5259	45.6295	0.309

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 6. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 6.41 cm/pix
Point density: 244 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	3
Aligned cameras	3
Markers	6
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	5,195 of 5,356
RMS reprojection error	0.188752 (0.642517 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.7216 (4.47883 pix)
Mean key point size	3.55935 pix
Effective overlap	2.40011
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Highest
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	1 minutes 9 seconds
Alignment time	1 minutes 8 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	0 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	726,068
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	4 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	1 seconds
Model	
Faces	176,364
Vertices	88,550
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	180,000
Processing time	2 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	2 seconds
Blending time	14 seconds
DEM	
Size	1,820 x 1,972
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	4 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	6,219 x 6,211
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	17 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Manual Markers / GCPs Test 7

4 July 2015

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	3	Camera stations:	3
Flying altitude:	67.3 m	Tie points:	5,188
Ground resolution:	1.65 cm/pix	Projections:	12,479
Coverage area:	5.24e+03 m ²	Reprojection error:	0.409 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μ m	No
Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)	4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm).

Canon PowerShot A1300 (5 mm)

1 images

Resolution 4608 x 3456	Focal Length 5 mm	Pixel Size 1.34 x 1.34 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	3678.18
Cx:	50.8756	B1:	68.7736
Cy:	46.4264	B2:	43.6703
K1:	-0.00428223	P1:	0.0168186
K2:	-0.23664	P2:	-0.000696575
K3:	0.577586	P3:	-0.267971
K4:	-0.44686	P4:	0.196107

Camera Calibration

Fig. 3. Image residuals for Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm).

Canon PowerShot A1400 (5 mm)

2 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4608 x 3456	5 mm	1.34 x 1.34 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	3683.76
Cx:	31.7181	B1:	56.9543
Cy:	73.2615	B2:	43.5713
K1:	-0.0386246	P1:	0.0170203
K2:	-0.0945463	P2:	0.00667992
K3:	0.304663	P3:	-0.534219
K4:	-0.260961	P4:	0.519283

Camera Locations

Fig. 4. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.

Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total error (cm)
3.40873	4.2261	5.78976	5.42949	7.93729

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 5. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
6	35.3429	38.3839	14.8152	52.1771	54.2396	0.203

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
44	2.39068	-0.915865	-26.3921	26.516	0.129 (3)
41	21.1269	8.99131	-18.9282	29.7567	0.067 (3)
114	48.3381	-52.4447	3.4896	71.4087	0.274 (3)
121	14.8234	-25.2231	6.74185	30.0231	0.156 (3)
116	-66.9518	73.2823	1.41131	99.2715	0.314 (3)
119	1.95027	1.15217	14.2302	14.4094	0.168 (3)
Total	35.3429	38.3839	14.8152	54.2396	0.203

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 6. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 6.6 cm/pix
Point density: 229 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	3
Aligned cameras	3
Markers	6
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	5,188 of 5,356
RMS reprojection error	0.142226 (0.408625 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.649288 (3.35683 pix)
Mean key point size	3.1375 pix
Effective overlap	2.41075
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Highest
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	1 minutes 20 seconds
Alignment time	2 minutes 29 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	0 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	699,310
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	4 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	1 seconds
Model	
Faces	176,531
Vertices	88,650
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	180,000
Processing time	2 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	1 seconds
Blending time	13 seconds
DEM	
Size	1,713 x 1,898
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	4 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	5,865 x 6,008
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	16 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Appendix 3
Agisoft PhotoScan Reports for Snow cover measurement by Drone
for
Testing the impact of Flying height

Agisoft PhotoScan

Test of Flying height at 50m

28 March 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	60	Camera stations:	60
Flying altitude:	51.4 m	Tie points:	60,158
Ground resolution:	2 cm/pix	Projections:	216,817
Coverage area:	0.0377 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.992 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

60 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2343.93
Cx:	-3.18194	B1:	-5.56457
Cy:	-8.67707	B2:	-2.04295
K1:	-0.00502655	P1:	-0.000100807
K2:	-0.0149421	P2:	-0.000778928
K3:	0.0496451	P3:	-0.817851
K4:	-0.0249659	P4:	0.128609

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
22.3727	32.9388	53.0607	39.8184	66.3396

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
9	1.3807	2.14361	2.28021	2.54979	3.42064	0.110

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
77	0.244346	-4.41074	-0.568494	4.45394	0.053 (6)
74	1.63023	3.32742	0.722884	3.77517	0.050 (6)
73	-0.719337	1.01773	0.400729	1.30912	0.038 (6)
72	1.33331	-1.89442	0.106288	2.31902	0.063 (12)
75	-3.31446	-0.872335	1.82906	3.88485	0.104 (8)
76	1.01274	1.98847	-3.56401	4.20497	0.157 (9)
120	-0.290431	1.20043	4.71709	4.8761	0.143 (11)
121	-0.111683	-0.101358	-2.60243	2.6068	0.140 (12)
122	0.190701	-0.196044	-0.83996	0.883365	0.101 (10)
Total	1.3807	2.14361	2.28021	3.42064	0.110

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 8 cm/pix
Point density: 156 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	60
Aligned cameras	60
Markers	9
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	60,158 of 65,703
RMS reprojection error	0.146547 (0.992403 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.608774 (24.2615 pix)
Mean key point size	6.42288 pix
Effective overlap	3.76946
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	5 minutes 39 seconds
Alignment time	2 minutes 0 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	12 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	6,628,823
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	14 minutes 57 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	51 seconds
Model	
Faces	1,294,470
Vertices	649,104
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	1,325,764
Processing time	33 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	18 seconds
Blending time	2 minutes 16 seconds
Tiled Model	
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Tile size	256
Processing time	2 hours 21 minutes
DEM	

Size	4,626 x 4,675
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	25 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	12,353 x 14,161
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	3 minutes 30 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Test of Flying height at 100m

28 March 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	20	Camera stations:	20
Flying altitude:	103 m	Tie points:	20,477
Ground resolution:	4.03 cm/pix	Projections:	74,651
Coverage area:	0.0624 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.979 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

20 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2328.06
Cx:	0.982791	B1:	-4.61368
Cy:	-9.52297	B2:	-1.42239
K1:	-0.00807764	P1:	0.000545005
K2:	-9.9491e-05	P2:	-0.000122255
K3:	0.0275658	P3:	0
K4:	-0.0143977	P4:	0

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
23.0197	32.8214	53.3035	40.0893	66.6964

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
9	1.86213	2.11019	1.96624	2.81433	3.43315	0.140

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
77	1.30662	-4.54137	0.978952	4.82594	0.099 (7)
74	2.18088	3.02605	0.291123	3.74139	0.115 (8)
73	-0.119939	0.123636	-0.0203466	0.173451	0.105 (6)
72	0.246717	0.17223	2.84098	2.85687	0.112 (8)
75	-4.18003	0.827452	-1.4103	4.48846	0.135 (8)
76	-1.87162	1.27097	-3.33734	4.0319	0.142 (7)
120	1.60944	1.13079	2.37672	3.08509	0.104 (9)
121	-0.134828	0.567601	0.57352	0.818092	0.201 (11)
122	1.04156	-2.51978	-2.56428	3.74295	0.172 (9)
Total	1.86213	2.11019	1.96624	3.43315	0.140

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution:	16.1 cm/pix
Point density:	38.4 points/m ²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	20
Aligned cameras	20
Markers	9
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	20,477 of 22,047
RMS reprojection error	0.134082 (0.979264 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.747328 (19.2532 pix)
Mean key point size	6.8046 pix
Effective overlap	3.73008
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	1 minutes 34 seconds
Alignment time	28 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1, p2
Optimization time	2 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	2,569,643
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	4 minutes 40 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	13 seconds
Model	
Faces	501,369
Vertices	251,825
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	513,925
Processing time	11 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	7 seconds
Blending time	1 minutes 17 seconds
Tiled Model	
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Tile size	256
Processing time	4 hours 55 minutes
DEM	

Size	2,087 x 1,943
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	12 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	7,857 x 7,575
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	1 minutes 36 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Test of Flying height at 200m

28 March 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	12	Camera stations:	12
Flying altitude:	212 m	Tie points:	11,384
Ground resolution:	8.24 cm/pix	Projections:	43,125
Coverage area:	0.177 km ²	Reprojection error:	1.04 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

12 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2362.04
Cx:	-6.59056	B1:	2.0848
Cy:	-3.64096	B2:	-7.64464
K1:	-0.0193706	P1:	-2.66432e-05
K2:	0.0230955	P2:	-0.00084987
K3:	-0.0120311	P3:	0.211581
K4:	0.00840481	P4:	-1.01025

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
22.4826	34.3498	56.776	41.0534	70.0635

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
9	3.95989	4.75776	3.77083	6.19008	7.24819	0.152

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
77	0.521838	-2.64035	0.272153	2.70515	0.155 (9)
74	-1.25679	-1.50261	-1.60134	2.53015	0.111 (8)
73	-3.78833	4.34682	0.829284	5.82529	0.107 (9)
72	1.46176	-8.30154	1.70324	8.59962	0.079 (9)
75	7.90828	7.08468	1.80107	10.7693	0.139 (9)
76	-1.29638	-2.13135	-5.13133	5.70559	0.100 (9)
120	0.619522	-1.86176	8.20223	8.43366	0.200 (9)
121	-7.14839	6.74829	-0.570665	9.84706	0.249 (9)
122	2.66121	-1.71649	-4.95667	5.88191	0.146 (9)
Total	3.95989	4.75776	3.77083	7.24819	0.152

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 33 cm/pix
Point density: 9.2 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	12
Aligned cameras	12
Markers	9
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	11,384 of 12,718
RMS reprojection error	0.146508 (1.0414 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.549147 (16.1793 pix)
Mean key point size	6.90339 pix
Effective overlap	3.8885
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	1 minutes 20 seconds
Alignment time	39 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	6 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	1,582,093
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	2 minutes 45 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	10 seconds
Model	
Faces	307,141
Vertices	154,424
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	316,415
Processing time	6 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	7 seconds
Blending time	41 seconds
Tiled Model	
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Tile size	256
Processing time	6 hours 37 minutes
DEM	

Size	1,970 x 1,743
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	7 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	6,630 x 6,338
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	51 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Test of Flying height at 350m

28 March 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	8	Camera stations:	8
Flying altitude:	368 m	Tie points:	7,948
Ground resolution:	14.5 cm/pix	Projections:	29,360
Coverage area:	0.333 km ²	Reprojection error:	1.03 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

FC300S (3.61 mm)

8 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2389.68
Cx:	2.68802	B1:	-5.37391
Cy:	-6.10237	B2:	-3.57439
K1:	0.00558391	P1:	0.000714031
K2:	-0.0275641	P2:	-0.000934776
K3:	0.0422491	P3:	-1.47735
K4:	-0.00948244	P4:	1.13692

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
23.5728	32.9376	63.4257	40.5039	75.2555

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
9	4.62866	6.71805	8.58647	8.15823	11.8442	0.166

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
77	0.362068	-8.01708	-7.21556	10.7921	0.189 (8)
74	4.93916	3.37137	15.4992	16.6128	0.134 (8)
73	0.828171	9.80477	2.4225	10.1335	0.155 (8)
72	-9.32189	-9.26847	-4.14766	13.7842	0.076 (8)
75	-2.41386	-7.41996	-13.0277	15.1857	0.051 (8)
76	1.38975	3.60011	-2.12073	4.40337	0.107 (8)
120	-4.83145	7.42866	9.64356	13.0968	0.156 (8)
121	2.24416	-2.8607	6.13263	7.12945	0.300 (8)
122	6.67632	4.1385	-6.58483	10.2499	0.188 (8)
Total	4.62866	6.71805	8.58647	11.8442	0.166

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 58.2 cm/pix
Point density: 2.96 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	8
Aligned cameras	8
Markers	9
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	7,948 of 8,633
RMS reprojection error	0.144287 (1.02937 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.694119 (10.2933 pix)
Mean key point size	7.27514 pix
Effective overlap	3.73902
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	59 seconds
Alignment time	21 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	2 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	988,971
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	1 minutes 5 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	5 seconds
Model	
Faces	190,924
Vertices	96,063
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	197,787
Processing time	2 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	2 seconds
Blending time	28 seconds
Tiled Model	
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Tile size	256
Processing time	7 hours 45 minutes
DEM	

Size	1,658 x 1,537
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	6 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	5,256 x 5,246
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	37 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Test of Flying height at 500m

28 March 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	10	Camera stations:	10
Flying altitude:	583 m	Tie points:	11,151
Ground resolution:	20.9 cm/pix	Projections:	34,946
Coverage area:	0.918 km ²	Reprojection error:	1.26 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

10 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2643.38
Cx:	23.4244	B1:	-13.8398
Cy:	10.1487	B2:	-10.1492
K1:	0.0525268	P1:	0.000931098
K2:	-0.0914319	P2:	0.00056446
K3:	0.206575	P3:	5.80793
K4:	-0.115838	P4:	-4.32823

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
34.1769	37.9793	24.6661	51.0929	56.7354

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
9	4.64011	6.2026	16.2671	7.74615	18.0172	0.085

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
77	0.369007	-6.98688	-7.60952	10.3372	0.074 (6)
74	0.619864	7.11168	12.0799	14.0315	0.112 (7)
73	8.42074	9.36518	28.4286	31.0934	0.058 (6)
72	-6.36279	-9.71317	-19.4135	22.6211	0.064 (6)
75	-2.12753	-3.98861	-6.45592	7.88126	0.075 (7)
76	-6.48148	-1.71911	-8.03341	10.4643	0.072 (7)
120	5.88853	6.76649	25.4281	26.9638	0.089 (7)
122	0.777328	0.321619	-4.89723	4.96896	0.080 (6)
121	-0.21462	-0.228018	-14.6928	14.6961	0.107 (8)
Total	4.64011	6.2026	16.2671	18.0172	0.085

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 83.7 cm/pix
Point density: 1.43 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	10
Aligned cameras	10
Markers	9
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	11,151 of 11,987
RMS reprojection error	0.171043 (1.2595 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.892071 (14.1365 pix)
Mean key point size	7.81462 pix
Effective overlap	3.20155
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	1 minutes 35 seconds
Alignment time	46 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	4 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	1,327,029
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	1 minutes 35 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	5 seconds
Model	
Faces	255,559
Vertices	128,642
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	265,395
Processing time	4 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	2 seconds
Blending time	32 seconds
Tiled Model	
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Tile size	256
Processing time	8 hours 8 minutes
DEM	

Size	1,832 x 1,723
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	5 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	5,886 x 5,670
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	31 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Appendix 4
Agisoft PhotoScan Reports for Snow cover monitoring by Drone
at Jabal El Dib area at year 2017

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Jabal El Dib by drone at height of 100 m

28 March 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	39	Camera stations:	39
Flying altitude:	103 m	Tie points:	24,770
Ground resolution:	4 cm/pix	Projections:	126,985
Coverage area:	0.0745 km ²	Reprojection error:	1.21 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

39 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2329
Cx:	0.544794	B1:	-7.61941
Cy:	-9.39877	B2:	-1.73309
K1:	-0.00889205	P1:	0.000512604
K2:	-0.000920702	P2:	-0.000292914
K3:	0.0273955	P3:	0
K4:	-0.0140003	P4:	0

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
23.2835	33.0282	53.702	40.4102	67.2078

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
9	2.60117	2.63267	1.58607	3.70095	4.02649	0.123

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
77	0.590573	-4.18997	-0.707324	4.2901	0.084 (9)
74	0.15695	5.24278	0.168005	5.24782	0.095 (10)
73	-1.57425	1.31897	0.707913	2.17235	0.100 (11)
72	4.33609	-1.78344	1.88531	5.05339	0.084 (17)
122	-1.92351	-2.97674	-1.11755	3.71616	0.135 (18)
120	0.86574	1.70565	3.35094	3.85844	0.124 (14)
76	2.71019	0.577238	-1.28122	3.05285	0.085 (9)
75	-5.23688	0.493992	-1.56036	5.48667	0.124 (14)
121	0.148313	-0.260732	-1.22575	1.26192	0.188 (17)
Total	2.60117	2.63267	1.58607	4.02649	0.123

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 16 cm/pix
Point density: 39.1 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	39
Aligned cameras	39
Markers	9
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	24,770 of 29,905
RMS reprojection error	0.166452 (1.21404 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.06127 (22.7131 pix)
Mean key point size	6.69135 pix
Effective overlap	5.3803
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	5 minutes 21 seconds
Alignment time	51 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1, p2
Optimization time	1 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	3,247,959
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	9 minutes 29 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	33 seconds
Model	
Faces	630,101
Vertices	316,364
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	649,591
Processing time	13 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	8 seconds
Blending time	1 minutes 50 seconds
Tiled Model	
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Tile size	256
Processing time	1 hours 47 minutes
DEM	

Size	3,151 x 3,153
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled
Processing time	18 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	8,819 x 10,366
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	2 minutes 57 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Jabal El Dib by drone at height of 100 m

2 June 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	30	Camera stations:	30
Flying altitude:	110 m	Tie points:	20,617
Ground resolution:	4.22 cm/pix	Projections:	115,158
Coverage area:	0.0757 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.689 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

30 images

Resolution 4000 x 2250	Focal Length 3.61 mm	Pixel Size 1.7 x 1.7 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	2320.33
Cx:	-2.6625	B1:	-2.67911
Cy:	-11.0949	B2:	0.852602
K1:	-0.00348806	P1:	-0.000311816
K2:	-0.0259103	P2:	-0.000877892
K3:	0.0640847	P3:	-1.03813
K4:	-0.0317317	P4:	0.267075

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
22.7898	34.6915	5.1098	41.5075	41.8208

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
6	0.826273	1.07055	1.07559	1.35233	1.72791	0.090

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
801	-0.136134	-0.474165	-0.248338	0.552301	0.062 (9)
802	0.947154	1.54883	1.84017	2.585	0.111 (6)
804	-1.25065	-1.28573	-1.6882	2.46317	0.137 (7)
814	0.835475	1.05196	0.540526	1.44803	0.072 (5)
816	-0.854847	-1.10339	-0.572372	1.50859	0.089 (6)
808	0.433379	0.524925	0.153721	0.697849	0.060 (10)
Total	0.826273	1.07055	1.07559	1.72791	0.090

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 16.9 cm/pix
Point density: 35.1 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	30
Aligned cameras	30
Markers	6
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	20,617 of 21,961
RMS reprojection error	0.131506 (0.68902 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.565154 (9.5479 pix)
Mean key point size	5.19229 pix
Effective overlap	5.73726
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	2 minutes 59 seconds
Alignment time	16 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	5 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	3,040,038
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	10 minutes 32 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	33 seconds
Model	
Faces	587,556
Vertices	295,239
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	608,007
Processing time	18 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	5 seconds
Blending time	1 minutes 59 seconds
DEM	
Size	2,908 x 2,928
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	22 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	8,236 x 9,059
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	3 minutes 1 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Jabal El Dib by drone at height of 100 m

11 June 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	88	Camera stations:	88
Flying altitude:	114 m	Tie points:	55,108
Ground resolution:	4.41 cm/pix	Projections:	338,055
Coverage area:	0.205 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.819 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

88 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2321.58
Cx:	-4.37223	B1:	-4.21282
Cy:	-11.2636	B2:	0.417695
K1:	-0.00211842	P1:	-0.000240742
K2:	-0.0224651	P2:	-0.000664173
K3:	0.0540746	P3:	-0.753187
K4:	-0.0248605	P4:	-0.00413939

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
21.2455	33.3002	15.0199	39.5004	42.2596

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
8	1.65541	1.6632	1.11696	2.34662	2.59889	0.116

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
801	2.54954	2.13872	-1.63495	3.70774	0.061 (8)
802	0.508884	-0.982987	2.19874	2.46164	0.120 (11)
804	-0.430312	1.76716	-0.808048	1.99022	0.133 (14)
814	-0.463494	0.419281	-0.868518	1.07002	0.108 (14)
816	-3.41903	-3.39148	0.73974	4.87228	0.104 (14)
808	-0.311199	-0.896856	0.322862	1.00271	0.134 (10)
811	1.72549	0.277081	0.345687	1.78145	0.133 (12)
810	-0.00241043	0.952643	-0.543199	1.09663	0.100 (10)
Total	1.65541	1.6632	1.11696	2.59889	0.116

Table 4. Control points.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
808					0.051 (6)
Total					

Table 5. Check points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 17.6 cm/pix
Point density: 32.2 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	88
Aligned cameras	88
Markers	9
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	55,108 of 59,082
RMS reprojection error	0.145241 (0.81945 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.825864 (15.049 pix)
Mean key point size	5.47825 pix
Effective overlap	6.32531
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	19 minutes 30 seconds
Alignment time	35 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	12 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	7,204,987
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	54 minutes 35 seconds
Dense cloud generation time	2 minutes 25 seconds
Model	
Faces	1,405,878
Vertices	705,251
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	1,440,977
Processing time	52 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	52 seconds
Blending time	7 minutes 23 seconds
DEM	
Size	4,321 x 4,190
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	51 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	12,938 x 13,751
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	11 minutes 18 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Jabal El Dib by drone at height of 100 m

26 June 2017

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	68	Camera stations:	68
Flying altitude:	114 m	Tie points:	15,652
Ground resolution:	4.39 cm/pix	Projections:	179,251
Coverage area:	0.0836 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.767 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

68 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2301.39
Cx:	-5.68758	B1:	-7.17096
Cy:	-12.3885	B2:	-0.711145
K1:	-0.0018967	P1:	-0.000471192
K2:	-0.0204126	P2:	-0.000693685
K3:	0.0499418	P3:	-1.50457
K4:	-0.0227894	P4:	0.743553

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
22.6317	36.1105	6.71289	42.6164	43.1419

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
6	5.91315	4.42895	2.40639	7.38789	7.76992	0.141

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
801	-0.0524148	0.0867667	-1.47083	1.47432	0.087 (26)
802	-1.84335	-2.40743	4.46907	5.40057	0.197 (18)
804	10.1785	2.13157	-3.53739	10.9845	0.207 (15)
814	-9.93629	7.4658	-0.201387	12.4301	0.169 (10)
816	1.93342	-7.14372	0.0613381	7.40098	0.074 (17)
808	-0.56634	0.758846	0.225972	0.973474	0.106 (23)
Total	5.91315	4.42895	2.40639	7.76992	0.141

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 17.6 cm/pix
Point density: 32.4 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	68
Aligned cameras	68
Markers	6
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	15,652 of 22,220
RMS reprojection error	0.151132 (0.766561 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.26314 (6.89841 pix)
Mean key point size	5.15373 pix
Effective overlap	12.9876
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	19 minutes 59 seconds
Alignment time	1 minutes 22 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	13 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	3,214,757
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	1 hours 23 minutes
Dense cloud generation time	3 minutes 31 seconds
Model	
Faces	620,271
Vertices	311,575
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	642,950
Processing time	26 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	15 seconds
Blending time	5 minutes 57 seconds
DEM	
Size	3,253 x 3,148
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	31 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	8,375 x 10,629
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	5 minutes 55 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Appendix 5
Agisoft PhotoScan Reports for Snow cover monitoring by Drone
at Bou Mechleh area at year 2018

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Bou Mechleh by Drone at height of 150 m

18 March 2018

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	298	Camera stations:	298
Flying altitude:	134 m	Tie points:	79,684
Ground resolution:	4.98 cm/pix	Projections:	871,251
Coverage area:	0.51 km ²	Reprojection error:	1.16 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 3000	3.61 mm	1.56 x 1.56 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

298 images

Resolution 4000 x 3000	Focal Length 3.61 mm	Pixel Size 1.56 x 1.56 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	2358.76
Cx:	-7.221	B1:	-7.85629
Cy:	-9.08928	B2:	-0.230365
K1:	-0.00507061	P1:	-0.000520252
K2:	-0.0127803	P2:	-0.000781764
K3:	0.0400366	P3:	-1.14135
K4:	-0.0166827	P4:	0.442772

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
23.4488	35.5497	39.5059	42.5867	58.0891

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
16	5.1269	5.12128	5.02092	7.24656	8.81602	0.173

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
610	2.20584	5.27648	-2.20528	6.12945	0.118 (16)
600	-1.04088	-0.602305	-3.03094	3.2608	0.053 (17)
615	-4.40157	1.4521	8.67225	9.83313	0.214 (24)
604	-1.18716	3.02141	4.63575	5.65937	0.131 (15)
601	-2.52213	-0.565009	3.2056	4.1178	0.065 (24)
611	-7.13138	-4.01177	2.37103	8.51896	0.086 (23)
605	-3.17962	-3.75836	5.94467	7.71844	0.090 (20)
602	-0.264718	-3.66563	-4.19158	5.57461	0.102 (22)
616	-0.360786	-3.5097	-4.89726	6.03584	0.512 (21)
617	4.70589	4.49741	6.37301	9.10974	0.137 (26)
618	1.27052	0.661428	-2.62844	2.9934	0.113 (33)
609	3.34388	4.80298	-1.22847	5.9799	0.049 (20)
603	-5.5988	-10.9214	1.86905	12.4143	0.130 (26)
612	12.124	-6.22385	0.352065	13.6327	0.135 (25)
614	8.39191	10.4263	-3.26283	13.776	0.157 (20)
608	-6.52671	3.66795	-11.6842	13.877	0.145 (24)
Total	5.1269	5.12128	5.02092	8.81602	0.173

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 19.9 cm/pix
Point density: 25.2 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	298
Aligned cameras	298
Markers	16
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	79,684 of 111,076
RMS reprojection error	0.191035 (1.15976 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.60777 (32.7381 pix)
Mean key point size	5.62968 pix
Effective overlap	11.6183
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	37 minutes 53 seconds
Alignment time	11 minutes 25 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	12 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	16,429,798
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	4 hours 48 minutes
Dense cloud generation time	14 minutes 59 seconds
Model	
Faces	3,218,798
Vertices	1,612,930
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	3,285,959
Processing time	1 minutes 12 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	28 seconds
Blending time	23 minutes 53 seconds
DEM	
Size	6,765 x 6,623
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	1 minutes 35 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	20,275 x 19,645
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	25 minutes 24 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Bou Mechleh by Drone at height of 150 m

25 March 2018

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	287	Camera stations:	287
Flying altitude:	128 m	Tie points:	87,252
Ground resolution:	4.78 cm/pix	Projections:	938,654
Coverage area:	0.488 km ²	Reprojection error:	1.01 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300S (3.61 mm)	4000 x 3000	3.61 mm	1.56 x 1.56 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300S (3.61 mm).

FC300S (3.61 mm)

287 images

Resolution 4000 x 3000	Focal Length 3.61 mm	Pixel Size 1.56 x 1.56 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	2350.77
Cx:	-5.56117	B1:	-6.94269
Cy:	-9.7481	B2:	-1.3611
K1:	-0.00278619	P1:	-0.000432675
K2:	-0.0222524	P2:	-0.000745976
K3:	0.052861	P3:	-1.04458
K4:	-0.0226512	P4:	0.286791

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
23.0432	35.2354	25.6794	42.1014	49.3149

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
13	7.47861	9.18706	4.90876	11.8462	12.8229	0.112

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
600	-0.94587	-1.24842	-2.32518	2.80351	0.050 (13)
601	1.04171	-4.32445	1.21451	4.61097	0.067 (22)
604	4.31246	7.8319	-1.06284	9.00365	0.079 (14)
605	-10.3815	1.50117	4.40765	11.3779	0.086 (20)
606	5.52124	-8.87496	-0.0521244	10.4524	0.073 (18)
611	-10.6208	-14.4951	2.95823	18.2115	0.118 (18)
612	4.72218	-2.40926	-1.00506	5.39571	0.121 (24)
603	-6.63782	-4.08353	-3.82419	8.68103	0.137 (23)
602	-2.02914	10.9967	-5.13623	12.3055	0.096 (23)
614	16.8607	21.2959	-6.19674	27.8603	0.165 (20)
615	1.57088	-7.69023	12.3229	14.6103	0.177 (23)
618	4.78005	6.63035	4.03992	9.11764	0.098 (30)
616	-8.68175	-4.94777	-5.33528	11.3278	0.070 (16)
Total	7.47861	9.18706	4.90876	12.8229	0.112

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 19.1 cm/pix
Point density: 27.3 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	287
Aligned cameras	287
Markers	13
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	87,252 of 108,524
RMS reprojection error	0.18247 (1.01022 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.1014 (20.1407 pix)
Mean key point size	5.33663 pix
Effective overlap	11.4312
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	33 minutes 17 seconds
Alignment time	4 minutes 2 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	53 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	17,039,705
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	2 hours 10 minutes
Dense cloud generation time	8 minutes 37 seconds
Model	
Faces	3,335,625
Vertices	1,671,464
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	3,407,936
Processing time	39 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	36 seconds
Blending time	15 minutes 15 seconds
DEM	
Size	6,115 x 5,651
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	58 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	20,971 x 18,787
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	18 minutes 16 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Bou Mechleh by Drone at height of 150 m

6 April 2018

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	296	Camera stations:	296
Flying altitude:	124 m	Tie points:	132,185
Ground resolution:	3.06 cm/pix	Projections:	1,074,278
Coverage area:	0.431 km ²	Reprojection error:	1.07 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC6310 (8.8 mm)	5472 x 3078	8.8 mm	2.53 x 2.53 μm	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC6310 (8.8 mm).

FC6310 (8.8 mm)

296 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
5472 x 3078	8.8 mm	2.53 x 2.53 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	3727.5
Cx:	-5.66371	B1:	-23.2819
Cy:	-1.97492	B2:	-1.54178
K1:	0.00798659	P1:	-0.000201683
K2:	-0.0650415	P2:	0.00080071
K3:	0.130252	P3:	1.42949
K4:	-0.0850402	P4:	-1.06795

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
22.0386	36.3007	49.6037	42.4669	65.2991

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
11	3.87344	5.17529	2.1839	6.4643	6.82324	0.092

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
600	1.51544	-0.293277	-1.63827	2.25089	0.092 (11)
601	-7.85235	-10.701	4.22976	13.9306	0.089 (10)
602	5.56693	-1.19412	-3.31782	6.58973	0.095 (12)
609	-4.61377	7.62863	-0.0341147	8.91539	0.068 (11)
605	0.771741	-0.951582	1.19211	1.70945	0.103 (7)
604	2.84144	1.85161	2.0511	3.9635	0.100 (9)
611	-4.74568	5.58245	1.14438	7.41585	0.050 (10)
616	-0.0155675	-2.9618	0.845589	3.08019	0.052 (12)
618	2.20038	5.36311	-0.595608	5.82747	0.117 (18)
603	3.51392	2.40082	0.255729	4.26345	0.088 (16)
612	0.651737	-6.45013	-3.57865	7.40511	0.110 (14)
Total	3.87344	5.17529	2.1839	6.82324	0.092

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 12.2 cm/pix
Point density: 66.8 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	296
Aligned cameras	296
Markers	11
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	132,185 of 152,536
RMS reprojection error	0.197618 (1.06646 pix)
Max reprojection error	0.893065 (28.3154 pix)
Mean key point size	5.33634 pix
Effective overlap	8.36696
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	35 minutes 55 seconds
Alignment time	11 minutes 2 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	8 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	36,459,566
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	2 hours 20 minutes
Dense cloud generation time	15 minutes 16 seconds
Model	
Faces	7,169,226
Vertices	3,590,261
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	7,291,906
Processing time	1 minutes 54 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	1 minutes 9 seconds
Blending time	25 minutes 7 seconds
DEM	
Size	9,072 x 8,592
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	1 minutes 55 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	29,984 x 28,106
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	30 minutes 28 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Bou Mechleh by Drone at height of 150 m

14 April 2018

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	292	Camera stations:	292
Flying altitude:	129 m	Tie points:	105,665
Ground resolution:	4.89 cm/pix	Projections:	1,019,647
Coverage area:	0.465 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.907 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300X (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300X (3.61 mm).

FC300X (3.61 mm)

292 images

Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μm	No
Type:	Frame	F:	2376.21
Cx:	24.5809	B1:	-8.53268
Cy:	0.510067	B2:	0.438168
K1:	-0.000417629	P1:	0.00139786
K2:	-0.0361736	P2:	-0.000535267
K3:	0.0732974	P3:	-0.384779
K4:	-0.0353826	P4:	-0.233085

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
22.0789	36.9202	21.8524	43.0184	48.2505

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
12	3.63974	8.1051	4.84873	8.88484	10.1218	0.125

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
605	-1.40731	1.99357	0.442236	2.48001	0.064 (13)
606	-2.46897	0.655756	1.53705	2.98134	0.068 (15)
602	7.34008	1.88649	-4.26541	8.69651	0.066 (17)
601	-2.59715	-5.89967	1.62514	6.64774	0.072 (22)
604	3.66499	-5.93691	-0.140334	6.97845	0.072 (10)
611	-3.0581	-1.04875	4.86506	5.84129	0.090 (16)
616	2.11965	-17.0322	-0.769748	17.1808	0.113 (16)
618	-1.86821	8.8389	2.34852	9.33445	0.090 (26)
600	1.0303	-1.65061	-2.77716	3.39096	0.077 (11)
603	-4.23405	0.769066	-0.57447	4.3415	0.088 (22)
614	5.08639	-0.850166	-11.3408	12.4583	0.216 (19)
615	-3.8271	18.3558	9.60601	21.0679	0.269 (16)
Total	3.63974	8.1051	4.84873	10.1218	0.125

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 19.6 cm/pix
Point density: 26.1 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	292
Aligned cameras	292
Markers	12
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	105,665 of 123,999
RMS reprojection error	0.169126 (0.907475 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.02947 (18.7215 pix)
Mean key point size	5.27405 pix
Effective overlap	10.0544
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	28 minutes 20 seconds
Alignment time	7 minutes 55 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	17 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	15,465,855
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	1 hours 31 minutes
Dense cloud generation time	5 minutes 12 seconds
Model	
Faces	3,031,528
Vertices	1,519,020
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	3,093,170
Processing time	55 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	23 seconds
Blending time	8 minutes 55 seconds
DEM	
Size	5,853 x 5,413
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	49 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	19,663 x 18,049
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	11 minutes 28 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Agisoft PhotoScan

Snow cover at Bou Mechleh by Drone at height of 150 m

24 April 2018

Survey Data

Fig. 1. Camera locations and image overlap.

Number of images:	304	Camera stations:	304
Flying altitude:	125 m	Tie points:	105,684
Ground resolution:	4.8 cm/pix	Projections:	1,060,797
Coverage area:	0.472 km ²	Reprojection error:	0.923 pix

Camera Model	Resolution	Focal Length	Pixel Size	Precalibrated
FC300X (3.61 mm)	4000 x 2250	3.61 mm	1.7 x 1.7 μ m	No

Table 1. Cameras.

Camera Calibration

Fig. 2. Image residuals for FC300X (3.61 mm).

FC300X (3.61 mm)

304 images

Resolution 4000 x 2250	Focal Length 3.61 mm	Pixel Size 1.7 x 1.7 μm	Precalibrated No
Type:	Frame	F:	2339.76
Cx:	27.4694	B1:	-8.4986
Cy:	-0.0679543	B2:	0.701778
K1:	-0.00203077	P1:	0.00125482
K2:	-0.028049	P2:	-0.000441371
K3:	0.0586325	P3:	-0.362636
K4:	-0.027266	P4:	-0.216301

Camera Locations

Fig. 3. Camera locations and error estimates.

Z error is represented by ellipse color. X,Y errors are represented by ellipse shape.
 Estimated camera locations are marked with a black dot.

X error (m)	Y error (m)	Z error (m)	XY error (m)	Total error (m)
22.2962	34.8922	18.8888	41.4076	45.5124

Table 2. Average camera location error.

Ground Control Points

Fig. 4. GCP locations.

Count	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	XY error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
18	9.78419	13.5616	5.3747	16.7227	17.5652	0.252

Table 3. Control points RMSE.

Label	X error (cm)	Y error (cm)	Z error (cm)	Total (cm)	Image (pix)
609	-30.6974	42.6114	0.556179	52.5202	0.364 (15)
605	8.33506	-2.12609	0.767297	8.6361	0.096 (15)
607	11.5308	-21.7101	-4.24662	24.9463	0.494 (14)
604	2.71089	6.13472	9.11272	11.3148	0.728 (12)
613	2.51041	7.68577	-7.6158	11.1074	0.138 (22)
606	17.6	-10.896	1.7653	20.775	0.331 (16)
600	1.82896	0.33853	-1.64248	2.48142	0.063 (11)
601	1.879	-15.9669	2.08524	16.2117	0.154 (20)
602	-3.27084	-7.01972	0.499555	7.76044	0.132 (15)
603	-0.0330782	-5.29793	2.50547	5.8606	0.082 (12)
608	-7.46255	-0.814627	-0.481728	7.52233	0.167 (17)
610	-7.52711	-6.21159	-8.20272	12.7486	0.353 (12)
611	-0.770084	10.5793	5.03722	11.7426	0.143 (17)
614	9.7104	-13.4808	-12.7222	20.9255	0.144 (11)
615	-5.25008	8.44142	7.51853	12.4639	0.122 (16)
616	-0.935316	-2.73137	-2.84846	4.05573	0.067 (18)
617	-1.24741	1.96156	4.89027	5.41465	0.109 (18)
618	0.414891	7.45968	-0.0860522	7.4717	0.081 (24)
Total	9.78419	13.5616	5.3747	17.5652	0.252

Table 4. Control points.

Digital Elevation Model

Fig. 5. Reconstructed digital elevation model.

Resolution: 19.2 cm/pix
Point density: 27.1 points/m²

Processing Parameters

General	
Cameras	304
Aligned cameras	304
Markers	18
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Point Cloud	
Points	105,684 of 125,639
RMS reprojection error	0.179622 (0.922975 pix)
Max reprojection error	1.2451 (21.7661 pix)
Mean key point size	5.11325 pix
Effective overlap	10.3706
Alignment parameters	
Accuracy	Medium
Pair preselection	Reference
Key point limit	40,000
Tie point limit	4,000
Constrain features by mask	No
Adaptive camera model fitting	Yes
Matching time	18 minutes 17 seconds
Alignment time	4 minutes 7 seconds
Optimization parameters	
Parameters	f, b1, b2, cx, cy, k1-k4, p1-p4
Optimization time	12 seconds
Dense Point Cloud	
Points	16,282,592
Reconstruction parameters	
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Depth maps generation time	1 hours 24 minutes
Dense cloud generation time	5 minutes 33 seconds
Model	
Faces	3,186,035
Vertices	1,596,436
Texture	4,096 x 4,096, uint8
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface type	Height field
Source data	Dense
Interpolation	Enabled
Quality	Medium
Depth filtering	Aggressive
Face count	3,256,518
Processing time	38 seconds
Texturing parameters	
Mapping mode	Orthophoto
Blending mode	Mosaic
Texture size	4,096 x 4,096
Enable color correction	Yes
Enable hole filling	Yes
UV mapping time	19 seconds
Blending time	9 minutes 31 seconds
DEM	
Size	7,011 x 6,913
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Reconstruction parameters	
Source data	Dense cloud
Interpolation	Enabled

Processing time	1 minutes 2 seconds
Orthomosaic	
Size	21,079 x 19,307
Coordinate system	Deir ez Zor / Levant Stereographic (EPSG:22780)
Channels	3, uint8
Blending mode	Mosaic
Reconstruction parameters	
Surface	Mesh
Enable color correction	Yes
Processing time	12 minutes 6 seconds
Software	
Version	1.2.6 build 2834
Platform	Windows 64 bit

Appendix 6

Phantom III advanced, Phantom III professional and Phantom IV professional Specifications

PHANTOM 3 ADVANCED SPECS

AIRCRAFT

Weight (Battery & Propellers Included)	1280 g
Diagonal Size (Propellers Excluded)	350 mm
Max Ascent Speed	5 m/s
Max Descent Speed	3 m/s
Max Speed	16 m/s (ATTI mode)
Max Tilt Angle	35°
Max Angular Speed	150°/s
Max Service Ceiling Above Sea Level	19685 feet (6000 m)
Max Flight Time	Approx. 23 minutes
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)
Satellite Positioning Systems	GPS/GLONASS

Hover Accuracy Range	Vertical: ±0.1 m (with Vision Positioning) ±0.5 m (with GPS Positioning) Horizontal: ±0.3 m (with Vision Positioning) ±1.5 m (with GPS Positioning)
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GIMBAL

Stabilization	3-axis (pitch, roll, yaw)
Controllable Range	Pitch: -90° to +30°
Max Controllable Angular Speed	Pitch: 90°/s
Angular Control Accuracy	±0.02°

REMOTE CONTROLLER

Operating Frequency	2.400 - 2.483 GHz
Max Transmission Distance	FCC Compliant: 3.1 mi (5 km) CE Compliant: 2.2 mi (3.5 km) (Unobstructed, free of interference)
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)
Battery	6000 mAh LiPo 2S
Transmitter Power (EIRP)	FCC: 20 dBm CE: 16 dBm MIC: 16 dBm
Operating Current/Voltage	1.2 A@7.4 V
Video Output Port	USB
Mobile Device Holder	Tablets and smart phones

INTELLIGENT FLIGHT BATTERY

Capacity	4480 mAh
Voltage	15.2 V

Battery Type	LiPo 4S
Energy	68 Wh
Net Weight	365 g
Charging Temperature Range	41° to 104°F (5° to 40°C)
Max Charging Power	100 W

The Phantom 3 Advanced has been certified by Apple in their Works with iMovie and Works with Final Cut Pro X programs, so you can edit 4K without worry whether you are a professional or shooting for fun.

CAMERA

Sensor	1/2.3" CMOS Effective pixels: 12.4 M (total pixels: 12.76 M)
Lens	FOV 94° 20 mm (35 mm format equivalent) f/2.8 focus at ∞
ISO Range	100-3200 (video) 100-1600 (photo)
Electronic Shutter Speed	8 - 1/8000 s
Image Size	4000×3000
Still Photography Modes	Single Shot Burst Shooting: 3/5/7 frames Auto Exposure Bracketing (AEB): 3/5 bracketed frames at 0.7 EV Bias Timelapse
Video Recording Modes	2.7K: 2704 x1520p 24/25/30 (29.97) FHD: 1920x1080p 24/25/30/48/50/60 HD: 1280x720p 24/25/30/48/50/60
Max Video Bitrate	40 Mbps

Supported File Systems	FAT32 (≤32 GB); exFAT (>32 GB)
Photo	JPEG, DNG (RAW)
Video	MP4, MOV (MPEG-4 AVC/H.264)
Supported SD Cards	Micro SD Max capacity: 64 GB Class 10 or UHS-I rating required
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)

VISION SYSTEM

Vision System	Downward Vision System
Velocity Range	≤8 m/s (2 m above ground)
Altitude Range	30 - 300 cm
Operating Range	50 - 300 cm
Operating Environment	Surface with clear pattern and adequate lighting (lux>15)

CHARGER

Voltage	17.4 V
Rated Power	57 W

APP / LIVE VIEW

Mobile App	DJI GO
Live View Working Frequency	2.4 GHz ISM
Live View Quality	720P @ 30fps
Latency	220ms (depending on conditions and mobile device)
Required Operating Systems	iOS 8.0 or later Android 4.1.2 or later
Recommended Devices	ios: iPhone 5s, iPhone 6, iPhone 6 Plus, iPhone 6s, iPhone 6s Plus, iPod touch 6, iPad Pro, iPad Air, iPad Air Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad

mini 2, iPad mini 2 Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad Air 2, iPad Air 2 Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad mini 3, iPad mini 3 Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad mini 4, and iPad mini 4 Wi-Fi + Cellular. This app is optimized for iPhone 5s, iPhone 6, iPhone 6 Plus, iPhone 6s and iPhone 6s Plus.

Android: Samsung tabs 705c, Samsung S6, Samsung S5, Samsung NOTE4, Samsung NOTE3, Google Nexus 9, Google Nexus 7 II, Ascend Mate7, Huawei Mate 8, Nubia Z7 mini, SONY Xperia Z3, MI 3, MI PAD

*Support for additional Android devices available as testing and development continues.

PHANTOM 3 PROFESSIONAL SPECS

AIRCRAFT

Weight (Battery & Propellers Included)	1280 g
Diagonal Size (Propellers Excluded)	350 mm
Max Ascent Speed	5 m/s
Max Descent Speed	3 m/s
Max Speed	16 m/s (ATTI mode)
Max Tilt Angle	35°
Max Angular Speed	150°/s
Max Service Ceiling Above Sea Level	19685 feet (6000 m)
Max Flight Time	Approx. 23 minutes
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)
Satellite Positioning Systems	GPS/GLONASS

Hover Accuracy Range	Vertical: ±0.1 m (with Vision Positioning) ±0.5 m (with GPS Positioning) Horizontal: ±0.3 m (with Vision Positioning) ±1.5 m (with GPS Positioning)
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GIMBAL

Stabilization	3-axis (pitch, roll, yaw)
Controllable Range	Pitch: -90° to +30°
Max Controllable Angular Speed	Pitch: 90°/s
Angular Control Accuracy	±0.02°

REMOTE CONTROLLER

Operating Frequency	2.400 - 2.483 GHz
Max Transmission Distance	FCC Compliant: 3.1 mi (5 km) CE Compliant: 2.2 mi (3.5 km) (Unobstructed, free of interference)
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)
Battery	6000 mAh LiPo 2S
Transmitter Power (EIRP)	FCC: 20 dBm CE: 16 dBm MIC: 16 dBm
Operating Current/Voltage	1.2 A@7.4 V
Video Output Port	USB
Mobile Device Holder	Tablets and smart phones

INTELLIGENT FLIGHT BATTERY

Capacity	4480 mAh
Voltage	15.2 V

Battery Type	LiPo 4S
Energy	68 Wh
Net Weight	365 g
Charging Temperature Range	41° to 104°F (5° to 40°C)
Max Charging Power	100 W

The Phantom 3 Professional has been certified by Apple in their Works with iMovie and Works with Final Cut Pro X programs, so you can edit 4K without worry whether you are a professional or shooting for fun.

CAMERA

Sensor	1/2.3" CMOS Effective pixels: 12.4 M (total pixels: 12.76 M)
Lens	FOV 94° 20 mm (35 mm format equivalent) f/2.8 focus at ∞
ISO Range	100-3200 (video) 100-1600 (photo)
Electronic Shutter Speed	8 - 1/8000 s
Image Size	4000×3000
Still Photography Modes	Single Shot Burst Shooting: 3/5/7 frames Auto Exposure Bracketing (AEB): 3/5 bracketed frames at 0.7 EV Bias Timelapse
Video Recording Modes	UHD: 4096x2160p 24/25, 3840x2160p 24/25/30 FHD: 1920x1080p 24/25/30/48/50/60 HD: 1280x720p 24/25/30/48/50/60
Max Video Bitrate	60 Mbps

Supported File Systems	FAT32 (≤32 GB); exFAT (>32 GB)
Photo	JPEG, DNG (RAW)
Video	MP4, MOV (MPEG-4 AVC/H.264)
Supported SD Cards	Micro SD Max capacity: 64 GB Class 10 or UHS-I rating required
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)

VISION SYSTEM

Vision System	Downward Vision System
Velocity Range	≤8 m/s (2 m above ground)
Altitude Range	30 - 300 cm
Operating Range	50 - 300 cm
Operating Environment	Surface with clear pattern and adequate lighting (lux>15)

CHARGER

Voltage	17.4 V
Rated Power	100 W

APP / LIVE VIEW

Mobile App	DJI GO
Live View Working Frequency	2.4 GHz ISM
Live View Quality	720P @ 30fps
Latency	220ms (depending on conditions and mobile device)
Required Operating Systems	iOS 8.0 or later Android 4.1.2 or later
Recommended Devices	ios: iPhone 5s, iPhone 6, iPhone 6 Plus, iPhone 6s, iPhone 6s Plus, iPod touch 6, iPad Pro, iPad Air, iPad Air Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad

mini 2, iPad mini 2 Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad Air 2, iPad Air 2 Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad mini 3, iPad mini 3 Wi-Fi + Cellular, iPad mini 4, and iPad mini 4 Wi-Fi + Cellular. This app is optimized for iPhone 5s, iPhone 6, iPhone 6 Plus, iPhone 6s and iPhone 6s Plus.

Android: Samsung tabs 705c, Samsung S6, Samsung S5, Samsung NOTE4, Samsung NOTE3, Google Nexus 9, Google Nexus 7 II, Ascend Mate7, Huawei Mate 8, Nubia Z7 mini, SONY Xperia Z3, MI 3, MI PAD

*Support for additional Android devices available as testing and development continues.

PHANTOM 4 PRO SPECS

AIRCRAFT

Weight (Battery & Propellers Included)	1388 g
Diagonal Size (Propellers Excluded)	350 mm
Max Ascent Speed	S-mode: 6 m/s P-mode: 5 m/s
Max Descent Speed	S-mode: 4 m/s P-mode: 3 m/s
Max Speed	S-mode: 45 mph (72 kph) A-mode: 36 mph (58 kph) P-mode: 31 mph (50 kph)
Max Tilt Angle	S-mode: 42° A-mode: 35° P-mode: 25°

Max Angular Speed	S-mode: 250°/s A-mode: 150°/s
Max Service Ceiling Above Sea Level	19685 feet (6000 m)
Max Wind Speed Resistance	10 m/s
Max Flight Time	Approx. 30 minutes
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)
Satellite Positioning Systems	GPS/GLONASS
Hover Accuracy Range	Vertical: ±0.1 m (with Vision Positioning) ±0.5 m (with GPS Positioning) Horizontal: ±0.3 m (with Vision Positioning) ±1.5 m (with GPS Positioning)

VISION SYSTEM

Vision System	Forward Vision System Backward Vision System Downward Vision System
Velocity Range	≤31 mph (50 kph) at 6.6 ft (2 m) above ground
Altitude Range	0 - 33 feet (0 - 10 m)
Operating Range	0 - 33 feet (0 - 10 m)
Obstacle Sensory Range	2 - 98 feet (0.7 - 30 m)
FOV	Forward: 60°(Horizontal), ±27°(Vertical) Backward: 60°(Horizontal), ±27°(Vertical) Downward: 70°(Front and Rear), 50°(Left and Right)

Measuring Frequency	Forward: 10 Hz Backward: 10 Hz Downward: 20 Hz
Operating Environment	Surface with clear pattern and adequate lighting (lux>15)
CAMERA	
Sensor	1" CMOS Effective pixels: 20M
Lens	FOV 84° 8.8 mm/24 mm (35 mm format equivalent) f2.8 - f11 auto focus at 1 m - ∞
ISO Range	Video: 100 - 3200 (Auto) 100 - 6400 (Manual) Photo: 100 - 3200 (Auto) 100- 12800 (Manual)
Mechanical Shutter Speed	8 - 1/2000 s
Electronic Shutter Speed	8 - 1/8000 s
Image Size	3:2 Aspect Ratio: 5472 × 3648 4:3 Aspect Ratio: 4864 × 3648 16:9 Aspect Ratio: 5472 × 3078
PIV Image Size	4096×2160(4096×2160 24/25/30/48/50p) 3840×2160(3840×2160 24/25/30/48/50/60p) 2720×1530(2720×1530 24/25/30/48/50/60p) 1920×1080(1920×1080 24/25/30/48/50/60/120p) 1280×720(1280×720 24/25/30/48/50/60/120p)
Still Photography Modes	Single Shot Burst Shooting: 3/5/7/10/14 frames Auto Exposure Bracketing (AEB): 3/5 bracketed frames at 0.7 EV

	<p>Bias</p> <p>Interval: 2/3/5/7/10/15/20/30/60 s</p>
Video Recording Modes	<p>H.265</p> <p>C4K:4096×2160 24/25/30p @100Mbps 4K:3840×2160 24/25/30p @100Mbps 2.7K:2720×1530 24/25/30p @65Mbps 2.7K:2720×1530 48/50/60p @80Mbps FHD:1920×1080 24/25/30p @50Mbps FHD:1920×1080 48/50/60p @65Mbps FHD:1920×1080 120p @100Mbps HD:1280×720 24/25/30p @25Mbps HD:1280×720 48/50/60p @35Mbps HD:1280×720 120p @60Mbps</p> <p>H.264</p> <p>C4K:4096×2160 24/25/30/48/50/60p @100Mbps 4K:3840×2160 24/25/30/48/50/60p @100Mbps 2.7K:2720×1530 24/25/30p @80Mbps 2.7K:2720×1530 48/50/60p @100Mbps FHD:1920×1080 24/25/30p @60Mbps FHD:1920×1080 48/50/60 @80Mbps FHD:1920×1080 120p @100Mbps HD:1280×720 24/25/30p @30Mbps HD:1280×720 48/50/60p @45Mbps HD:1280×720 120p @80Mbps</p>
Max Video Bitrate	100 Mbps
Supported File Systems	FAT32 (≤32 GB); exFAT (>32 GB)
Photo	JPEG, DNG (RAW), JPEG + DNG
Video	MP4/MOV (AVC/H.264; HEVC/H.265)
Supported SD Cards	<p>Micro SD</p> <p>Max Capacity: 128GB</p> <p>Write speed ≥15MB/s, Class 10 or UHS-I rating required</p>

Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)
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CHARGER

Voltage	17.4 V
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Rated Power	100 W
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APP / LIVE VIEW

Mobile App	DJI GO 4
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Live View Working Frequency	2.4 GHz ISM, 5.8 GHz ISM
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Live View Quality	720P @ 30fps
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Latency	Phantom 4 Pro: 220 ms (depending on conditions and mobile device) Phantom 4 Pro V : 160 - 180 ms
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Required Operating Systems	iOS 9.0 or later Android 4.4.0 or later
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GIMBAL

Stabilization	3-axis (pitch, roll, yaw)
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Controllable Range	Pitch: -90° to +30°
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Max Controllable Angular Speed	Pitch: 90°/s
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Angular Vibration Range	±0.02°
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INFRARED SENSING SYSTEM

Obstacle Sensory Range	0.6 - 23 feet (0.2 - 7 m)
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FOV	70° (Horizontal), ±10° (Vertical)
Measuring Frequency	10 Hz
Operating Environment	Surface with diffuse reflection material, and reflectivity > 8% (such as wall, trees, humans, etc.)

REMOTE CONTROLLER

Operating Frequency	2.400 - 2.483 GHz and 5.725 - 5.825 GHz
Max Transmission Distance	2.400 - 2.483 GHz (Unobstructed, free of interference) FCC: 4.3 mi (7 km) CE: 2.2 mi (3.5 km) SRRC: 2.5 mi (4 km) 5.725 - 5.825 GHz (Unobstructed, free of interference) FCC: 4.3 mi (7 km) CE: 1.2 mi (2 km) SRRC: 3.1 mi (5 km)
Operating Temperature Range	32° to 104°F (0° to 40°C)
Battery	6000 mAh LiPo 2S
Transmitter Power (EIRP)	2.400 - 2.483 GHz FCC: 26 dBm CE: 17 dBm SRRC: 20 dBm MIC: 17 dBm 5.725 - 5.825 GHz FCC: 28 dBm CE: 14 dBm SRRC: 20 dBm MIC: -
Operating Current/Voltage	1.2 A@7.4 V
Video Output Port	GL300E: HDMI GL300F: USB

Mobile Device Holder

GL300E: Built-in display device (5.5 inch screen, 1920×1080, 1000 cd/m², Android system, 4 GB RAM+16 GB ROM)

GL300F: Tablets and smart phones

INTELLIGENT FLIGHT BATTERY

Capacity	5870 mAh
Voltage	15.2 V
Battery Type	LiPo 4S
Energy	89.2 Wh
Net Weight	468 g
Charging Temperature Range	41° to 104°F (5° to 40°C)
Max Charging Power	160 W

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